

UTAH LAKE MESOCOSM STUDY

Ecological Section

"Diversity begets stability: Biodiversity loss may accelerate the destabilization of ecosystems"
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Progress Report 2023

By
David C. Richards, Ph.D.

OreoHelix Ecological, Vineyard UT 84059
Phone: 406.580.7816
Email: oreohelix@icloud.com

And

Sam Rushforth, Ph.D., and Sarah Rushforth
Rushforth Phycology, Provo, UT

Brett Marshall
River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT

Gustavious Williams, Ph.D.
Brigham Young University

Blake Wellard
Salt Lake City, UT

For
Richard Mickelsen
District Manager
Timpanogos Special Service District

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Chapter 1: Introduction, Justification, Goals

Utah Lake is but a small remnant of oligotrophic/mesotrophic Pluvial Lake Bonneville, once as large as present day Lake Michigan. Utah Lake is now a shallow, turbid, eutrophic, slightly saline, and exceedingly regulated lake managed as a storage reservoir. Its ecosystem has been severely degraded ever since first settlement by Americans of European descent over 150 years ago (Richards 2022). The lake continues to be a highly abused ecosystem.

Utah Lake has lost its ecological integrity¹ and by most quantitative, qualitative, and bioassessment based standards remains in poor health². The major loss of integrity occurred when the lake transitioned from a low entropy, stable, clear water state to a turbid, high entropy state of unknown stability shortly after settler population growth in the valley, circa late 1800s. This transition rapidly degraded the lake's native food web, water quality, and ecosystem function (Janetski 1990, Richards et al. 2022 a, b, c, d). Utah Lake's resilience to future perturbation and resistance to improvement (restoration) now appears to be compromised (Richards 2022b).

¹ **Ecological integrity** is the sum of physical, chemical, and biological integrity. Integrity implies an unimpaired condition or the quality or state of being complete or undivided; it implies correspondence with some original condition. (Karr 1993, 1996).

² **Ecological health** implies a flourishing condition, well-being, vitality, or prosperity. An ecosystem is healthy when it performs all its vital functions normally and properly; a healthy ecosystem is resilient, able to recover from many stresses; a healthy ecosystem requires minimal outside care" (Karr 1996).

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Presently, Utah Lake's ecosystem is dominated by only a handful of taxa including invasive Common Carp, other non-native fishes, and pollution tolerant chironomids. Primary production is co-dominated by water column primary production and strongly respiring benthic detritus, mostly derived from detrital 'rain' (Richards 2022b). The lake has low robustness (e.g., resistance), is well below optimal trophic functioning, and despite its long geologic history is now stalled at an 'immature' early succession stage, primarily because of chronic wave action and unnatural water level fluctuations that consistently disturb unconsolidated sediments and reset the food web, thus preventing maturation and stability of the system (Richards 2022b).

Ecosystems are highly complex thermodynamic systems. Despite their complexity, ecosystem dynamics must eventually succumb to the laws of thermodynamics (e.g., entropy) (Silow et al. 2011). However, living organisms and ecosystems have the ability to temporarily resist, postpone, or reverse entropy³ by capturing sunlight via photosynthesis and creating complex, open systems (Chang and Wen 2017, Silow et al. 2011). In ecosystems such as Utah Lake, the net entropy flow becomes negative (i.e., the lake absorbs negative entropy from its surroundings) and can function as a 'superorganism' (Aoki 1989). This phenomenon is known as exergy or ecoexergy⁴ (Jørgensen 1992). An ecosystem loses this ability as it degrades into a higher entropy state via ecosystem shifts and hysteresis. We discuss ecoexergy in more detail in the *State, Structure, and Function of Utah Lake's Ecosystem* section in Chapter 4: Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages.

Utah Lake has undergone a seismic ecosystem shift from a clear water state with high complexity (low entropy, high ecoexergy) to turbid, lower complexity state (high entropy, low ecoexergy) ever since settlement along its shores by Americans of European descent; a classic example of a large shallow lake rapidly increasing in entropy after deterioration of its native mature foodweb that for millennia evolved to resist entropy (Scheffer et al. 2001, Berrios et al. 2017, Silow et al. 2011). One of the key components in the increase in entropy and loss of ecoexergy in the Utah Lake ecosystem has been the loss of its robust near shore littoral zone (Richards et al. 2023).

Utah Lake once had a littoral zone that extended as far out into the lake as early explorers could see from its shoreline or from make-shift reed boats (Janetski 1990, Carter 2005). The Timpanogos Tribe, a dominant subgroup of Shoshone that lived in the area were known as the "Reed People" attesting to the bounty of aquatic vegetation (macrophytes) that thrived along Utah Lake's shores and littoral zone wetlands⁵. Historically, the lake was characterized by a more stable substrate

³ "Entropy is central to the [second law of thermodynamics](#), which states that the entropy of an isolated system left to spontaneous evolution cannot decrease with time. As a result, isolated systems evolve toward [thermodynamic equilibrium](#), where the entropy is highest. A consequence of the second law of thermodynamics is that certain processes are [irreversible](#)." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entropy>.

⁴ "Ecosystems can be characterized by the processes of transforming available energy, cycling materials, and replicating information. Ecosystems self-organize into hierarchical networks. An ecosystem is a thermodynamic system, and its dynamics follows the laws of thermodynamics. Eco-exergy is used to measure the following aspects of an ecosystem state: 1) the total complexity of ecosystem; 2) structure and functions of ecosystem; and 3) ability of an ecosystem to survive. Structural ecoexergy reflects: 1) efficiency of energy use by organisms; and 2) the ability of ecosystem to regulate interactions between organisms or groups of organisms." (Berrios et al. 2017, Silow et al. 2011).

⁵ Today the Timpanogos People point out that the names Yutahs, Ewuha or Eutah (Indian words spelled phonetically) also refer to the reeds that grow around Utah Lake that were used to make arrows. "eu" in their language means reed, and "tah" meaning arrow. Bancroft makes the same observation also referenced in his book *The works of Hubert Howe Bancroft; The Native Races 1883 – 1886* (Gottfredson 2022). Technically, the only 'reeds' native to Utah Lake were *Phragmites* sp.

than at present due to stabilizing biota including native aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, and bivalve mollusks (higher ecoexergy, lower entropy) (Richards et al. 2023, Richards 2022, Richards and Miller 2019, Libralato et al. 2006). Utah Lake's diverse and abundant molluscan assemblage was likely unsurpassed in the western USA (Richards 2017); a true Utah natural heritage that has all but vanished. The synergy between aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, and bivalves and other benthic invertebrates insured that water clarity in such a shallow lake was able to penetrate to its benthos throughout a large portion of the lake (Richards 2022a).

Utah Lake's littoral zone began to suffer and rapidly decline soon after settlement by nonnatives in the late 1800's. Reasons for this decline were numerous including water diversions, pollutants, and introduction of bioturbating Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and catfish (Family Ictaluridae), and the loss of native mollusks, among other factors (Janetski 1990, Carter 2005, Richards 2022, Richards and Miller 2017, 2019). Photosynthetically available light that can reach the substrate is now typically between 10 to 50 cm depth; any substrate deeper than this receives very little to no light (see our previous mesocosm reports). This means that almost the entirety of this shallow lake resides outside of the littoral zone especially during low lake levels when surviving emergent aquatic vegetation is outside of the lake. Presently, aquatic vegetation coverage is between 1 and 5% of the lake. Unfortunately, aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, and bivalves are no longer able to provide sediment stabilizing ecosystem services due to strong wave action that easily disturbs suspended sediments and dislodges their benthic habitat making it mostly unstable and uninhabitable (e.g., early successional, low ecoexergy, high entropy).

The open water limnetic (euphotic) zone in Utah Lake also varies from about 10 to 50 cm depending on conditions. This zone is now almost exclusively where primary production occurs in the form of photosynthetic phytoplankton including potentially harmful cyanobacteria. This is also where phytoplanktonic grazers, zooplankton reside. Consequently, the majority of secondary production occurs in the limnetic zone (Richards 2022). Domination by limnetic zone primary and secondary production as opposed to a balance with littoral zone production indicates degradation from past conditions in Utah Lake and is the reason the lake is often classified as eutrophic or hyper-eutrophic (Richards 2022a).

Almost all lakes have a well-developed profundal zone, the area located below the range of effective light penetration. The amount of area that a lake's profundal zone covers is dependent on many factors including depth, topography, climate, benthic substrate, trophic state, and the health and balance of biota in its food web. Most healthy lakes have a balance between littoral, limnetic, and profundal zones. This is not the case for Utah Lake; it is now almost completely dominated by the profundal zone. The lake's profundal zone substrate is comprised of a thick unconsolidated, easily disturbed, nutrient laden sediment that is homogenous throughout most of the lake bottom with very little structural habitat. Its benthic inhabitants are those relegated to survival under very low or no light conditions, low levels of dissolved oxygen (hypoxia), and unstable fine sediments that provide almost no structural habitat diversity. The lake's profundal zone only allows for low ecoexergy- high entropy primary and secondary production derived from heterotrophic decomposition including detrital 'rain' that falls from the limnetic zone primarily in summer months (Richards 2022a, b, c).

JUSTIFICATION

There is much concern as to the future of Utah Lake and what can be done to improve its condition (i.e., health, integrity), including the reduction of algal blooms and restoration of its native biota. However, there has been little to no effort expended to examine or understand the importance of the lake's food web and how top-down, trophic cascades effect and respond to current conditions or how biomanipulation may help restore its ecosystem health despite decades of research documenting their importance worldwide. Successful Utah Lake restoration cannot proceed without this understanding and holistic implementation.

LIMNOCORRAL STUDY GOALS

The overall goal of our 2023 mesocosm studies was to understand factors that influence nutrient cycling, algal blooms, food web dynamics, and ecosystem functioning that contribute to the impairment of the ecological health of Utah Lake, particularly the effects of wind driven wave turbulence. Results from this ongoing research will help direct managers on how best to initiate restoration⁶ essential to improving its health by using an integrated and adaptive management strategy (Richards 2021a, ongoing DWQ Utah Lake Science Panel studies, Richards 2021c, others).

The goal of the ecological component of the TSSD Utah Lake limnocorral study 2023 was to examine the direct and indirect effects of wave action, geochemical augmentation, juvenile and adult carp, and surrogate bivalves on:

1. Phytoplankton assemblages,
2. Benthic algae (periphyton) assemblages,
3. Zooplankton assemblages and,
4. Benthic invertebrate assemblages.

We postulated that the application of these treatments would have measurable direct and indirect effects on these four assemblages and that these non-target effects needed to be addressed. In addition, we expected that treatment effects would alter nutrient cycling and water quality in complicated interactions within the food web (see Williams et al. 2023 for more details of this project) (please review Richards et al. 2023, 2019, Richards and Miller 2019a, and Richards and Miller 2017 for a holistic overview of Utah Lake's unique foodweb and ecology).

We have discussed in detail in our previous mesocosm reports (Richards et al. 2022, 2023) Utah Lake's ecosystem function including the effects of carp, loss of native species, particularly mollusks and aquatic vegetation, and the now all too prevalent effects of wind driven wave turbulence that prevents ecosystem recovery. Our 2023 limnocorral studies presented in this report focus on the direct and indirect effects of wind driven wave action, bivalves, juvenile and adult carp, and geochemical augmentation on phytoplankton, benthic algae, zooplankton, and

⁶ Ecological restoration, "placing the ecosystem on a trajectory of recovery but not necessarily recovery to its former state so that it can persist, and its species can adapt and evolve" (Society Ecological Restoration).

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benthic invertebrate assemblages. We conclude this progress report with a viable alternative option for restoring Utah Lake.

CHAPTER 2: PHYTOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

By
David C. Richards, Ph.D.

OreoHelix Ecological, Vineyard UT 84059
Phone: 406.580.7816
Email: oreohelix@icloud.com

And

Sam Rushforth, Ph.D., and Sarah Rushforth
Rushforth Phycology, Provo, UT

SUMMARY

In this chapter, *Chapter 1: Phytoplankton Assemblages*, we present our findings on the effects of mesocosms and treatment within, on phytoplankton assemblages. Results presented confirm our previous mesocosm experimental outcomes and are in line with accepted and predicted ecological outcomes from decades of research of aquatic ecosystems worldwide. It is somewhat remarkable that we measured any ecological effects given the degraded state of Utah Lake that exhibits strong resistance to change, including improvement.

We found strong evidence that phytoplankton assemblages varied seasonally during the 2023 study, which was to be expected. These findings on their own provide much needed valuable information on the ecology and ecosystem function of Utah Lake.

We also found that mesocosms had measurable effects on assemblages simply by marginally reducing wave turbulence. Turbidity is arguably the primary direct and indirect factor limiting lake recovery. Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, and Euglenophyta had greater biovolumes inside mesocosms than in the lake, whereas Cyanophyta biovolumes seemed unaffected by mesocosms, except in the bivalve treatment where Cyanophyta decreased.

There was good-strong evidence that the effective number of taxa (ENT), evenness, and diversity improved inside mesocosms, presumably due to reduced turbidity. The negative effects of anthropogenically induced turbidity and sediment resuspension in Utah Lake as documented with these measures should be an alarm call for all Utah Lake management agencies, as these metrics are widely used to monitor water quality and are well known indicators of biodiversity, health, and integrity. A more diverse, balanced, and rich phytoplankton assemblage will dampen the intensity and occurrences of potentially harmful cyanobacteria blooms in the lake. Any potential improvement of phytoplankton assemblage ENT, evenness, and diversity by even slight reductions in turbidity and sediment resuspension should initiate committed management planning and action to alleviate this problem.

Individual mesocosm treatments also improved or altered phytoplankton assemblages evaluated at division and individual taxa levels. Taxa often responded differently to treatments between each sample event reflecting changing dynamics within mesocosms and the lake.

We also found diurnal seasonal changes in taxa biovolumes. Some taxa were more abundant in late morning than early afternoon and vice versa.

Treatments using surrogate filter feeding bivalves demonstrated that even under less-than-ideal conditions, bivalves have the ability to filter large amounts of phytoplankton. One of the most important findings of the bivalve treatments was that these filter feeders reduced cyanophyte biovolume often more so than other phytoplankton division biovolumes. Cyanophytes are the only phytoplankton division that can cause harmful algal blooms in Utah Lake. Reduction in cyanobacteria biovolume by bivalves is a major lake restoration finding. Bivalves also had other positive indirect effects on ecosystem function and are obviously a key component of Utah Lake

restoration. Hence, the importance of reestablishing native bivalves to Utah Lake's ecosystem cannot be overstated.

The two nutrient addition mesocosms showed mixed effects on phytoplankton biovolumes. Total phytoplankton biovolume was lower in the nutrient treatments in one treatment mesocosm after addition but spiked and then decreased in the second nutrient treatment mesocosm. This can be attributed to the spike in zooplankton densities that grazed the phytoplankton and is discussed in subsequent chapters. This also demonstrated the ability of Utah Lake to rapidly adjust to changes in nutrient availability via phytoplankton uptake and growth that is then synthesized and equilibrated throughout the ecosystem, likely via positive feedback loops.

Results from this 2023 study support our past mesocosm experimental findings and those of ecologists worldwide tasked with restoring shallow lake ecosystems. These results will also be directly applicable to ecosystem function models that we are developing to monitor and predict effects of restoration efforts aimed at reducing turbation and restoring Utah Lake's health including reduction of invasive species and reestablishment of native biota.

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INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we focus our attention on mesocom effects on phytoplankton assemblages. Subsequent chapters will examine zooplankton and benthic invertebrates and the interactions between biota and water chemistry.

METHODS

PHYTOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

STUDY SITE

Phytoplankton samples were collected inside limnocorrals (mesocosms) and outside of corals, in-lake (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Schematic of limnocorrals (LC) (mesocosms) and outside in-lake sample locations. Orange triangles are buoys. Schematic generated by River Continuum Concepts.

PHYTOPLANKTON SAMPLING AND PROCESSING

We used what Utah Division of Water Quality (DWQ) refers to as an 'integrated' sample or what Rushforth Phycology refers to as a 'surface' sample to collect phytoplankton from inside and outside corals. We inverted a 500 ml labeled plastic sample jar to elbow depth in the water and then slowly reinverted and lifted the jar to the surface to capture as much water equally at depth. Lugol's solution was added to the samples. Samples were then placed on ice and delivered to Rushforth Phycology as soon as possible, usually within one day.

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A total of 95 phytoplankton samples were collected and processed. See Table 1 for a listing of sample dates, and samples collected inside and outside of limnocorrals (mesocosms).

Table 1 List of sample events (dates), samples collected inside limnocorrals (LC), and outside of limnocorrals (Out). See Figure 1 for limnocorral locations and numbering.

Sample Event	Inside Mesocosms (LC)	Outside Mesocosms (Out)
June 16/17	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12	1a,1b, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7
August 17	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
August 31	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10,11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
September 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10,11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
September 27	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9

All algal taxonomies were performed by Rushforth Phycology (rushforthphycology.com), the leading algal taxonomy experts for Utah Lake and surrounding aquatic ecosystems, since 1974(?). Rushforth Phycology reported phytoplankton taxonomic results as percent relative density, cell mL⁻¹, and biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$)⁷. The most commonly used values are cell counts (cells mL⁻¹) and biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$). Linear regression analysis showed that both were highly significantly correlated ($R^2 = 0.94$ for *A. flosaquae* combined with all other taxa, $R^2 = 1.00$ when modeled separately) (Richards et al. 2023). Biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) was chosen for this 2023 analysis, as we consider biovolume to be the most ecologically relevant measure.

TREATMENTS

Several treatments within mesocosms (limnocorrals) were applied during the study. These included:

- Juvenile carp (eggs, YOY)
- Adult carp
- Bivalve mollusks
- Geochem
- Nutrients
- Rhodamine⁸
- Control

CARP TREATMENTS

Carp laid approximately 2000 eggs on the inside of mesocosm 1 prior to lowering of the mesocosms skirt and were allowed to hatch into larvae and then YOY after the skirt was lowered and secured to substrate circa August 8, 2023. Fertilized carp eggs were also collected from TSSD outfall on multiple occasions in June through late July. Carp egg laying continued well into late- July due to the unusually high, cold, water year. Eggs were placed into aerated plastic pools at TSSD and allowed to hatch into larvae throughout late June and most of July awaiting mesocosm stocking. Larvae and early YOY were fed zooplankton and chironomid larvae collected from the nearby native plant nursery or TSSD experimental ponds every two or three days. Approximately 1000 early < 2.5

⁷ Cell (bio)volume values were specifically developed for Utah Lake phytoplankton by Rushforth Phycology.

⁸ Rhodamine typically is rapidly biodegraded either by bacteria or phytoplankton. Consequently, we considered this as part of the nutrient addition treatment.

cm juvenile YOY were then placed into mesocosm 5 on August 9, 2023. Four adult carp were captured from TSSD outlet on August 4, 2023, and two were placed into mesocosm 10 and two into mesocosm 22. Mesocosm structural integrity was compromised throughout the study and the number of individual fish that remained in mesocosms was unknown except that adult carp escaped sometime prior to August 25, 2023, in mesocosm 10. Adult carp were present in mesocosm 11 at least until September 4, 2024.

BIVALVE TREATMENT

Surrogate bivalves, *Corbicula* sp. for extirpated natives, *Anodonta* sp. and near extirpated Sphaeriidae were placed into six cages shown in Figure 2 and the placed into mesocosms 6 and 9. Three cages were placed on the bottom of the mesocosm 6 or suspended on poles inside mesocosm 9. Cages and bivalves were removed at the end of the study and bivalves destroyed.

Figure 2 Bivalves were placed into these types of cages, latched, and zip tied to prevent opening after being deployed into mesocosms 6 and 9.

STATISTICAL METHODS

Four to five letter codes were made for each phytoplankton taxon, typically the first two letters of the genus name and the first two letters of the species name unless there were duplicates (Table 2). Seven to eight- digit location and sampling date codes were also developed for use in analyses.

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMS) ordination was used to compare phytoplankton assemblage dis(similarity) relationships statistically and visually between corrals and dates. Ordination techniques are often more informative than hypothesis-testing approaches for exploring relationships between multivariate ecological assemblages or communities (McCune and Grace 2002). In general, ordination is the ordering of objects along axes according to their (dis)similarities; the main objective of ordination is to reduce many-dimensional relationships into

a small number of more easily interpretable dimensions (i.e., axes on a plot). The strongest correlation structure in the data is extracted and is then used to position objects in ordination space. Objects that are close in the ordination space are more similar than objects distant in ordination space (McCune and Mefford 2011).

NMS was used in these analyses because it has been shown to be robust and highly informative for understanding ecological relationships. NMS ordination is often more broadly applicable for ecological studies than other ordination techniques because it does not require relationships among variables to be linear (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). NMS ordination permits the visualization of the multidimensional relationships of phytoplankton assemblages into a more easily visualized, lower dimensional space. Dimensional reduction obviously creates some distortion in relationships between samples. The level of reduction in distortion is measured as 'stress', where lower stress values equal less distortion. NMS plots with stress values of 15% (0.15) or less are typically considered to be a good representation of the data and stress values lower than 10% (0.10) are considered excellent representations (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010).

Several distance measures were used and evaluated including Sorensen (Bray-Curtis), Relative Sorensen, Jaccard, Euclidean, Relative Euclidean, and Morisita-Horn. NMS analysis was run for 250 iterations using the real data and 250 iterations in randomized Monte Carlo simulations. Best-fit models were selected based on stable final stress < 0.15 and 3-dimensional solutions or less. NMS ordinations were rotated using varimax rotation to maximize variation along the axes and extracted as univariate scores. Consequently, the final ordinations can be rotated either vertically or horizontally without effecting the results. Centroid labels and convex hulls of months were added to the ordinations to aid in the interpret the relationships. Post hoc proportion of variance represented by each axis was calculated based on the R^2 value between distance in the ordination space and distance in the original space.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP), a non-parametric multivariate method was used to formally test the hypothesis of no differences in phytoplankton assemblages between months. MRPP has the advantage of not requiring distributional assumptions such as multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance and thus is often preferred over perMANOVA for analyzing multivariate ecological data (McCune and Grace 2002). The same distance measure was used for each MRPP analyses as was for corresponding NMS models. The chance-corrected within-group test statistic, A (and associated p-value) was used to evaluate the hypothesis of no difference in groupings (McCune and Grace 2002). Post hoc multiple comparisons were also made when appropriate.

We used Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) in PC-ORD to determine taxa that were strong indicators of sampling events (seasonal). ISA used Dufrêne and Legendre's (1997) method of calculating species indicator values that provided a simple, intuitive solution. The method combined information on biovolumes of phytoplankton taxa abundance for each sample event and the faithfulness of occurrence of a taxa in a particular sample event. ISA produced indicator values for each taxon in each group. These were then tested for statistical significance using a randomization technique (see Appendix 4 for more detailed information on ISA method).

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All multivariate and additional analyses including rank abundance and descriptive summary statistics were made using PC-ORD for Windows Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018) using Parallels Desktop 19.2.1 for Mac virtual platform.

Regression analyses were selected using the most appropriate model including linear, Poisson, fractional, and negative binomial. Best fit regression models were chosen based on lowest log likelihood, AIC, and BIC values. ANOVAs and MANOVAs were also conducted where appropriate. Descriptive statistics were also calculated for select data. Statistical analyses and graphics were made using Stata 16.1 for Mac (Intel 64-bit) (StataCorp 2021). Multivariate assemblage analyses were conducted using PC-ORD Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018). Graphical representations of statistical models were made using either Stata or PC-ORD. Details of additional statistical methods not listed here are described in individual Results sections.

RESULTS

We found and identified 70 phytoplankton taxa in our 2023 mesocosm study (Table 2). These taxa were from several algal divisions including Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, Cyanophyta, Chrysophyta, Cryptophyta, Dinophyta, and Euglenophyta (taxa grouped by Division are in Appendix 5).

Table 2 Phytoplankton taxa found in 2023 mesocosm study with taxon codes used in analyses. 70 taxa occurrences. Taxa listed by Division are in Appendix 5.

Taxon	Code
<i>Actinastrum gracillimum</i> Smith	ACGR
<i>Anabaena</i> species	ANSP
<i>Anabaenopsis</i> species	ANASP
<i>Ankistrodesmus faatus</i> (Corda) Ralfs	ANFA
<i>Ankyra judayi</i> (Smith) Fott (= <i>Schroederia judayi</i> (Smith) Fott)	ANJU
<i>Aphanizomenon flosaquae</i> Ralfs ex Bornet & Flahault	APFL
<i>Aphanocapsa incerta</i> (Lemmermann) G.Cronberg & Komárek (= <i>Microcystis incerta</i> (Lemmermann) Cronberg & Komárek)	APIN
<i>Aphanocapsa</i> species	APSP
<i>Aphanothece</i> species	APHSP
<i>Asterionella formosa</i> Hassall	ASFO
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i>)	AUGR
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> (Müller) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i>)	AUGR
centric diatoms species	CENTDIAT
centric diatoms species 2	CENTDIAT 2
<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i> (Müller) Dujardin	CEHI
<i>Chlamydomonas</i> species	CHLSP
<i>Chroococciopsis</i> species	CHROSP
<i>Chroococcus dispersus</i> (Keissler) Lemmermann	CHDI
<i>Chroococcus minor</i> (Kützing) Nägeli	CHMI
<i>Chroococcus turgidus</i> (Kützing) Nägeli	CHTU

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<i>Chroomonas</i> species	CHRSP
<i>Closteriopsis acicularis</i> (Chodat) Beher & Swale	CLAC
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> (Lemmermann) Lemmermann	CLLO
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> var. <i>tropica</i> West & West	CLLO
<i>Cosmarium</i> species	COSP
<i>Crucigenia fenestrata</i> (Schmidle) Schmidle	CRFE
<i>Crucigenia quadrata</i> Morren	CRQU
<i>Crucigenia</i> species	CRUSP
<i>Crucigeniella rectangularis</i> (Nägeli) Komárek (= <i>Willea rectangularis</i> (Braun) John, Wynne & Tsarenko)	CRRE
<i>Cryptomonas</i> species	CRSP
<i>Cylindrospermopsis</i> species	CYSP
<i>Cylindrospermum</i> species	CYSP
<i>Desmodesmus bicaudatus</i> (Dedusenko) .Tsarenko	DEBI
<i>Desmodesmus bicellularis</i> (Chodat) An, Friedl & Hegewald	DEBI
<i>Desmodesmus communis</i> (Hegewald) Hegewald	DECO
<i>Desmodesmus intermedius</i> (Chodat) Hegewald	DEIN
<i>Desmodesmus opoliensis</i> (Richter) Hegewald	DEOP
<i>Desmodesmus</i> species	DESP
<i>Dictyosphaerium ehrenbergianum</i> Nägeli	DIEH
<i>Dolichospermum circinalis</i> (Brébisson) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek (= <i>Anabaena circinalis</i> Rabenhorst)	DOCI
<i>Dolichospermum</i> species	DOSP
<i>Eremosphaera gigas</i> (Archer) Fott & Kalina (= <i>Oocystis gigas</i> Archer)	ERGI
<i>Euglena</i> species	EUSP
<i>Gregiochloris lacustris</i> (Chodat) Marvan, Komárek & Comas (= <i>Quadrigula lacustris</i> (Chodat) Smith)	GRLA
<i>Gymnodinium</i> species	GYSP
<i>Kirchneriella lunaris</i> (Kirchner) Möbius (= <i>Kirchneriella lunata</i> Schmidle)	KILU
<i>Komma</i> species	KOSP
<i>Lepocinclis acus</i> (O.F.Müller) B.Marin & Melkonian in Marin	LEAC
<i>Lepocinclis</i> species	LESP
<i>Lyngbya</i> species	LYSP
<i>Melosira varians</i> Agardh	MEVA
<i>Merismopedia</i> species	MESP
<i>Oocystis borgei</i> Snow	OOBO
<i>Oocystis</i> species	OOSP
<i>Oscillatoria princeps</i> Vaucher ex Gomont	OSPR
<i>Oscillatoria</i> species	OSSP
<i>Pectinodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Hegewald, Wolf, Keller, Friedl & Krienitz (= <i>Acutodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Tsarenko)	PEPE
<i>Pediastrum angulosum</i> Ehrenberg ex Meneghini	PEAN

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<i>Pediastrum duplex</i> Meyen (= <i>Pediastrum duplex</i> var. <i>clathratum</i> Meyen)	PEDU
pennate diatoms	PENNDIAT
<i>Peridinium</i> species	PESP
<i>Phacus</i> species	PHASP
<i>Phormidium</i> species	PHSP
<i>Pteromonas</i> species	PTSP
<i>Scenedesmus ellipticus</i> Corda	SCEL
<i>Scenedesmus</i> species	SCSP
<i>Schroederia setigera</i> (Schröder) Lemmermann	SCSE
<i>Sphaerocystis schroeteri</i> Chodat	SPSC
<i>Trachelomonas</i> species	TRSP
Unknown filamentous cyanophyte	UNFICYAN

We estimated that there were between 83 and 102 taxa in the study area based on rarefaction analysis, first-order jackknife, second-order jackknife, and Chao estimators given our sampling effort (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Rarefaction curve of number of tax predicted in our study area based on sample effort.

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Figure 4 Rank abundances of phytoplankton encountered in our mesocosm study, 2023. logSum was used to emphasize the dominance by few taxa particularly APFL, DOCI, PHSP, CHLSP, etc. Rank abundance metrics are in Table 3.

Table 3 Phytoplankton taxa, rank abundance, total biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$), rank frequency, and number of occurrences that were found in this study.

Taxon	Rank Abundance	Sum	Rank Frequency	Frequency (number of occurrences)
APFL	1	1.69E+09	15	31
DOCI	2	3.85E+08	4	69
PHSP	3	1.64E+08	12	35
CHLSP	4	7.87E+07	2	85
CEHI	5	5.34E+07	7	49
CRSP	6	2.99E+07	6	60
CHRSP	7	1.23E+07	22	18
PENNDIAT	8	1.08E+07	1	86
OSPR	9	5.36E+06	52	1
EUSP	10	4.61E+06	10	41
SPSC	11	3.77E+06	19	22
CLLO	12	3.49E+06	11	41
DOSP	13	2.25E+06	28	9
CENTDIAT	14	2.21E+06	3	77
AUGR	15	2.19E+06	5	61
APSP	16	1.72E+06	14	31
OOBO	17	1.46E+06	8	49
CRFE	18	514080	20	20
SCSE	19	347480	9	47

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CRQU	20	324800	24	16
CHROSP	21	322784	65	1
SCEL	22	301997	26	11
KOSP	23	274925	17	25
ANJU	24	271320	16	29
LYSP	25	268800	43	3
ERGI	26	253344	32	6
ANSP	27	222869	49	2
PEDU	28	217280	35	5
PHASP	29	163386	25	14
APIN	30	145040	44	3
OOSP	31	129024	40	4
CHDI	32	125798	18	23
OSSP	33	101094	66	1
CYSP	34	79002	29	9
COSP	35	78400	64	1
UNFICYAN	36	75600	51	1
PESP	37	65800	37	4
PTSP	38	59570	21	20
SCSP	39	57948.8	42	3
GYSP	40	51884	33	6
DEBI	41	48646.4	23	17
CHMI	42	38561.6	27	9
CRUSP	43	36470.4	31	8
LESP	44	33600	60	1
ANFA	45	33196.8	13	34
CHSP	46	24796.8	47	2
APHSP	47	24024	36	4
MEVA	48	21616	62	1
DECO	49	20160	30	9
CHTU	50	19790.4	50	1
LEAC	51	19000.8	55	1
DESP	52	15120	57	1
PEPE	53	14000	45	3
ASFO	54	12868.8	53	1
TRSP	55	12314.4	39	4
MESP	56	11289.6	34	5
PEAN	57	11222.4	61	1

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DEOP	58	8400	41	3
ACGR	59	6316.8	59	1
DIEH	60	6092.8	63	1
CRRE	61	5600	58	1
GRLA	62	5600	38	4
CLAC	63	3987.2	56	1
ANASP	64	3942.4	54	1
DEIN	65	3225.6	46	2
KILU	66	1008	48	2

SEASONAL CHANGES IN PHYTOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

We found strong evidence of seasonal phytoplankton assemblage patterns. We developed a good-excellent fit NMS model for the phytoplankton assemblages showing seasonal changes. The NMS model had a 3-dimensional solution, with final stress = 11.00, final instability < 0.0001 at 87 iterations using a Relative Sorensen distance matrix. The NMS model explained 0.87 seasonal variability in assemblages with Axis 1 = 0.42, Axis 2 = 0.26, and Axis 3 = 0.18 (Figure 6 and Figure 7). The NMS model showed that phytoplankton assemblages varied seasonally (Figure 6 and Figure 7) as we have reported elsewhere in Utah Lake and as occurs throughout temperate regions, although individual taxa biovolumes in Utah Lake can differ annually (Richards et al. years). Some of the less common taxa varied more so than did the common taxa annually. 2023 was a very high-water year compared to recent years and likely affected assemblages and taxa relative abundances.

Figure 6 NMS Axis 1 and Axis 2 showing seasonal trend in phytoplankton assemblages starting in June progressing through summer and into early autumn when assemblages once again started to resemble early summer assemblages.

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Figure 7 NMS Axis 1 vs. Axis 3 and Axis 2 vs. Axis 3 showing differences and similarities of phytoplankton assemblages among and between sampling events.

NMS axes were determined by biovolumes of individual taxa. Table 4 provides Pearson (parametric r , and R^2) and Kendall (τ) correlations of taxa with each of the three NMS axes.

Table 4 Pearson and Kendall correlations with NMS ordination axes. Positive values are to the right and top of axes, negative values are to the left and bottom of axes.

Taxon	Axis 1			Axis 2			Axis 3		
	r	R^2	τ	r	R^2	τ	r	R^2	τ
ANFA	0.186	0.035	0.108	0.119	0.014	0.057	-0.124	0.015	-0.142
ACGR	0.115	0.013	0.096	-0.045	0.002	-0.04	0.049	0.002	0.071
ANJU	-0.55	0.303	-0.534	-0.198	0.039	-0.068	0.033	0.001	0.084
ANASP	0.108	0.012	0.083	-0.032	0.001	-0.006	0.052	0.003	0.074
ANSP	0.121	0.015	0.1	-0.046	0.002	-0.023	0.135	0.018	0.141
APFL	-0.524	0.275	-0.468	-0.553	0.305	-0.536	-0.117	0.014	-0.069
APIN	-0.173	0.03	-0.123	0.262	0.069	0.202	-0.01	0	0.076
APHSP	0.064	0.004	0.048	0.202	0.041	0.162	-0.029	0.001	0.034
APSP	-0.179	0.032	-0.18	-0.386	0.149	-0.392	-0.084	0.007	0.013
ASFO	-0.109	0.012	-0.083	0.058	0.003	0.065	0.317	0.1	0.145
AUGR	-0.079	0.006	-0.015	-0.498	0.248	-0.356	0.223	0.05	0.241
CEHI	0.224	0.05	0.138	-0.214	0.046	-0.305	0.586	0.343	0.387
CENTDIAT	-0.037	0.001	-0.086	0.346	0.119	0.316	0.235	0.055	0.204
CHDI	-0.15	0.022	-0.144	0.175	0.031	0.108	-0.118	0.014	-0.116

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CHLSP	-0.029	0.001	-0.008	-0.407	0.166	-0.349	0.357	0.127	0.369
CHMI	-0.252	0.064	-0.23	-0.076	0.006	0.065	0.14	0.02	0.174
CHRSP	-0.111	0.012	-0.358	0.059	0.004	0.179	0.318	0.101	0.023
CHROSP	-0.137	0.019	-0.108	-0.142	0.02	-0.127	-0.039	0.001	-0.04
CHSP	-0.103	0.011	-0.141	0.141	0.02	0.021	0.114	0.013	0.093
CHTU	-0.1	0.01	-0.068	0.153	0.023	0.111	-0.156	0.024	-0.139
CLAC	0.126	0.016	0.114	-0.036	0.001	-0.015	-0.093	0.009	-0.102
CLLO	0.207	0.043	0.171	0.091	0.008	0.088	-0.167	0.028	-0.143
COSP	0.042	0.002	0.019	0.088	0.008	0.071	-0.068	0.005	-0.071
CRFE	0.338	0.114	0.252	-0.019	0	0.043	0.111	0.012	0.079
CRQU	-0.34	0.116	-0.285	0.341	0.116	0.285	0.043	0.002	0.145
CRRE	0.108	0.012	0.083	-0.032	0.001	-0.006	0.052	0.003	0.074
CRSP	-0.04	0.002	0.161	-0.114	0.013	-0.022	-0.112	0.013	-0.097
CRUSP	-0.331	0.11	-0.27	-0.365	0.133	-0.341	-0.075	0.006	-0.027
CYSP	0.201	0.041	0.218	-0.065	0.004	-0.038	0.133	0.018	0.253
DEBI	0.012	0	0.006	-0.151	0.023	-0.01	0.072	0.005	0.091
DECO	-0.023	0.001	-0.101	0.026	0.001	0.059	0.202	0.041	0.17
DIEH	0.108	0.012	0.083	-0.032	0.001	-0.006	0.052	0.003	0.074
DEIN	0.125	0.016	0.089	0.045	0.002	0.08	-0.005	0	-0.014
DEOP	-0.021	0	-0.029	-0.051	0.003	-0.002	-0.072	0.005	-0.039
DESP	-0.105	0.011	-0.077	-0.13	0.017	-0.108	-0.035	0.001	-0.022
DOCI	0.452	0.204	0.453	-0.344	0.118	-0.448	-0.106	0.011	-0.05
DOSP	-0.128	0.017	-0.106	-0.14	0.02	0.008	0.022	0	0.228
ERGI	0.144	0.021	0.05	-0.013	0	0.092	0.168	0.028	0.102
EUSP	-0.127	0.016	0.003	-0.358	0.128	-0.362	0.109	0.012	0.321
GRLA	-0.148	0.022	-0.105	0.107	0.011	0.129	0.188	0.035	0.159
GYSO	0.2	0.04	0.162	-0.058	0.003	-0.004	0.072	0.005	0.195
KILU	0.118	0.014	0.079	-0.029	0.001	0.015	0.217	0.047	0.149
KOSP	-0.178	0.032	-0.131	-0.27	0.073	-0.123	-0.056	0.003	-0.009
LEAC	0.067	0.004	0.034	-0.017	0	0.019	0.253	0.064	0.139
LESP	0.102	0.01	0.071	-0.034	0.001	-0.012	0.101	0.01	0.093
LYSP	0.213	0.045	0.214	-0.112	0.013	-0.133	-0.135	0.018	-0.162
MESP	-0.067	0.004	-0.015	-0.158	0.025	-0.146	-0.025	0.001	0.04
MEVA	0.005	0	-0.009	0.165	0.027	0.123	0.001	0	0.034
OBOO	-0.222	0.049	-0.095	0.328	0.108	0.278	0.044	0.002	0.029
OOSP	-0.236	0.056	-0.191	0.024	0.001	-0.071	-0.04	0.002	0.018
OSPR	-0.067	0.004	-0.037	-0.098	0.01	-0.09	0.151	0.023	0.123
OSSP	-0.092	0.009	-0.056	-0.12	0.014	-0.099	-0.032	0.001	-0.009

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PEAN	0.097	0.009	0.059	-0.024	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.001	0.065
PEDU	0.053	0.003	-0.01	0.203	0.041	0.17	0.015	0	0.032
PENNDIAT	0.118	0.014	-0.005	0.023	0.001	0.11	0	0	0.217
PEPE	0.021	0	0.039	-0.137	0.019	-0.101	0.011	0	0.048
PESP	-0.121	0.015	-0.077	-0.03	0.001	-0.009	0.079	0.006	0.079
PHASP	0.285	0.081	0.279	-0.095	0.009	-0.048	0.433	0.188	0.207
PHSP	0.327	0.107	0.335	-0.117	0.014	-0.109	0.466	0.217	0.331
PTSP	0.291	0.085	0.133	-0.122	0.015	-0.036	0.382	0.146	0.329
SCEL	-0.039	0.001	-0.032	-0.127	0.016	-0.067	0.107	0.012	0.115
SCSE	0.254	0.065	0.277	0.162	0.026	0.101	-0.017	0	-0.083
SCSP	-0.135	0.018	-0.083	-0.189	0.036	-0.166	0.014	0	0.053
SPSC	-0.087	0.008	-0.09	0.405	0.164	0.405	-0.321	0.103	-0.262
TRSP	0.056	0.003	0.014	0.076	0.006	0.041	-0.05	0.002	-0.033
UNFICYAN	-0.132	0.017	-0.099	0.181	0.033	0.133	-0.053	0.003	-0.049

Multi-response Permutation Procedures (MRPP) results confirmed our NMS results that showed seasonal changes in phytoplankton assemblages. MRPP provided very strong evidence that phytoplankton assemblages differed seasonally ($T = -48.19$, $A = 0.36$, $p < 0.001$) and between all sampling events (Table 5).

Table 5 MRPP results provided strong evidence ($p < 0.01$) that phytoplankton assemblages differed between and among sample events.

Sample Events	T	A	p
17-Aug vs.31-Aug	-21.80	0.31	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 12-Sep	-22.00	0.34	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 27-Sep	-22.81	0.30	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 16-Jun	-19.85	0.29	< 0.01
31-Aug vs. 12-Sep	-14.91	0.17	< 0.01
31-Aug vs. 27-Sep	-22.25	0.25	< 0.01
31-Aug vs.16-Jun	-20.34	0.25	< 0.01
12-Sep vs. 27-Sep	-20.84	0.25	< 0.01
12-Sep vs.16-Jun	-19.33	0.26	< 0.01
27-Sep vs.16-Jun	-16.59	0.15	< 0.01

SEASONAL PHYTOPLANKTON INDICATOR TAXA

In the previous section we showed that phytoplankton assemblages differed seasonally (sample events). In this section we demonstrate that many individual phytoplankton taxa were strong seasonal indicators based on our Indicator Species Analysis (Table 6). For example, several Chlorophyta taxa were strong indicators of early summer (June16) samples including *Ankyra judayi* (ANJU), *Crucigenia quadrata* (CRQU) *Oocystis borgei* (OOBO), and *Desmodesmus communis*

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(DECO), as well as Bacillariophyta centric diatoms (CENTDIAT) the Cryptophyta taxon, *Chroomonas* species (CHRSP) and the Cyanophyta taxon *Aphanocapsa incerta* (Table 6).

By mid-summer (August 17 and 31) indicator taxa transitioned more to Cyanophyta and Dinophyta taxa including the cyanophyte *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* and the dinophyte *Ceratium hirudinella*, as well as the euglenophyte, *Euglena* sp. (Table 6).

In early September (September 12) there were only two strong indicator taxa, the cyanophytes, *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI) and *Lynbya* species (LYSP) (Table 6). By September 27, the phytoplankton assemblage was more characterized by different chlorophyte taxa *Ankistrodesmus falcatus* (ANFA), *Schroederia setigera* (SCSE), *Sphaerocystis Schroeteri* (SPSC) and *Closteriopsis longissimi* (CLLO) as well as two cyanophyte taxa, *Chroococcus disperses* CHDI and *Aphanothece species* (APHSP) (Table 6).

Table 6 Seasonal phytoplankton Indicator taxa. See Table 2 for taxa names.

Sample Event	Taxon	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	IV from Randomized groups		
			Mean	Std. Dev	p *
June16	ANJU	45.5	13.2	3.82	0.0002
	CHRSP	81.1	22.2	7.6	0.0002
	CRQU	85.2	9.9	3.94	0.0002
	OOBO	41.4	17.3	3.48	0.0004
	GRLA	25	5.6	3.14	0.0018
	APIN	18.8	5.3	3.24	0.0044
	CENTDIAT	29.4	22.5	2.88	0.0224
	CHMI	17.3	7.7	3.62	0.0236
	CHSP	12.5	6.1	2.18	0.0272
	DECO	14.7	7.7	3.66	0.0646
August17	APFL	99	14.3	4.28	0.0002
	APSP	50.9	14.2	4.15	0.0002
	AUGR	43.6	19.9	3.42	0.0002
	CRUSP	40	6.9	3.38	0.0002
	EUSP	46.4	17.7	4.87	0.0002
	KOSP	37.4	13.1	4.47	0.0008
	SCSP	15	5	3.14	0.0358
August31	CEHI	75.7	19.1	4.52	0.0002
	CHLSP	49.4	27.6	4.45	0.0002
	CYSP	45	8.3	4.02	0.0002
	PHASP	45.3	9	3.51	0.0002
	PHSP	92.2	16.4	4.89	0.0002
	PTSP	68.8	10.9	3.86	0.0002

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	CRFE	28.2	10.5	3.58	0.0016
	ERGI	17	6.7	3.56	0.0206
	GYSP	12.9	6.8	3.61	0.072
September12	DOCI	49.5	23.4	4.38	0.0002
	LYSP	15.8	5.1	3.03	0.0088
September27	ANFA	45.8	15.5	4.54	0.0002
	SCSE	44.6	17.2	3.69	0.0002
	SPSC	45.6	11.9	4.08	0.0002
	CLLO	35.1	15.7	3.74	0.0006
	CHDI	30.5	11.4	3.62	0.0008
	APHSP	20	5.7	3.26	0.0056

* Proportion of randomized trials with indicator value equal to or exceeding the observed indicator value. $p = (1 + \text{number of runs} \geq \text{observed}) / (1 + \text{number of randomized runs})$.

MESOCOSM EFFECTS ON PHYTOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

In this section we provide strong evidence that the mesocosms themselves (sin treatment effects) affected phytoplankton assemblages in August and late September but not in June or early September (Table 7).

Table 7 Multi-Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP) results of mesocosm effects (inside vs. outside of mesocosms) on phytoplankton assemblages by sample event. A = chance corrected within group agreement statistic.

Sample Event	A	p
June16	< 0.001	0.43
Aug17	0.06	0.04
Aug31	0.07	0.01
Sept12	-0.01	0.53
Sept27	0.09	< 0.01

TAXA RICHNESS AND DIVERSITY

We did not find evidence that mesocosms affected richness (number of taxa) at any sample event (Figure 8). However, and more importantly, we found very good evidence that mesocosms increased the effective number of taxa (ENT) on the August 17 and August 31 sample event, and it appeared that this occurred on the September sampling events as well (Figure 9). ENT only ranged from about 1 to 5 or 6 (Figure 9) as compared to the total number of taxa found at each sample event inside and outside of corrals roughly between 9 and 15 or 16 (Figure 8) and the total number of taxa found during the study, 70 (Table 1). Such very low ENT signifies major impairment to the lake and any increase in ENT is vital to the lake's health.

Figure 8 Taxa Richness, S inside and outside of mesocosm by sampling event. Mean and 95% CIs

Figure 9. Effective number of taxa, ENT inside and outside of mesocosms on five sample events, 2023. Mean and 95% CIs. ANOVA August 17: $F = 6.22$, $p = 0.02$, ANOVA August 31: $F = 6.98$, $p = 0.02$.

We found evidence that mesocosms improved evenness in August 17, August 31, and September 12 sample events, but not June 16 and September 27 sampling events using ANOVA (Figure 10).

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Figure 10 Taxa Evenness, E inside and outside of mesocosm by sampling event. ANOVA results: Aug17 ($F = 8.70$, $p = 0.01$), Aug31 ($F = 5.46$, $p = 0.03$), Sept12 ($F = 4.43$, $p = 0.05$).

Diversity was consistently improved inside mesocosms than in the lake after the June 16 sample event with statistical supporting evidence for greater diversity inside mesocosms on August 17, August 31, and September 12 sample events (Figure 11 and Figure 12).

Figure 11 Shannon Diversity, H inside and outside of mesocosms by sample events. Mean and 95% CIs. ANOVA results: August 17 $F=8.85$, $p=0.01$, August 31 $F=7.49$, $p=0.01$, and September 12 $F=4.21$, $p=0.056$.

Figure 12 Simpson Diversity, D: ANOVA Aug17 (F = 7.83, p = 0.01), Aug31 (F = 4.71, p = 0.04), Sept12 (F = 4.65, p = 0.05).

It did not appear the reduction in wave turbulence by mesocosms affected total phytoplankton biovolume, mostly because Cyanophyta dominated the assemblage and appeared to be generally unaffected by mesocosms (Figure 13). However, most of the phytoplankton divisions appeared to be seasonally affected by mesocosms, particularly Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, Cryptophyta, and Dinophyta (Figure 15). Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, Euglenophyta, and Cryptophyta were consistently more abundant inside mesocosms than in the lake, whereas Dinophyta were more abundant in the lake than in the mesocosms when they were at their peak abundance August 31 (Figure 15). Cyanophyta abundance on the other hand did not appear to be affected by mesocosms (Figure 15). The likely reason phytoplankton division biovolumes, other than cyanophytes, were often greater inside mesocosms was reduced turbidity.

Figure 13 Phytoplankton biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) inside and outside of mesocosms by sample event.

Figure 14 shows the relative abundances of phytoplankton biovolumes inside and outside of mesocosms on the four sampling dates.

Figure 14 Relative abundances of phytoplankton divisions inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event.

Figure 15 shows biovolumes of phytoplankton divisions inside and outside of mesocosms.

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Figure 15 Phytoplankton Division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event.

Table 8 presents phytoplankton division biovolumes within each sample from each of the four sampling dates, 2023.

Table 8 Phytoplankton Division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) for each sample inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event. There was only one occurrence of Chrysophyta Aug 17, OUT1 = 156,800.

Sample Event	Corral	Bacillariophyta	Chlorophyta	Cryptophyta	Cyanophyta	Dinophyta	Euglenophyta	Division Total
JUNE 16	LC 1	160,849	121,520	10,332	54,880	0	0	347,581
	LC 3	87,612	92,025	14,465	13,300	0	0	207,402
	LC 4	93,296	69,272	24,108	14,039	0	0	200,715
	LC 5	114,660	860,126	6,199	19,790	0	0	1,000,776
	LC 6	70,364	31,976	0	3,226	0	0	105,566
	LC 7	30,800	102,382	689	367,391	0	0	501,262
	LC 8	107,408	227,343	4,133	244,927	0	0	583,811
	LC 12	78,596	90,947	5,510	4,435	13,160	0	192,648
	OUT 1A	72,912	38,394	689	122,464	0	0	234,458
	OUT 1B	104,642	85,926	3,444	122,464	0	0	316,476

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	OUT 2	133,084	224,403	26,174	158,043	0	0	541,705	
	OUT 3	52,528	116,234	11,021	213,167	0	0	392,949	
	OUT 4	127,792	116,130	12,104,400	2,957	0	12,869	12,364,148	
	OUT 5	93,296	169,845	28,241	53,416	13,160	0	357,958	
	OUT 6	180,124	65,512	53,038	14,778	0	0	313,452	
	OUT 7	163,800	117,121	21,353	39,956	0	6,160	348,390	
AUG 17	LC 1	303,408	4,195,761	454,138	24,952,603	2,017,344	221,760	32,145,014	
	LC 2	134,568	4,818,257	340,603	27,355,742	967,747	209,440	33,826,358	
	LC 3	182,818	7,350,644	141,918	10,463,872	1,492,546	197,120	19,828,917	
	LC 5	142,072	1,954,775	15,154	162,308,558	0	5,835	164,426,394	
	LC 6	349,188	5,001,259	5,109,048	186,596,290	605,203	517,440	198,178,428	
	LC 7	129,192	4,651,315	3,150,580	148,116,780	0	868,560	156,916,427	
	LC 8	246,792	2,511,356	0	103,529,236	0	295,680	106,583,064	
	LC 9	140,660	1,492,582	263,562	125,387,824	374,650	74,058	127,733,336	
	LC 10	894,376	107,797	28,384	979,709	201,734	0	2,212,000	
	LC 11	173,656	3,139,508	1,816,550	78,541,554	605,203	186,852	84,463,324	
	LC 12	168,504	592,323	170,302	30,660,302	0	12,320	31,603,751	
		OUT 1	30,408	420,067	2,755	67,306,607	0	36,960	67,953,598
		OUT 2	51,296	430,298	6,888	157,619,952	806,938	36,960	158,952,332
		OUT 3	67,760	509,292	0	94,039,019	134,490	0	94,750,561
		OUT 4	27,832	693,560	5,510	111,917,702	134,490	30,475	112,809,570
		OUT 5	29,120	160,306	0	59,167,830	0	36,960	59,394,216
		OUT 6	183,910	1,806,050	1,447,564	145,979,089	806,938	110,880	150,334,430
		OUT 7	16,632	50,753	170,302	90,136,830	403,469	0	90,777,985
		OUT 8	28,496	54,007	0	60,578,248	249,766	0	60,910,517
	OUT 9	65,572	203,736	105,425	54,613,416	999,066	34,320	56,021,534	
AUG 31	LC 1	150,864	2,834,250	510,905	30,753,038	537,958	184,800	34,971,815	
	LC 2	755,160	2,545,379	0	14,147,650	941,427	189,986	18,579,602	

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	LC 3	134,848	389,463	170,302	7,377,580	268,979	43,120	8,384,292
	LC 4	330,876	6,308,324	340,603	58,484,891	3,832,954	294,706	69,592,354
	LC 5	122,052	3,326,518	85,151	24,702,670	2,622,547	147,840	31,006,777
	LC 6	271,779	3,382,624	0	19,227,869	2,958,771	73,920	25,914,963
	LC 7	111,048	1,296,148	0	12,781,406	941,427	36,960	15,166,990
	LC 8	138,544	2,123,106	567,672	14,608,328	941,427	110,555	18,489,632
	LC9	33,236	349,602	28,384	2,407,961	268,979	36,960	3,125,122
	LC 10	358,204	80,640	0	437,388	268,979	6,160	1,151,371
	LC 11	129,696	2,190,479	227,069	20,316,576	134,490	66,786	23,065,095
	LC 12	84,784	2,554,076	624,439	6,598,609	3,099,365	12,320	12,973,593
	OUT 1	152,824	2,090,088	340,603	23,468,094	1,485,490	150,315	27,687,414
	OUT 2	76,272	1,477,952	0	6,275,455	1,479,386	0	9,309,065
	OUT 3	246,568	1,241,918	56,767	12,086,771	1,344,896	61,600	15,038,520
	OUT 5	44,464	778,688	0	2,815,436	5,648,563	73,270	9,360,422
	OUT 6	77,560	2,053,478	85,151	6,510,269	5,853,350	94,343	14,674,150
	OUT 7	76,776	2,286,390	85,151	15,294,989	2,891,526	115,937	20,750,769
	OUT 8	144,032	1,828,406	0	15,309,678	947,531	30,475	18,260,122
	OUT 9	122,192	1,754,799	0	20,275,634	4,040,792	54,466	26,247,883
SEPT 12	LC 1	274,568	143,422	3,065,429	37,666,020	158,906	116,715	41,425,059
	LC 2	50,932	93,926	0	13,113,324	67,245	0	13,325,427
	LC 3	49,000	41,902	28,384	2,746,338	67,245	0	2,932,868
	LC 4	1,262,632	13,255	56,767	4,023,970	0	12,320	5,368,944
	LC 5	69,748	56,759	56,767	6,385,865	67,245	0	6,636,384
	LC 6	1,488,211	30,038	56,767	4,074,622	268,979	12,320	5,930,938
	LC 7	621,264	29,674	340,603	7,785,506	0	12,320	8,789,368
	LC 8	29,400	11,620	56,767	6,017,542	0	0	6,115,329
	LC 9	88,200	4,052	0	349,910	0	0	442,162
	LC 10	108,808	121,526	170,302	10,497,312	1,075,917	0	11,973,864

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	LC 11	110,096	99,148	397,370	8,135,417	403,469	16,425	9,161,925
	LC 12	203,952	105,857	170,302	11,878,541	268,979	0	12,627,630
	OUT 1	4,116	62,182	170,302	4,811,268	0	0	5,047,868
	OUT 2	31,332	90,874	85,151	3,411,626	67,245	0	3,686,228
	OUT 3	9,660	22,994	85,151	1,871,562	0	2,918	1,992,284
	OUT 5	9,016	27,860	85,151	3,017,977	0	2,918	3,142,922
	OUT 6	37,996	73,167	113,534	8,250,673	0	0	8,475,370
	OUT 7	4,900	77,179	170,302	18,676,165	67,245	2,918	18,998,708
	OUT 9	0	402,584	170,302	37,464,168	134,490	0	38,171,543
SEPT 27	LC 1	165,144	158,990	340,603	568,126	0	0	1,232,862
	LC 2	319,704	145,751	681,206	104,849	0	0	1,251,510
	LC 3	364,280	260,831	624,439	345,862	0	4,105	1,599,517
	LC 4	53,900	151,175	85,151	89,090	0	0	379,316
	LC 5	89,684	161,414	624,439	0	0	2,052	877,590
	LC 6	14,560	198,293	56,767	7,182	0	0	276,802
	LC 7	110,068	52,363	368,987	45,352	67,245	6,160	650,174
	LC 8	143,864	197,369	368,987	129,192	0	0	839,412
	LC 9	83,496	210,476	454,138	87,478	0	0	835,587
	LC 10	123,984	136,293	1,021,810	0	0	0	1,282,086
	LC 11	142,464	799,467	737,974	3,226	134,490	0	1,817,620
	LC 12	286,272	233,296	510,905	99,338	134,490	0	1,264,301
	OUT 1	32,928	461,401	283,836	0	0	0	778,165
	OUT 2	52,248	370,076	56,767	6,451	0	0	485,542
	OUT 3	22,932	102,393	689	0	0	0	126,014
	OUT 5	62,328	396,323	1,248,878	289,800	0	0	1,997,330
	OUT 6	24,696	277,556	312,220	659,308	0	0	1,273,779
OUT 7	42,728	120,719	170,302	1,795,836	0	0	2,129,585	
OUT 8	21,364	574,624	141,918	611,654	0	0	1,349,561	

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	OUT 9	8,232	380,108	170,302	345,542	0	0	904,184
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MESOCOSM EFFECTS ON PHYTOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES AND INDIVIDUAL PHYTOPLANKTON TAXA

In the previous section we showed that by reducing turbulence, the mesocosms physically affected phytoplankton division relative abundances and biovolumes. In this section we show how mesocosms physically affected phytoplankton assemblages and individual phytoplankton taxa.

Cluster analysis showed that phytoplankton assemblages differed in several of the treatments (Figure 16). Specifically,

- mesocosm 10 on August 17 and August 31 (two adult carp added August 4),
- mesocosm 1 on August 31 and September 27 (2000 carp eggs added August 8),
- mesocosms 7 and 8 on June 16 (controls) and
- mesocosm 3 on August 17 (no treatment prior to August 24)

were much different than the other treatments during the same sampling events (Figure 16). Reasons for these differences are undetermined, whether actual treatment effects, condition of mesocosms, or because there was only one sample collected from a mesocosm. There did not appear to be any other treatment effects on phytoplankton assemblages, likely because of chronic disrepair of mesocosms allowing relatively rapid flushing, thus preventing defensible effects. However, in a following section we present measurable results of individual mesocosm treatments on phytoplankton division biovolumes.

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Figure 16 Potential effects of treatments on phytoplankton assemblages using cluster analysis and dendrograms. Coded by month. Distance measure = relative Sorenson, group linkage = nearest neighbor, clustering of codes relativized by maximum.

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We then used cluster analysis to examine if treatments specifically affected cyanophyte assemblages. There were substantial differences in cyanophyte assemblages between most mesocosms on the September 27 sample event and mesocosm 3 on the August 17 sample event (Figure 17).

Figure 17 Potential effects of treatments on cyanophyte assemblages using cluster analysis represented by dendrograms. Coded by month. Distance measure = relative Sorenson, group linkage = nearest neighbor, clustering of codes relativized by maximum.

Cluster analysis showed some mesocosm effects therefore, we examined in more detail whether there were mesocosm effects on individual phytoplankton taxa.

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Figure 18 shows many of the phytoplankton taxa biovolumes that could be compared inside and outside of mesocosms. Some taxa seemed unaffected, while others were either more abundant inside mesocosms or outside mesocosms in the lake (Figure 18).

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Figure 18 Effects of mesocosms on individual phytoplankton taxa biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) on our four sampling dates, 2023. Taxa names are in Table 2.

DIURNAL PATTERNS

It is well known that phytoplankton assemblage diurnal patterns exist throughout the world and have been reported in Utah Lake (Richards and Miller personal observations). We cursorily examined diurnal patterns of phytoplankton taxa in this study. Some taxa appeared to have diurnal patterns either occurring at greater biovolumes late morning or early afternoon and varied by sampling event (month) (Figure 19). Wave induced turbidity may have clouded these results. These results support other's observations that diurnal patterns exist in the lake and that sample timing may influence results and confound interpretation.

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Figure 19 Diurnal biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) of individual phytoplankton taxa on the four sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are median, 25th, and 75th centiles. Taxa names are in Table 2.

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TREATMENT EFFECTS

As we have shown in the previous sections, simply by slightly reducing wave induced turbulence, the mesocosms positively improved ecosystem function as shown in the phytoplankton assemblages. We did not anticipate being able to have much success measuring the effects of individual treatments on phytoplankton because lake conditions in 2023 had such a large impact on mesocosm physical condition and because of limited replication. However, we did potentially find effects of most treatments on phytoplankton biomass, as follows.

BIVALVE TREATMENT EFFECTS

MESOCOSM 6, BIVALVES

Between 750 to 1000 *Corbicula fluminea* collected from Utah Lake in the vicinity of our mesocosms were placed into Mesocosm 6 by August 23, 2023. Survival rate of clams in Mesocosm 6 was approximately 70% by the end of the study indicating that about half the clams were able to filter feed and/or pedal feed until we collected our final phytoplankton samples on September 27th.

We had mixed results. However, by September 12 and through September 27, Cyanophyta biovolumes were much lower in the clam Mesocosm 6 than controls (Figure 20).

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Figure 20 Effects of surrogate bivalves in Mesocosm 6 on phytoplankton division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) on three sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are simply the low, middle, and high values from the control and the single value from the bivalve treatment.

After visually evaluating the effects of bivalves on phytoplankton division biovolumes in Figure 20, we conducted parametric one tailed t-tests on log transformed phytoplankton divisions to statistically evaluate the effects of bivalves. These results provided good evidence that the bivalves were able to reduce Cyanophyta biovolume in Mesocosm 6 during the month of September (September 12 and September 27 sample events) (Table 9). Bivalves were also able to directly or indirectly reduce Bacillariophyta and Cryptophyta biovolume, as well as total phytoplankton biovolume in late September (Table 9).

Table 9 One tailed t-tests on effects of bivalves in Mesocosm 9 on log transformed phytoplankton division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) on the August 31 and September 12 sampling events. Pr. ($T > t$) is the probability that biovolumes in control mesocosms ($N = 3$) were greater than biovolumes in clam mesocosm ($N = 1$).

August 31			
Division	t	Pr. ($T > t$)	d. f.
Bacillariophyta	-6.42	0.99	2
Chlorophyta	-2.81	0.95	2
Cryptophyta	NA		
Cyanophyta	-2.38	0.93	2
Dinophyta	-1.88	0.90	2
Total phytoplankton	-5.10	0.98	2

September 12			
Division	t	Pr. ($T > t$)	d. f.
Bacillariophyta	-2.54	0.94	2
Chlorophyta	0.16	0.46	2
Cryptophyta	1.85	0.10	2
Cyanophyta	3.54	0.04	2
Dinophyta	NA		
Total phytoplankton	1.88	0.10	2
Bacillariophyta	-2.54	0.94	2

September 27			
Division	t	Pr. ($T > t$)	d. f.

Bacillariophyta	8.53	0.01	2
Chlorophyta	-0.83	0.75	2
Cryptophyta	18.26	< 0.01	2
Cyanophyta	7.80	< 0.01	2
Dinophyta	NA		
Total phytoplankton	5.99	0.01	2

MESOCOSM 9, BIVALVES

Approximately 1000 *Corbicula fluminea* collected from Utah Lake in the vicinity of our mesocosms were placed into Mesocosm 9 on August 8, 2023, as surrogates for the native bivalve, *Anodonta nutalliana/californiensis* that was extirpated from Utah Lake and native fingernail clams, Sphaeriidae that are precariously close to extinction in the lake and are now what we consider ecologically extinct (Richards et al. 2022).

Survival rate of clams in Mesocosm 9 was approximately 70% by the end of the study indicating that most clams were able to filter feed and/or pedal feed until we collected our final phytoplankton samples on September 27th.

We compared phytoplankton division biomasses between Mesocosm 9 and the three control mesocosms, 7, 8, and 12 using nonparametric boxplots. There was visual evidence that phytoplankton division biomasses, as well as total phytoplankton biomasses, were less than control biomasses for almost all of the divisions particularly in the August 17 and 31 sample events, except for Euglenophyta, which didn't seem to be affected by clams (Figure 21). As occurred in Mesocosm 6, Cyanophyta had less biovolume in Mesocosm 9 with clams after the bloom occurred around the August 17 sample event (Figure 21). We attribute these results primarily filter feeding by clams, although limited replication and non-demonic intrusion (Hurlbert 1984) were always a possibility.

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Figure 21 Effects of surrogate bivalves in Mesocosm 9 on phytoplankton division biovolumes on four sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are simply the low, middle, and high values from the control and the single value from the bivalve treatment.

After visually evaluating the effects of bivalves on phytoplankton division biovolumes in Figure 21, we conducted parametric one tailed t-tests on log transformed phytoplankton divisions to statistically evaluate the effects of bivalves. These results provided strong evidence that for all phytoplankton divisions, biovolumes were less in the bivalve treatments than in controls on the August 31 sample event and Chlorophyta and Cyanophyta biovolumes were lower in bivalve treatments than controls on the September 12 sample event (Table 10). However, limited replication, mesocosm condition, and non-demonic intrusion (Hurlbert 1984 but also see Oksanen 2004) may have influenced results.

Table 10 One tailed t-tests on effects of bivalves in Mesocosm 9 on log transformed phytoplankton division biovolumes on the August 31 and September 12 sampling events. Pr. ($T > t$) is the probability that biovolumes in control mesocosms ($N = 3$) were greater than biovolumes in clam mesocosm ($N = 1$).

August 31				September 12			
Division	t	Pr. ($T > t$)	d. f.	Division	t	Pr. ($T > t$)	d. f.
Bacillariophyta	8.38	0.01	2	Bacillariophyta	0.63	0.30	2
Chlorophyta	8.40	0.01	2	Chlorophyta	3.28	0.04	2
Cryptophyta	63.86	0.01	1	Cryptophyta	NA		
Cyanophyta	6.08	0.01	2	Cyanophyta	15.93	< 0.01	2
Dinophyta	4.15	0.03	2	Dinophyta	NA		
Total phytoplankton	15.56	< 0.01	2	Total phytoplankton	14.28	< 0.01	2

GEOCHEMICAL, RHODAMINE, AND PHOSPHORUS TREATMENT EFFECTS

MESOCOSM 3

Geochemical, rhodamine, and phosphorus treatments were added to Mesocosm 3 in late August 2023. There appeared to be initial negative effects on phytoplankton division biovolumes including Chlorophyta, Cryptophyta, Cyanophyta, and Dinophyta however, Bacillariophyta and Cryptophyta may have benefited over the long term (Figure 22). Overall, the treatments had a negative effect on total phytoplankton biovolume up until September 27, 2023, when phytoplankton appeared to rebound inside treatment mesocom vs. controls (Figure 22). This apparent rebound in total phytoplankton biovolume is typical of chemical treatments, initial decline and then resurgence.

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Figure 22 Potential effects of treatments on phytoplankton division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) in Mesocosm 3 on four sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are simply the low, middle, and high values from the control and the single value from the treatment.

MESOCOSM 4

Geochemical, rhodamine, and phosphorus treatments were initiated in Mesocosm 4 in mid-August. The treatments appeared to have had initial positive effects on Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, Cyanophyta, Dinophyta, and Euglenophyta biovolumes, as well as total phytoplankton biovolume (Figure 23). Cyanophytes biovolume however appeared to have a lag response to treatments and decreased by September 12. Treatments could have had negative effects on Cryptophytes lasting until late September (Figure 23).

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Figure 23 Potential effects of treatments on phytoplankton division biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) in Mesocosm 4 on four sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are simply the low, middle, and high values from the control and the single value from the treatment.

MESOCOSM 10

Rhodamine and phosphorus were added to Mesocosm 10 from August 29 to September 4, 2023. There appeared to be positive effects on the phytoplankton divisions Cryptophytes, Chlorophytes, and Dinophytes and possibly total phytoplankton biovolume (Figure 24).

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Figure 24 Potential effects of treatments on phytoplankton division biovolumes in Mesocosm 10 on four sampling dates, 2023. Box plots are simply the low, middle, and high values from the control and the single value from the treatment. RandP = rhodamine and phosphorus.

CARP TREATMENTS

The abnormally high-water year combined with strong wind and wave action caused undue stress on mesocosms that allowed juvenile and adult carp to escape the mesocosm treatments before they had a measurable effect on phytoplankton samples. Therefore, no results are presented other than in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

As with all temperate lakes, Utah Lake's phytoplankton assemblage transitioned seasonally in a generally predictable manner. This natural transition was somewhat delayed by an abnormally high-water year that diluted nutrients in spring and kept water temperatures lower than in previous low water years that have consistently occurred during the last decade or so. As a result, Bacillariophyta and Chlorophyta taxa dominated the assemblage into late spring/early summer as shown from analysis of our June17 sample event. By August, Cyanophyta taxa, particularly *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* and *Chroococcus disperses* and *Aphanothece* sp. comprised well over 80% phytoplankton biovolume. Cyanophyta taxa *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOC1) and *Lynbya* sp. replaced *A. flosaquae* as the dominant blue-green algae in the study area by mid-September. By September 27, the phytoplankton assemblage transitioned to an assemblage that more closely resembled the June assemblage with greater relative abundances of Bacillariophyta and Chlorophyta taxa and even Cryptophyta, although relative proportions of different taxa within each division contributed to this more generalized division-based assemblage interpretation. Dinophyta, predominately *Ceratium hirudinella*, were important members of the phytoplankton assemblage as measured by biovolume in late August but did not persist into September except for outside of the mesocosms in the lake. Large relative proportions of Cyanophyta and Dinophyta in summer have important effects on the lake's ecosystem function, particularly zooplankton grazers as they are more difficult to digest. These interactions will be discussed in the zooplankton chapter.

The effects of mesocosms on the phytoplankton assemblage clearly implicates wave induced turbidity and sediment resuspension as a leading impairment to Utah Lake's health. The effects of turbidity and sediment resuspension on the effective number of taxa (ENT), evenness, and diversity

should be an alarm call for all Utah Lake management agencies, as these metrics are widely used to monitor water quality and are well known indicators of biodiversity, i.e., health and integrity, that are already impaired in Utah Lake. A more diverse, balanced, and phytoplankton rich assemblage in Utah Lake will dampen the intensity and occurrences of harmful algal blooms. Any improvement of ENT, evenness, and diversity of the phytoplankton assemblage by even slight reductions in turbidity and sediment resuspension should initiate management planning to alleviate this problem.

Utah Lake suffers from high turbidity due to several factors including,

- its shallow nature,
- strong winds and waves,
- easily suspended dissolved and fine sediments,
- bioturbator fishes (primarily carp but also other non-indigenous species),
- transition from benthic and macrophyte primary producers that stabilized sediments to phytoplankton dominated primary production,
- loss of mollusks that also stabilized sediments, and
- regulation as a reservoir that resulted in unnatural lake level fluctuations, etc. (Richards reports)

Even though these factors contribute to turbidity in Utah Lake; turbidity is now primarily caused by wind and wave driven sediment resuspension that directly affects light penetration and nutrient levels in the water column. Bioturbators (e.g., carp, catfish) also contribute to sediment resuspension but likely to a lesser extent. Light and nutrient levels can have many anticipated and unanticipated indirect effects on Utah Lake’s foodweb including the transfer of nutrients and energy from the base of the foodweb (primary producers), to grazer consumers (zooplankton), to higher level trophic organisms including fishes and birds.

Figure 25 Response of primary, secondary, and tertiary production to turbulence (e.g., sediment resuspension, turbidity). From Jin et al. (2021).

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In large shallow lake ecosystems such as Utah Lake, phytoplankton primary productivity generally increases with nutrient availability but then becomes light limited by wave induced turbidity (Quinlan et al. 2021, Edwards et al. 2016, Scheffer 1998, Scheffer et al. 2001, Richards 2022b). Resuspension enhances release of sediment bound particles into the water column making them available to phytoplankton (Tammeorg et al. 2013, Tang et al. 2020, Zhang et al. 2020). However, large amounts of suspended solids entering the water column from resuspension interferes with nutrient and light availability for phytoplankton production (Schallenberg and Burns 2004).

Wind and wave turbulence resuspends sediments on a regular basis in Utah Lake (Figure 26). These effects prevent the lake from functioning properly as discussed throughout this progress report and past reports.

Figure 26 Wind and wave turbulence increases suspended sediment that directly affects ecosystem function of Utah Lake. Satellite image June 21, 2023, and September 25, 2023, from Landsat Explorer (<https://livingatlas2.arcgis.com/landsatexplorer/>). In these images, suspended solids from high runoff in tributaries was circulated throughout most of the Utah Lake.

BIVALVES

This year's mesocosm study clearly demonstrated the importance of bivalves on ecosystem function, as confirmed in phytoplankton biovolume reductions in Mesocosms 6 and 9. Even though there was unanticipated flow through the mesocosms due to lake induced disrepair that diluted estimates of bivalve filtering effects, bivalves altered the mesocosm's food web and ecosystem. The importance of bivalve filtering and ecosystem function has been well documented and is cursorily discussed next.

Mollusk diversity and abundances peak in the Utah Lake-Jordan River drainage and the surrounding areas in the depauperate western USA (Richards 2017, Richards 2014). Utah Lake's historic mollusk diversity and abundances were due to its Lake Bonneville heritage of abundant nutrients, relatively high pH and high CaCO_3 levels originating from the > 1-mile-thick limestone base rock within the watershed (Richards and Miller 2019).

Native mollusks were the dominant benthic ecosystem engineers in Utah Lake when early explorers and Americans of European descent first arrived in the 1800's. Native mollusks were also responsible for much of the water column functioning (Richards 2014, 2017, 2018b, and 2019a) and until recently likely governed almost all its ecosystem functions. Unfortunately, their role as keystone species and ecosystem engineers has been eliminated.

In the following paragraphs we review and discuss the ecological role of the surrogate taxon, *Corbicula* sp. that has been studied extensively. We posit that its ecosystem effects and role are similar to Utah Lake's native mussel *Anodonta* sp. and Sphaeriidae fingernail clams that likely

occurred by the tens of millions in the lake but have for the most part been completely extirpated from the entire watershed (Richards 2017).

The survival rate of *Corbicula fluminea* in our mesocosms was approximately 70%, which is typical for this taxon. Sousa et al. (2008) and McMahon (2002) (in Richards (2018)) reported that *C. fluminea* juvenile and adult survivorship is usually low. Survival rates of native bivalves in Utah Lake are unknown but are likely equal to or greater than *Corbicula* (Sousa et al. (2008)).

FEEDING AND FILTRATION

Corbicula can directly reduce the amount of particulate organic matter (POM) available to be remineralized by pelagic consumers and bacterioplankton (Newell et al. 2005). *Corbicula* also actively select particles to digest or reject as pseudofeces as illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27. A conceptual model of food processing by *Corbicula* actively filter feeding and particle selecting for rejection as pseudofeces or digestion (from Dame and Olenin (2005)).

Table 11. *Corbicula* filtration rates (from Lauritsen (1986) Table 1).

	Algal Volume (mm ³ /L)				
	0.33	0.67	1.33	2.00	2.67
Mean filtration rate (ml/hr)	782.3	656.5	489.0	420.2 ^a	277.8
1 SE	69.6	55.5	53.6		82.5
Mean volume ingested (mm ³)	0.23	0.41	0.64		0.80
1 SE	0.01	0.03	0.06		0.07

Corbicula typically have a lower ingestion size limit of < 1 μm and upper size limit of about 20 μm for filtered POM (McMahon and Bogan 2001; Way et al. 1990) but can consume algae with a spherical diameter from 50 μm up to 170 μm (Boltovskoy et al. 1995). However, larger sized POM or

higher concentrations of POM favor the production of pseudofeces and/or reduced filtration rates (Beaver et al. 1991; Lauritsen 1986; Way et al. 1990). Because of this particle ingestion size range, they can effectively remove a large majority of or even completely deplete detritus, bacteria and algae from the water column when they occur at high densities/biomass (McMahon 1999, Boltovskoy et al. 1995; Dame and Olenin 2005). Consequently, *Corbicula* play a key role in the stability of aquatic ecosystems (Herman and Scholten 1990; Kotta et al 2005; Dame et al. 1989, 1991). *Corbicula* has been shown to initiate pseudofeces production at 17 to 20 mg l⁻¹ TSS (Fuji 1979, Hornbach et al. 1984, Way et al. 1990, Richards 2018).

Corbicula is considered to be mostly a non-selective, filter-feeder (Lauritsen 1986; Way et al. 1990; Beaver et al. 1991). Several feeding studies have suggested that *Corbicula* grow equally well on green algae and diatoms and assimilation and net production efficiencies of *Corbicula* fed the cyanobacteria, *Anabaena oscillaroides* were not significantly different than those fed chlorophytes (Lauritsen 1986; Beaver et al. 1991). The Lauritsen (1986) study found that the lowest filtration rates and the highest assimilation efficiencies were with another cyanobacteria, *Anabaena flos-aquae*, the most abundant phytoplankton taxa found in our 2023 mesocosm study. *Corbicula* are even thought to have reduced the severity of cyanoHABs in the Potomac River (Phelps 1994). High densities of *Corbicula* in eutrophic systems are completely capable of reducing water column phosphorus (TP) levels (Beaver et al. 1991).

Filter feeding *Corbicula* also reduce turbidity, increase water clarity, and thereby increase nutrient mineralization rates and light availability to microphytobenthos and aquatic vegetation (Buttner 1986; Lauritsen and Mozley 1989; Phelps 1994; Newell et al. 2005; Buttner 1986; Lauritsen and Mozley 1989; Phelps 1994; Beaver et al. 1991; Newell 2004; Newell & Koch 2004). Phelps (1994) suggested that it was *Corbicula* filter feeding at high clearance rates that reduced turbidity and increased light availability to bottom sections of the Potomac River and allowed aquatic vegetation to reestablish.

Most researchers focus on nutrient regeneration of bivalve filter-feeding, however one of the more important effects of bivalve feeding is the repackaging of small seston particles into large aggregates of feces and pseudofeces, known as biodeposition (Newell et al. 2005; more). Particles in bivalve feces are tightly bound in a mucoid matrix and voided as pelleted strings that can be as long as several millimeters (Beninger et al. 1999; Kautsky and Evans 1987, Widdows et al. 1998; Newell et al. 2005). Feces and pseudofeces sinking velocities can be up to 40 times faster than that of non-aggregated particles, although pseudofeces are less tightly bound in mucus than feces and may disaggregate when voided (Kautsky and Evans 1987, Widdows et al. 1998; Newell et al. 2005).

Although some algae are undigested and passed as feces or pseudofeces (Hill and Knight 1981; Galtsoff 1964, Cohen et al. 1984), overall, “*Corbicula* biodeposition enhances net ecosystem losses of N and P via sediment burial and bacterially mediated, coupled nitrification-denitrification” (Newell et al. 2005). Microphytobenthos may then compete with nitrifying bacteria for N, potentially reducing coupled nitrification-denitrification, they retain N and P within sediments, further reducing net regeneration to the water column. (Newell et al. 2005).

Cohen et al. (1984) showed that *Corbicula* removed vast quantities of phytoplankton from Potomac River water. They also demonstrated that phaeopigment concentration in the sediment was proportional to clam biomass, thus verifying that *Corbicula* deposit some partially digested

phytoplankton on the bottom as feces or pseudofeces. Cohen et al. (1984) also reported that Prokopovich (1969) found that the mucoid-like mass of pseudofeces was a strong binding agent of sediment and that it would probably require a bottom-scouring storm to resuspend the excreted, partially decomposed algae.

For a more detailed discussion of life history and ecosystem effects of *Corbicula* sp. see Richards (2018) and our previous report from the 2022 mesocosm experiments (Richards et al. 2023) on the importance of native bivalve restoration in Utah Lake.

MAJOR IMPACT ON CYANOBACTERIA

In a properly functioning eutrophic lake ecosystem, cyanobacteria sink to the bottom at night in search of food (i.e., nutrients) at their own peril. Filter feeding bivalve predators await, either turning cyanobacteria cells into animal tissue, excretory waste, or expulsion into sediments as pseudofeces.

Cyanophyta biovolume decreased more often in our mesocosm bivalve treatments than any of the other phytoplankton divisions. Bivalves either selectively fed on Cyanophyta or simply consumed the most abundant phytoplankton that was nearest their siphons. Bivalves also likely expelled larger less edible Cyanophyta as pseudofeces although as we have discussed can easily assimilate some Cyanophyta taxa including *Aphanizomenon* sp. This capacity to reduce Cyanophyta has important implications for Utah Lake restoration and reduction of potentially toxic algal blooms.

The spike in phytoplankton in mid to late August throughout Utah Lake and within the mesocosms was greater inside the bivalve treatment mesocosms than controls. This was likely due to bivalve filter feeding phytoplankton resulting in decreased turbidity, reduced light limitation, and phytoplankton growth. Bivalve filter feeding relatively quickly reduced phytoplankton biovolume, particularly Cyanophyta biovolume. In a well-balanced, functioning ecosystem, any spike in phytoplankton biovolume would quickly be reduced directly or indirectly by other members of the foodweb (i.e., zooplankton, benthic algae, macrophytes, etc.) (Richards et al. 2023), more so than bivalves acting alone.

TROPHIC TRANSFER EFFICIENCY, STATE, STRUCTURE, AND FUNCTION OF UTAH LAKE'S ECOSYSTEM

Trophic transfer of energy and matter from primary producers to higher trophic levels is a fundamental aspect of food web functioning (Jin et al. 2021, Richards 2022a). A reduction in trophic transfer due to wind induced turbulence can potentially lead to declines of higher trophic levels in aquatic food webs including fish and waterbirds, but is generally understudied (Jin et al. 2021, Richards 2022a). A draft Utah Lake foodweb model created by Richards (2022b) suggested that trophic transfer efficiency in the lake was out of balance with Lindeman's (1942) 10% 'rule'. Richards (2022b) also found that zooplankton grazers in the lake did not appear to be able to utilize a large portion of the phytoplankton biomass mostly during summer months (i.e., low ecotrophic efficiency) and that much of the phytoplankton biomass was unconsumed and fell as detrital 'rain'. These findings suggest that the effects of sediment resuspension, turbulence, and turbidity on light

and nutrient levels in Utah Lake likely play a significant role in retaining Utah Lake in an unbalanced poorly functioning state, but the lake is redeemable.

As we reported in our 2022 mesocosm study report (Richards et al. 2023), understanding the state, structure, and function of Utah Lake's ecosystem is of paramount importance if we are to manage and restore it based on a scientific ecological perspective. Results from this year's experiments show that bivalves are a critical component in this understanding and restoration.

Richards (2022) draft foodweb/ecosystem function model provided several metrics commonly used to measure ecosystem health, integrity, maturity, robustness, resistance, resilience, state, structure, and function. These informative quantitative metrics are used by ecosystem ecologists more so than the latent buzz words used primarily by managers such as health and integrity.

BIVALVES

Results from this mesocosm study indirectly demonstrate the improvement of trophic transfer efficiency (TTE) due to bivalve filter feeding. TTE is how efficiently energy is transferred up to higher trophic levels (i.e., the foodweb), is widely used in aquatic foodweb models, and is a direct measure of an ecosystem's health. Richards (2022) preliminary foodweb/ecosystem function model showed that Utah Lake has major trophic level transfer problems. We submit that reintroduction of viable populations of native bivalves will improve TTE as demonstrated in these mesocosm experiments. Results from these mesocosm experiments can be incorporated into ecosystem function models such as those being developed by Richards and colleagues.

GEOCHEMICAL AND NUTRIENT ADDITION

Nutrient additions had mixed effects on phytoplankton assemblages as a result of different geochemical and nutrient treatments. Results were somewhat similar to our 2022 Mesocosm #7 nutrient addition (Richards et al. 2023) but will need further analysis.

CONCLUSION

Results from our 2023 mesocosm study concurred with our past research demonstrating the effects of mesocosms on phytoplankton assemblages, the initial biotic responders to experimental treatments and the base of Utah Lake's foodweb. These results clearly validated our conclusion that sediment resuspension from wind induced wave turbulence is now the ultimate factor limiting restoration of Utah Lake, although other factors are involved (e.g., invasive fish bioturbation, loss of macrophytes and benthic algae, etc.). We also demonstrated that the importance of reestablishing native bivalves to Utah Lake's ecosystem cannot be overstated. Findings from this study, supported by our past mesocosm experiments, other ecological research that we have conducted on Utah Lake over the last decade, and as supported throughout the scientific literature will help direct the course on holistic restoration of Utah Lake.

APPENDICES

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Appendix 1 Descriptive statistics of sample event phytoplankton taxa biovolumes inside and outside of mesocosms

Inside mesocosms

	ANFA	ACGR	ANJU	ANASP	ANSP	APFL	APIN	APHS P	ASFO	APSP	ASFO	AUGR	CEHI	CENTDIA T	CHDI	CHLSP	CHMI	CHRS P
17-Aug																		
Mean	131	0	6,508	0	0	7781210 0	0	0	0	58,482	0	72,31 1	565,904	10,301	440	3,168,38 1	1,546	1,378
Media n	0	0	2,964	0	0	7445787 2	0	0	0	28,728	0	77,61 6	374,650	8,232	0	3,066,71 4	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	2375793 8	0	0	0	14,364	0	55,44 0	0	0	0	1,427,16 6	0	0
75th	160	0	19,15 2	0	0	1.40E+08	0	0	0	86,184	0	94,61 8	941,427	15,288	0	4,644,36 0	0	0
31-Aug																		
Mean	293	526	0	329	15,196	1,163,40 4	0	0	0	24,539	0	34,93 6	1,400,93 3	35,672	134	2,187,51 8	0	0
Media n	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24,94 8	941,427	26,754	0	2,168,96 4	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11,08 8	268,979	10,290	0	744,534	0	0
75th	479	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32,319	0	44,35 2	2,790,65 9	57,624	0	2,943,42 3	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	0	0	6,185	0	0	76,540	6,860	0	0	0	0	3,226	0	29,698	403	7,781	647	5,080
Media n	0	0	5,586	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26,754	0	8,379	0	4,822
25th	0	0	3,192	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20,580	0	1,197	0	0
75th	0	0	7,980	0	0	122,464	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	39,102	0	13,167	370	8,266
12- Sep																		
Mean	372	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18,99 0	196,131	7,203	0	23,940	0	0
Media n	160	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16,63 2	67,245	6,174	0	8,379	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4,788	0	0
75th	479	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33,26 4	268,979	8,232	0	26,334	0	0

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27-Sep																		
Mean	466	0	0	0	0	40,821	0	1,092	0	8,379	0	8,778	28,019	33,614	2,419	31,322	0	0
Median	239	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11,088	0	24,696	806	21,546	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,772	0	18,522	0	10,773	0	0
75th	559	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7,182	0	11,088	33,622	45,276	4,838	33,516	0	0
Total																		
Mean	273	115	2,201	72	3,315	15836293	998	238	0	18,878	0	28,612	467,744	23,068	704	1,124,142	403	1,014
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11,088	67,245	16,464	0	28,728	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4,116	0	9,576	0	0
75th	319	0	1,596	0	0	367,391	0	0	0	14,364	0	39,379	537,958	32,928	0	2,092,356	0	0
	CHROSP	CHSP	CHTU	CLAC	CLLO	COSP	CRFE	CRQU	CRR E	CRSP	CRUS P	CYSP	DEBI	DECO	DIEH	DEIN	DEO P	DESP
17-Aug																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	23,883	0	0	0	0	1,043,189	1,063	0	630	153	0	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	263,562	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28,384	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	37,531	0	0	0	0	1,816,550	1,949	0	655	0	0	0	0	0
31-Aug																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	25,021	0	11,760	866	467	212,877	0	6,061	437	560	508	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	127,726	0	448	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	18,766	0	25,200	0	0	425,754	0	7,273	0	0	0	0	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	0	3,100	2,474	0	4,691	0	0	21,437	0	0	0	0	0	630	0	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18,189	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11,693	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	344	0	0	0	0	0	23,386	0	0	0	0	0	1,680	0	0	0	0
12-Sep																		
Mean	0	0	0	332	25,021	0	3,360	0	0	366,621	0	0	437	140	0	0	280	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	56,767	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42,575	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	56,297	0	0	0	0	255,452	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27-Sep																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	78,190	6,533	5,880	0	0	489,617	0	0	273	0	0	90	140	0
Median	0	0	0	0	75,062	0	0	0	0	482,521	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	37,531	0	0	0	0	354,795	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	112,594	0	15,120	0	0	652,823	0	0	328	0	0	0	0	0
Total																		
Mean	0	451	360	72	33,437	1,425	4,582	3,307	102	441,899	213	1,322	376	275	111	20	92	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	170,302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	75,062	0	0	0	0	454,138	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	DOCI	DOSP	ERGI	EUSP	GRLA	GYS P	KILU	KOSP	LEAC	LESP	LYSP	MESP	MEVA	OOBO	OOSP	OSPR	OSSP	PEAN
17-Aug																		
Mean	3,195,672	152,345	0	234,160	0	0	0	16,554	0	0	0	586	0	10,521	2,932	487,137	9,190	0
Median	1,624,584	0	0	197,120	0	0	0	8,288	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	437,388	0	0	12,320	0	0	0	1,658	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	4,067,709	0	0	295,680	0	0	0	29,837	0	0	0	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
31-Aug																		
Mean	9,214,307	39,900	14,075	95,480	0	509	42	2,625	0	0	0	314	0	19,170	0	0	0	935

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

Media n	9,250,757	0	0	61,600	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15,002	0	0	0	0
25th	3,914,623	0	0	36,960	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	11940693	39,900	0	160,160	0	0	0	829	0	0	0	269	0	30,005	0	0	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	0	3,325	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37,506	6,048	0	0	0
Media n	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40,006	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0
75th	0	6,650	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60,010	0	0	0	0
12-Sep																		
Mean	9,185,148	0	0	13,347	0	2,035	0	2,486	0	0	11,200	0	0	3,334	0	0	0	0
Media n	7,085,686	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	3,805,276	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	11065917	0	0	12,320	0	0	0	829	0	0	0	0	0	5,001	0	0	0	0
27-Sep																		
Mean	40,094	0	0	513	0	0	0	1,243	0	0	0	0	1,801	11,669	0	0	0	0
Media n	21,869	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	87,478	0	0	0	0	0	0	3,315	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0
Total																		
Mean	4,662,309	39,658	3,071	70,688	20	555	9.2	4,697	0	0	2,444	186	393	15,015	1,466	97,427	1,838	204
Media n	1,137,209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	8,135,417	0	0	73,920	0	0	0	3,315	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0

	PEDU	PENNDIAT	PEPE	PESP	PHASP	PHSP	PTSP	SCEL	SCSE	SCSP	SPSC	TRSP	UNFICYAN
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17-Aug													
Mean	0	177,864	0	3,589	0	1,023	0	11,766	3,902	5,268	4,268	187	0
Median	0	88,200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	45,500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	176,400	0	0	0	0	0	14,381	10,220	13,373	0	0	0
31-Aug													
Mean	4,527	147,817	700	0	4,863	7,189,481	2,547	5,992	3,151	0	0	0	0
Median	0	105,350	0	0	0	4,148,340	1,554	0	1,022	0	0	0	0
25th	0	53,900	0	0	0	1,830,150	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	129,850	0	0	11,670	7,808,640	4,144	0	4,088	0	0	0	0
16-Jun													
Mean	3,395	60,025	0	1,645	0	0	130	0	0	0	111,507	0	0
Median	0	56,350	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	53,900	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	71,050	0	0	0	0	259	0	0	0	70,426	0	0
12-Sep													
Mean	0	336,875	0	0	486	193,183	0	0	2,896	0	0	342	0
Median	0	83,300	0	0	0	61,005	0	0	2,044	0	0	0	0
25th	0	49,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	387,100	0	0	0	366,030	0	0	4,088	0	0	0	0
27-Sep													
Mean	4,527	113,925	0	0	0	30,503	86	1,198	8,346	0	75,514	513	0
Median	0	83,300	0	0	0	0	0	0	7,154	0	70,426	0	0
25th	0	56,350	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,533	0	0	0	0
75th	0	151,900	0	0	0	0	0	0	14,308	0	93,901	0	0
Total													
Mean	2,469	174,911	153	957	1,167	1,617,623	593	3,922	3,921	1,054	33,549	224	0
Median	0	88,200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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25th	0	53,900	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	147,000	0	0	0	488,040	0	0	6,132	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Outside mesocosms

	ANFA	ACGR	ANJU	ANASP	ANSP	APFL	APIN	APHSP	ASFO	APSP	ASFO	AUGR	CEHI	GENTDIAT	CHDI	CHLSP	CHMI	CHRSP
17-Aug																		
Mean	124	0	10,133	0	0	91026560	0	0	0	43,776	0	24,390	410,217	8,101	2,509	425,980	657	1,684
Median	0	0	3,192	0	0	90010744	0	0	0	28,728	0	22,176	249,766	8,232	0	344,736	0	0
25th	0	0	3,192	0	0	60497020	0	0	0	14,364	0	11,088	134,490	0	0	106,704	0	0
75th	319	0	19,152	0	0	1.10E+08	0	0	0	43,092	0	33,264	806,938	8,232	6,451	416,556	0	2,755
31-Aug																		
Mean	60	0	0	0	5,065	0	0	0	0	3,591	0	42,273	2,958,771	35,501	0	1,582,135	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33,264	2,185,456	26,754	0	1,577,646	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27,720	1,412,141	20,580	0	1,287,972	0	0
75th	80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60,984	4,841,626	45,276	0	1,951,110	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	0	0	7,382	0	0	45,924	11,270	0	1,609	0	1,609	1,075	0	44,247	3,226	11,372	1,309	1,531,045
Median	0	0	4,788	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41,160	0	1,197	62	23,764
25th	0	0	3,192	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26,754	0	0	0	7,232
75th	0	0	9,576	0	0	122,464	3,920	0	0	0	0	0	0	59,682	6,451	19,152	2,218	40,639
12-Sep																		
Mean	46	0	0	0	0	69,979	0	0	0	34,884	0	5,544	38,426	4,116	0	19,152	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4,116	0	16,758	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11,970	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	0	122,464	0	0	0	100,548	0	16,632	67,245	4,116	0	33,516	0	0
27-Sep																		
Mean	2,035	0	0	0	0	15,308	0	1,365	0	1,796	0	1,386	0	24,696	4,838	19,751	0	86
Median	1,676	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28,812	5,645	1,197	0	0
25th	319	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,348	1,613	0	0	0

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75th	3,591	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,184	0	0	0	0	0	32,928	7,258	13,167	0	0
Total																		
Mean	455	0	3,756	0	1,013	20505469	2,254	273	322	17,032	322	15,405	690,778	23,432	2,177	421,848	410	306,605
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7,073	0	16,464	0	33,516	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6,174	0	3,591	0	0
75th	319	0	3,192	0	0	183,695	0	0	0	14,364	0	27,720	806,938	32,928	4,032	497,952	0	1,722
	CHROSP	CHSP	CHTU	CLAC	CLLO	COSP	CRFE	CRQU	CRRE	CRSP	CRUSP	CYSP	DEBI	DECO	DIEH	DEIN	DEOP	DESP
17-Aug																		
Mean	35,865	0	0	0	32,765	0	0	0	0	191,477	2,753	0	996	0	0	0	373	1,680
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3,619	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	69,701	0	0	0	0	105,425	3,898	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31-Aug																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	37,531	0	18,900	0	0	70,959	0	784	1,802	210	0	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	15,120	0	0	28,384	0	0	655	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	75,062	0	40,320	0	0	85,151	0	896	3,931	0	0	0	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	4,691	0	0	17,864	0	0	0	0	0	420	0	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,992	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2,598	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27,283	0	0	0	0	0	840	0	0	0	0
12-Sep																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	69,701	0	7,200	0	0	125,699	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	37,531	0	0	0	0	113,534	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	85,151	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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75th	0	0	0	0	75,062	0	10,080	0	0	170,302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27-Sep																		
Mean	0	0	0	0	65,680	0	7,560	0	0	298,028	0	0	573	0	0	269	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	56,297	0	0	0	0	170,302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	37,531	0	0	0	0	99,343	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	75,062	0	10,080	0	0	298,028	0	0	983	0	0	0	0	0
Total																		
Mean	8,070	0	0	0	41,150	0	6,552	3,573	0	138,877	619	157	699	126	0	54	84	378
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	56,767	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	0	0	0	0	72,382	0	0	0	0	170,302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	DOCI	DOSP	ERGI	EUSP	GRLA	GYPSP	KILU	KOSP	LEAC	LESP	LYSP	MESP	MEVA	OBOB	OOSP	OSPR	OSSP	PEAN
17-Aug																		
Mean	2,362,892	4,433	0	31,191	0	0	0	737	0	0	0	119	0	4,445	0	0	0	0
Median	1,729,000	0	0	34,320	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	1,276,800	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	2,340,800	0	0	36,960	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31-Aug																		
Mean	3,624,853	0	6,334	54,670	0	2,671	63	0	2,375	4,200	0	0	0	3,751	0	0	0	0
Median	787,298	0	0	61,600	0	1,526	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25th	87,478	0	0	30,800	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	8,091,678	0	8,445	70,840	0	6,104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5,001	0	0	0	0
16-Jun																		
Mean	16,402	3,325	2,111	770	560	0	0	622	0	0	0	0	0	38,756	6,048	0	0	0
Median	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40,006	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0

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75th	21,869	6,650	0	0	1,120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50,008	0	0	0	0
12-Sep																		
Mean	10790987	0	0	0	0	0	0	237	0	0	19,200	0	0	8,573	0	0	0	0
Median	4,811,268	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
25th	3,017,977	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	18457774	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67,200	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
27-Sep																		
Mean	333,508	0	2,111	0	0	0	0	414	0	0	0	0	0	23,754	0	0	0	0
Median	240,563	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0
25th	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	568,604	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35,006	0	0	0	0
Total																		
Mean	3,215,026	1,663	2,111	18,106	112	534	13	414	475	840	3,360	27	0	15,753	1,210	0	0	0
Median	568,604	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10,002	0	0	0	0
25th	21,869	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75th	3,214,802	0	0	35,640	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20,003	0	0	0	0
	PEDU	PENNDIAT	PEPE	PESP	PHASP	PHSP	PTSP	SCEL	SCSE	SCSP	SPSC	TRSP	UNFICYAN					
17-Aug																		
Mean	0	23,178	622	0	0	8,137	288	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Median	0	9,800	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
25th	0	9,100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
75th	0	18,200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
31-Aug																		
Mean	0	39,813	0	0	11,306	9,120,248	3,043	7,190	4,471	0	23,475	0	0					
Median	0	34,300	0	0	8,753	8,845,725	2,849	0	1,533	0	0	0	0					
25th	0	19,600	0	0	2,918	5,490,450	2,072	0	0	0	0	0	0					
75th	0	58,800	0	0	18,964	13177080	3,626	14,381	9,198	0	46,950	0	0					

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31-Aug							
Mean	218,424	2,281,717	0	212,877	17653664	1,401,442	100,343
Median	136,696	2,367,929	0	127,726	14377989	941,427	70,353
25th	116,550	842,806	0	0	6,988,095	268,979	36,960
75th	301,328	3,080,384	0	425,754	22509623	2,790,659	166,320
16-Jun							
Mean	92,948	199,449	0	9,348	90,249	1,645	0
Median	90,454	97,203	0	6,199	16,915	0	0
25th	74,480	80,109	0	4,133	8,868	0	0
75th	111,034	174,432	0	14,465	149,904	0	0
12-Sep							
Mean	363,068	62,598	0	366,621	9,389,531	198,165	14,175
Median	109,452	49,330	0	56,767	7,085,686	67,245	0
25th	60,340	21,465	0	42,575	4,049,296	0	0
75th	447,916	102,502	0	255,452	11187927	268,979	12,320
27-Sep							
Mean	158,118	225,477	0	489,617	123,308	28,019	1,026
Median	133,224	179,392	0	482,521	88,284	0	0
25th	86,590	148,463	0	354,795	5,204	0	0
75th	225,708	221,886	0	652,823	117,020	33,622	1,026
Total							
Mean	226,984	1,240,885	0	451,575	22283863	469,256	72,284
Median	134,848	198,293	0	170,302	6,017,542	67,245	5,835
25th	88,200	93,926	0	15,154	99,338	0	0
75th	271,779	2,190,479	0	454,138	20316576	537,958	74,058

Outside corrals

	Bacillariophyta	Chlorophyta	Chrysophyta	Cryptophyta	Cyanophyta	Dinophyta	Euglenophyta
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17-Aug							
Mean	55,670	480,897	17,422	193,160	93484300	392,795	31,839
Median	30,408	420,067	0	5,510	90136832	249,766	34,320
25th	28,496	160,306	0	0	60578248	134,490	0
75th	65,572	509,292	0	105,425	1.10E+08	806,938	36,960
31-Aug							
Mean	117,586	1,688,965	0	70,959	12754541	2,961,442	72,551
Median	99,876	1,791,602	0	28,384	13690880	2,188,508	67,435
25th	76,524	1,359,935	0	0	6,392,862	1,412,141	42,470
75th	148,428	2,071,783	0	85,151	17792656	4,844,678	105,140
16-Jun							
Mean	116,022	116,696	0	1,531,045	90,906	1,645	2,379
Median	116,217	116,182	0	23,764	87,940	0	0
25th	83,104	75,719	0	7,232	27,367	0	0
75th	148,442	143,483	0	40,639	140,253	0	3,080
12-Sep							
Mean	13,860	108,120	0	125,699	11071920	38,426	1,250
Median	9,016	73,167	0	113,534	4,811,268	0	0
25th	4,116	27,860	0	85,151	3,017,977	0	0
75th	31,332	90,874	0	170,302	18676166	67,245	2,918
27-Sep							
Mean	33,432	335,400	0	298,114	463,574	0	0
Median	28,812	375,092	0	170,302	317,671	0	0
25th	22,148	199,137	0	99,343	3,226	0	0
75th	47,488	428,862	0	298,028	635,481	0	0
Total							
Mean	68,359	555,335	3,920	445,482	25633357	687,721	22,369
Median	51,772	250,979	0	70,959	4,111,447	0	0

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25th	26,264	88,400	0	3,100	185,605	0	0
75th	98,969	634,092	0	170,302	30466131	806,938	35,640

Appendix 3 MRPP PAIRWISE COMPARISONS

Note: p values not corrected for multiple comparisons.

Groups (identifiers)		T	A	p	
Compared					
AUG17	vs. AUG31	-21.80360992	0.31374783	0.00000000	
AUG17	vs. SEPT12	-21.99783091	0.34041576	0.00000000	
AUG17	vs. SEPT27	-22.81262451	0.30437822	0.00000000	
AUG17	vs. JUNE16	-19.85155734	0.28710622	0.00000000	
AUG31	vs. SEPT12	-14.90579427	0.17434792	0.00000001	
AUG31	vs. SEPT27	-22.24678840	0.25440508	0.00000000	
AUG31	vs. JUNE16	-20.33845007	0.25275387	0.00000000	
SEPT12	vs. SEPT27	-20.84147261	0.24844923	0.00000000	
SEPT12	vs. JUNE16	-19.32545704	0.26161907	0.00000000	
SEPT27	vs. JUNE16	-16.58812978	0.14774844	0.00000000	

***** MRPP finished *****

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Appendix 4 Indicator Species Method

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

Dufrene and Legendre's Method

The method assumes that two or more a priori groups of sample units exist, and that species abundances have been recorded in each of the sample units.

For each species, the following steps are made in the implementation in PC-ORD:

1. Calculate the proportional abundance of a particular species in a particular group relative to the abundance of that species in all groups. Also express as a percentage and display the intermediate result.

Let

A = sample unit x species matrix

a_{ijk} = abundance of species *j* in sample unit (SU) *i* of group *k*

n_k = number of sample units in group *k*

g = total number of groups

First calculate the mean abundance x_{kj} of species *j* in group *k*:

$$x_{kj} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} a_{ijk}}{n_k}$$

Then calculate the relative abundance RA_{jk} of species *j* in group *k*

$$RA_{jk} = \frac{x_{kj}}{\sum_{k=1}^g x_{kj}}$$

2. Calculate the proportional frequency of the species in each group, i.e. the percentage of sample units in each group that contain that species. Also express as a percentage and display the intermediate result.

First transform **A** to a matrix of presence-absence, **B**:

$$b_{ij} = a_{ij}^0$$

Then calculate relative frequency RF_{kj} of species *j* in group *k*:

$$RF_{kj} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} b_{ijk}}{n_k}$$

3. Combine the two proportions calculated in steps 1 and 2 by multiplying them. Express the result as a percentage, yielding an indicator value IV_{kj} for each species *j* in each group *k*.

$$IV_{kj} = RA_{jk} \bullet RF_{kj} \bullet 100$$

4. The highest indicator value (IV_{max}) for a given species across groups is saved as a summary of the overall indicator value of that species.

5. Evaluate statistical significance of IV_{max} by a randomization method. Randomly reassign SU's to groups a large number of times (default=1000). Each time, calculate IV_{max} . The probability of type I error is based on the proportion of times that the IV_{max} from the randomized data set equals or exceeds the IV_{max} from the actual data set. The null hypothesis is that IV_{max} is no larger than would be expected by chance (i.e. that the species has no indicator value).

Appendix 5 Taxa list and codes by Divisions

Taxon	Taxon	Algal Division
Aulacoseira granulata (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= Melosira granulata)	AUGR	Bacillariophyta
Aulacoseira granulata var. angustissima (Müller) Simonsen (=Melosira granulata var. angustissima)	AUGR	Bacillariophyta
centric diatoms species	CENTDIAT	Bacillariophyta
centric diatoms species 2	CENTDIA2	Bacillariophyta

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

Melosira varians Agardh
pennate diatoms

MEVA Bacillariophyta
PENNDIAT Bacillariophyta

Taxon	Taxon	Algal Division
Actinastrum gracillimum Smith	ACGR	Chlorophyta
Ankistrodesmus falcatus (Corda) Ralfs	ANFA	Chlorophyta
Ankyra judayi (Smith) Fott (= Schroederia judayi (Smith) Fott)	ANJU	Chlorophyta
Chlamydomonas species	CHLSP	Chlorophyta
Closteriopsis acicularis (Chodat) Belcher & Swale	CLAC	Chlorophyta
Closteriopsis longissima (Lemmermann) Lemmermann	CLLO	Chlorophyta
Closteriopsis longissima var. tropica West & West	CLLO	Chlorophyta
Cosmarium species	COSP	Chlorophyta
Crucigenia fenestrata (Schmidle) Schmidle	CRFE	Chlorophyta
Crucigenia quadrata Morren	CRQU	Chlorophyta
Crucigenia species	CRUSP	Chlorophyta
Crucigeniella rectangularis (Nägeli) Komárek (= Willea rectangularis (Braun) John, Wynne & Tsarenko)	CRRE	Chlorophyta
CRUSP	CRUSP	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus bicaudatus (Dedusenko) Tsarenko	DEBI	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus bicellularis (Chodat) An, Friedl & Hegewald	DEBI	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus communis (Hegewald) Hegewald	DECO	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus intermedius (Chodat) Hegewald	DEIN	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus opoliensis (Richter) Hegewald	DEOP	Chlorophyta
Desmodesmus species	DESP	Chlorophyta
Dictyosphaerium ehrenbergianum Nägeli	DIEH	Chlorophyta
Eremosphaera gigas (Archer) Fott & Kalina (= Oocystis gigas Archer)	ERGI	Chlorophyta
Gregiochloris lacustris (Chodat) Marvan, Komárek & Comas (= Quadrigula lacustris (Chodat) Smith)	GRLA	Chlorophyta
Kirchneriella lunaris (Kirchner) Möbius (= Kirchneriella lunata Schmidle)	KILU	Chlorophyta
Komma species	KOSP	Chlorophyta
Oocystis borgei Snow	OOBO	Chlorophyta
Oocystis species	OOSP	Chlorophyta
Pectinodesmus pectinatus (Meyen) Hegewald, Wolf, Keller, Friedl & Krienitz (= Acutodesmus pectinatus (Meyen) Tsarenko)	PEPE	Chlorophyta

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

Pediastrum angulosum Ehrenberg ex Meneghini	PEAN	Chlorophyta
Pediastrum duplex Meyen (= Pediastrum duplex var. clathratum Meyen)	PEDU	Chlorophyta
Pteromonas species	PTSP	Chlorophyta
Scenedesmus ellipticus Corda	SCEL	Chlorophyta
Scenedesmus species	SCSP	Chlorophyta
Schroederia setigera (Schröder) Lemmermann	SCSE	Chlorophyta
Sphaerocystis schroeteri Chodat	SPSC	Chlorophyta

Taxon	TaxaCode	
Anabaenopsis species	ANASP	Cyanophyta
Anabaena species	ANSP	Cyanophyta
Aphanizomenon flosaquae Ralfs ex Bornet & Flahault	APFL	Cyanophyta
Aphanothece species	APHSP	Cyanophyta
Aphanocapsa incerta (Lemmermann) G.Cronberg & Komárek (= Microcystis incerta (Lemmermann) Cronberg & Komárek)	APIN	Cyanophyta
Aphanocapsa species	APSP	Cyanophyta
Chroococcus dispersus (Keissler) Lemmermann	CHDI	Cyanophyta
Chroococcus minor (Kützing) Nägeli	CHMI	Cyanophyta
Chroococciopsis species	CHROSP	Cyanophyta
Chroococcus turgidus (Kützing) Nägeli	CHTU	Cyanophyta
Cylindrospermopsis species	CYSP	Cyanophyta
Cylindrospermum species	CYSP	Cyanophyta
Dolichospermum circinalis (Brébisson) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek (= Anabaena circinalis Rabenhorst)	DOCI	Cyanophyta
Dolichospermum species	DOSP	Cyanophyta
Lyngbya species	LYSP	Cyanophyta
Merismopedia species	MESP	Cyanophyta
Oscillatoria princeps Vaucher ex Gomont	OSPR	Cyanophyta
Oscillatoria species	OSSP	Cyanophyta
Phormidium species	PHSP	Cyanophyta
Unknown filamentous cyanophyte	UNFICYAN	Cyanophyta

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

Taxon	Taxon	Algal Division
Chroomonas species	CHRSP	Cryptophyta
Cryptomonas species	CRSP	Cryptophyta

Taxon	Taxon	Algal Division
Ceratium hirundinella (Müller) Dujardin	CEHI	Dinophyta
Gymnodinium species	GYSP	Dinophyta
Peridinium species	PESP	Dinophyta

Taxon	Taxon	Algal Division
Asterionella formosa Hassall	ASFO	Euglenophyta
Euglena species	EUSP	Euglenophyta
Lepocinclis acus (O.F.Müller) B.Marin & Melkonian in Marin	LEAC	Euglenophyta
Lepocinclis species	LESP	Euglenophyta
Phacus species	PHASP	Euglenophyta
PHaSP	PHSP	Euglenophyta
Trachelomonas species	TRSP	Euglenophyta

Appendix 6 Phytoplankton cluster diagram by month.

Chapter 2 Phytoplankton Assemblages

CHAPTER 3: ZOOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

By
David C. Richards, Ph.D.

OreoHelix Ecological, Vineyard UT 84059
Phone: 406.580.7816
Email: oreohelix@icloud.com

And

Brett Marshall
River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT

SUMMARY

We found strong evidence that zooplankton assemblages varied seasonally during 2023 study, as expected. We also found that marginally reducing wave turbulence, the proximal physical factor limiting lake recovery, resulted measurable effects on the zooplankton assemblage. Results from this 2023 study support our past mesocosm experimental findings and those of ecologists worldwide tasked with restoring shallow lake ecosystems; sediment stability needs to be increased. These results will also be directly applicable to ecosystem function models necessary for predicting effects of reduced turbation and thus guide scientifically sound lake restoration.

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INTRODUCTION

Zooplankton grazers are the number one water column regulator of phytoplankton, including cyanoHABs (Iglesias et al. 2007, Scheffer 1998). Zooplankton frequently move between habitats including daily horizontal migration; subsequently zooplankton are a vital linkage between the pelagic, benthic and littoral zones (Vander Zanden and Vadeboncoeur 2002, Jones and Waldron, 2003). However, very little is known about the spatial and temporal patterns of zooplankton in Utah Lake despite their critically important relationships with: nutrient cycling, phytoplankton (including cyanoHABs) ecology and population dynamics, and other food web components in the lake (Richards and Miller 2017, Richards 2018).

Zooplankton obviously have top-down grazing effects on phytoplankton and cyanobacteria and in turn are affected by these (bottom-up effects) (Iglesias et al. 2007). Zooplankton also have different modes of feeding including grazing and predation, some of which prey upon other zooplankton. Most zooplankton are selective feeders. All of these complex interactions directly and indirectly influence nutrient cycling in the water column. Zooplankton excretion and respiration of nitrogen, phosphorus, and ammonia is immediately available and consumed by phytoplankton, often within minutes. This phytoplankton-zooplankton component of water column nutrient cycling has been well documented and known by limnologists and ecologists for several decades and is likely an important driver of cyanobacteria blooms in Utah Lake (Iglesias et al. 2007, Scheffer 1998).

Medium- and large-sized cladocerans, typically *Daphnia* spp. can markedly reduce phytoplankton biomass (Jeppesen et al. 1990, Scheffer 1998), even in communities dominated by cyanobacteria (Jeppesen et al. 2003, Lampert et al. 1986, Brooks and Dodson 1965, Gorokhova and Engstrom-Ost 2009, and Hogfors et al. 2014). *Daphnia* spp. have the ability to feed on bacteria, protozoa, phytoplankton and even some small zooplankton, highlighting their important role in freshwater food webs (Yin et al. 2010). It has been demonstrated that intensive zooplankton grazing can promote a clear-water state (Scheffer 1998). For example, grazing by *Daphnia* sp. has been reported to be responsible for spring clearing in temperate lakes (Meijer et al. 1999).

Phytoplankton assemblages can have a bottom-up control on zooplankton assemblages via several mechanisms, including relative abundance, digestibility, nutrient content, etc. Conversely, zooplankton assemblages can have a top-down control on phytoplankton assemblages via selective and non-selective grazing and contrary to past assumptions, it has become apparent that zooplankton routinely and selectively rely on cyanoHABs in their diets. Consequently, zooplankton assemblages can shift phytoplankton assemblages toward better adapted cyanobacteria consumer species (Motwani et al. 2017, Woodland et al. 2013, Koski et al. 2002, Vehmaa et al. 2013, Gorokhova and Engstrom-Ost 2009, Hogfors et al. 2014, Ger et al. 2016).

Utah Lake appears to support a diverse zooplankton assemblage that varies spatially and temporally (Richards and Miller 2017). There are >> 20 zooplankton taxa occurring in Utah Lake

including cladocera, copepod, and rotifer taxa from several functional groups, each with different life history and feeding strategies (Richards and Miller 2017, Richards 2019, Marshall 2019, and unpublished data). However, the effective number of zooplankton taxa is rather small indicating impairment.

The taxonomy of Utah Lake's zooplankton has never been fully documented and verified. Because of this gap, zooplankton taxonomy is under revision by Oreohelix Ecological and River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). It is of utmost importance to correctly identify zooplankton taxa in the lake.

Unfortunately, zooplankton assemblages in Utah Lake have also undergone bottlenecks and assemblage shifts, including those stressors discussed in the previous sections that have resulted in Utah Lake's zooplankton assemblages becoming analogs of past natural assemblages and that may no longer be able to regulate cyanoHABs.

In this chapter we analyze zooplankton assemblages inside and outside of mesocosms.

JUSTIFICATION

There is much concern as to the future of Utah Lake and what can be done to improve its condition (i.e., health, integrity), including the reduction of algal blooms and restoration of its native biota. However, there has been little to no effort expended to examine or understand the importance of the lake's food web and how top-down, trophic cascades effect and respond to current conditions or how biomanipulation may help restore its ecosystem health despite decades of research documenting their importance worldwide. Successful Utah Lake restoration cannot proceed without this understanding and holistic implementation.

LIMNOCORRAL STUDY GOALS

The overall goal of our 2023 mesocosm study was to understand factors that influence nutrient cycling, algal blooms, food web dynamics, and ecosystem functioning that contribute to the impairment of the ecological health of Utah Lake, particularly the effects of wind driven wave turbulence. Results from this ongoing research will help direct managers on how best to initiate restoration⁹ by using an integrated and adaptive management strategy, essential to improving its health (Richards 2021a, ongoing DWQ Utah Lake Science Panel studies, Richards 2021c, others).

The goal of the ecological component of the TSSD Utah Lake limnocorral study 2023 was to examine the direct and indirect effects of wave action, application of nutrients, juvenile carp, and surrogate bivalves on:

5. Zooplankton assemblages,
6. Benthic algae (periphyton) assemblages,
7. Zooplankton assemblages and,
8. Benthic invertebrate assemblages.

We postulated that the application of these treatments would have measurable direct and indirect effects on these four assemblages and that these non-target effects needed to be addressed. In addition, we expected that treatment effects would alter nutrient cycling and water quality in

⁹ Ecological restoration, "placing the ecosystem on a trajectory of recovery but not necessarily recovery to its former state so that it can persist, and its species can adapt and evolve" (Society Ecological Restoration).

complicated interactions within the food web (see Williams et al. 2024 for more details of this project) (please review Richards et al. 2023, 2019, Richards and Miller 2019a, and Richards and Miller 2017 for a holistic overview of Utah Lake’s unique foodweb and ecology).

We have discussed in detail Utah Lake’s ecosystem function including the effects of carp, loss of native species, particularly mollusks and aquatic vegetation, and the now all too prevalent effects of wind driven wave turbulence prevents ecosystem recovery in our previous mesocosm reports (Richards et al. 2022, 2023). Our 2023 limnocorral studies presented in this report focused on the direct and indirect effects of wind driven wave action on zooplankton, benthic algae, zooplankton, and benthic invertebrate assemblages.

In this chapter we focus our attention on mesocom effects on Utah Lake’s zooplankton assemblage. Subsequent chapters will examine benthic invertebrates and the interactions between biota and water chemistry.

METHODS
ZOOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

STUDY SITE

Zooplankton samples were collected inside limnocorrals (mesocosms) and outside of corrals, in-lake (Figure 1).

Figure 28 Schematic of limnocorrals (LC) (mesocosms) and outside in-lake sample locations. Orange triangles are buoys. Schematic generated by River Continuum Concepts.

ZOOPLANKTON SAMPLING AND PROCESSING

Chapter 3 Zooplankton Assemblages

We attached two 2-oz stainless steel weights to the tip of a 63-micron mesh zooplankton net and lowered it until the weights touched the benthic zone—which meant the opening of the net was 1m from the bottom of the lake. The tow line was then relaxed to allow the steel hoop to sink about 25-30 cm, placing the opening of the net about 0.7-0.73m above the benthic substrata. The depth of the opening-ring was noted before we pulled the net steadily, vertically to the water's surface. We completely washed all plankton toward the bottom collection area using tap water, and then rinsed the zooplankton into a labeled sample container using 99 % isopropanol.

A total of 95 zooplankton samples were collected and processed. See Table 1 for a listing of sample dates, and samples collected inside and outside of limnocorrals (mesocosms).

Table 12 List of sample events (dates), samples collected inside limnocorrals (LC), and outside of limnocorrals (Out). See Figure 1 for limnocorral locations and numbering.

Sample Event	Inside Mesocosms (LC)	Outside Mesocosms (Out)
June 16/17	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7
August 17	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
August 31	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
September 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
September 27	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9

Zooplankton samples were collected using a 63 μm mesh net and vertical pull from substrate to surface. All algal taxonomies were performed by River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT, the leading zooplankton taxonomy experts for Utah Lake and surrounding aquatic ecosystems. River Continuum Concepts reported zooplankton taxonomic results as density, individuals L^{-1} . Taxa were identified to lowest practical level, typically species. Identification to species level exceeded most lake assessment protocols and provided superior resolution necessary for our analysis and for future studies.

LABORATORY

Upon arrival at the lab, all samples were inventoried and logged into our sample tracking database which assigned unique sample identifier numbers, site codes, dates, and replicate numbers. Samples were gently rinsed through a 63-micron stainless steel sieve and rinsed into a quadrant-splitter petri dish using 75% aqueous isopropanol. The contents of the splitting dish were mixed with a pipette until the distribution of animals within quadrants appeared roughly equivalent in abundance and size. If the sample contained significant detritus, it was separated from the zooplankters under a dissecting microscope using the most effective magnification (10-100x) to ensure that no specimens were attached to the detritus removed. Once all the detritus was removed, we used a 4-sided die to randomly select one of the quadrants, which was transferred by pipette to a 6x6 gridded rectangular petri dish. Specimens were spread evenly across the gridded surface and two 6-sided dice were cast to determine which of the 36 grids was selected for identification. All specimens were removed from the selected grid and identified. After all the specimens from the first grid were removed, enumerated, and identified, another grid was randomly selected using the dice and the process was repeated until the total number of identified organisms exceeded 200 animals. If the first quarter was completely processed and the total number of animals remained below 200 animals, another quarter was randomly selected from the quadrant splitter dish using the four-sided die, and that quarter was transferred to the gridded dish

and grids were randomly selected with pairs of six-sided dice. This process was repeated, when necessary, until the total number of animals exceeded 200 animals. The total number of specimens reported for a remained < 200 animals only for samples that were completely (100%) identified.

The subsample factor was used to estimate the total abundance of animals. The subsample factor is the reciprocal of the percent of the sample processed to attain 200 animals. Thus, if 10 grids were used from the first quarter of the sample, then the percentage of the sample used is 6.944% ($0.25 \times (10/36)$). In this case the total of 200 animals is corrected to density by dividing the sample abundance by 0.06944, resulting in an abundance of 2880 per sample ($200/0.06944$). The community density dataset applies this factor to each, and every species identified from the sample.

The fixed count method of processing zooplankton samples was selected because it provides timely and cost-effective analysis of the dominant species present and is used by state agencies as endorsed by the U.S. E.P.A. for biological assessment of lake zooplankton communities. However, there are some limitations to fixed count subsample methods, and those limitations become more relevant as the portion of the sample identified becomes very small (<~1%). Imagine two communities where there are 10 species, with 3 species being much more abundant than the others. When we select a random subsample of 200 animals from community 2, most of the time, some taxa are omitted. Therefore, for this report, when densities are used, we are cautious when comparing the occurrence or non-occurrence of lower abundant taxa from samples that were heavily subsampled.

Identification followed the consensus taxonomy of Marshall (2018), which uses the keys of Pennank (1978), Haney et al. (2014), Balcer (1984) and a slew of original systematic descriptions and systematic revisions (e.g., Goulden 1968, Keifer 1976, Kořínek 1981, Berner et al. 1986, Orlova-Bienkowskaja 1998, Kotov 2003, Kotov et al. 2003, Korovchinsky 2002, Kotov et al. 2009, Han et al. 2011, Miracle et al. 2013) to correct and amend the errors that abound in the primary keys of Thorpe and Rogers (2016) which have errors and omissions of several Utah Lake Taxa. Although the taxa list has changed since publication, the error-corrections (re: Thorpe and Rogers 2016) and methods of Marshall 2018, guided taxonomic determinations.

MESOCOSM TREATMENTS

Several treatments within limnocorrals were applied during the study. These included:

- Juvenile carp
- Corbicula
- Nutrients
- Rhodamine
- Control

STATISTICAL METHODS

Four to five letter codes were made for each zooplankton taxon, typically the first two letters of the genus name and the first two letters of the species name unless there were duplicates. Seven to eight- digit location and sampling date codes were also developed for use in analyses.

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMS) ordination was used to compare zooplankton assemblage dis(similarity) relationships statistically and visually between corrals and dates. Ordination techniques are often more informative than hypothesis-testing approaches for exploring relationships between multivariate ecological assemblages or communities (McCune and Grace 2002). In general, ordination is the ordering of objects along axes according to their (dis)similarities; the main objective of ordination is to reduce many-dimensional relationships into a small number of more easily interpretable dimensions (i.e., axes on a plot). The strongest correlation structure in the data is extracted and is then used to position objects in ordination space. Objects that are close in the ordination space are more similar than objects distant in ordination space (McCune and Mefford 2011).

NMS was used in these analyses because it has been shown to be robust and highly informative for understanding ecological relationships. NMS ordination is often more broadly applicable for ecological studies than other ordination techniques because it does not require relationships among variables to be linear (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). NMS ordination permits the visualization of the multidimensional relationships of zooplankton assemblages into a more easily visualized, lower dimensional space. Dimensional reduction obviously creates some distortion in relationships between samples. The level of reduction in distortion is measured as 'stress', where lower stress values equal less distortion. NMS plots with stress values of 15% (0.15) or less are typically considered to be a good representation of the data and stress values lower than 10% (0.10) are considered excellent representations (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010).

Several distance measures were used and evaluated including Sorensen (Bray-Curtis), Relative Sorensen, Jaccard, Euclidean, Relative Euclidean, and Morisita-Horn. NMS analysis was run for 250 iterations using the real data and 250 iterations in randomized Monte Carlo simulations. Best-fit models were selected based on stable final stress < 0.15 and 3-dimensional solutions or less. NMS ordinations were rotated using varimax rotation to maximize variation along the axes and extracted as univariate scores. Consequently, the final ordinations can be rotated either vertically or horizontally without effecting the results. Centroid labels and convex hulls of months were added to the ordinations to aid in the interpret the relationships. Post hoc proportion of variance represented by each axis was calculated based on the R^2 value between distance in the ordination space and distance in the original space.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP), a non-parametric multivariate method was used to formally test the hypothesis of no differences in zooplankton assemblages between months. MRPP has the advantage of not requiring distributional assumptions such as multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance and thus is often preferred over perMANOVA for analyzing multivariate ecological data (McCune and Grace 2002). The same distance measure was used for each MRPP analyses as was for corresponding NMS models. The chance-corrected within-group test statistic, A (and associated p-value) was used to evaluate the hypothesis of no difference in groupings (McCune and Grace 2002). Post hoc multiple comparisons were also made when appropriate.

We used Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) in PC-ORD to determine taxa that were strong indicators of sampling events (seasonal). ISA used Dufrêne and Legendre's (1997) method of calculating species indicator values that provided a simple, intuitive solution. The method combined information on biovolumes of zooplankton taxa abundance for each sample event and the faithfulness of occurrence of a taxa in a particular sample event. ISA produced indicator values for

Chapter 3 Zooplankton Assemblages

each taxon in each group. These were then tested for statistical significance using a randomization technique (see Appendix 4 for more detailed information on ISA method).

All multivariate and additional analyses including rank abundance and descriptive summary statistics were made using PC-ORD for Windows Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018) using Parallels Desktop 19.2.1 for Mac virtual platform.

Regression analyses were selected using the most appropriate model including linear, Poisson, fractional, and negative binomial. Best fit regression models were chosen based on lowest log likelihood, AIC, and BIC values. ANOVAs and MANOVAs were also conducted where appropriate. Descriptive statistics were also calculated for select data. Statistical analyses and graphics were made using Stata 16.1 for Mac (Intel 64-bit) (StataCorp 2021). Multivariate assemblage analyses were conducted using PC-ORD Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018). Graphical representations of statistical models were made using either Stata or PC-ORD. Details of additional statistical methods not listed here are described in individual Results sections.

RESULTS

We found and identified nineteen zooplankton taxa in our 2023 mesocosm study (Table 2).

Table 13 Zooplankton taxa found in 2023 mesocosm study with taxon codes used in analyses. 19 taxa occurrences.

Group	Phylum	Order	Family	Taxon	Code
copepods	Arthropoda	Cyclopoida		Nauplii (small)	NAUP1
copepods				Nauplii (large)	NAUP2
copepods	Arthropoda	Cyclopoida	Cyclopidae	<i>Acanthocyclops americanus</i>	ACAM
copepods	Arthropoda	Calanoida	Diaptomidae	Diaptomidae	DIAP
copepods	Arthropoda	Calanoida	Diaptomidae	<i>Leptodiaptomus sicilis</i>	LESI
copepods	Arthropoda	Calanoida	Diaptomidae	<i>Leptodiaptomus siciloides</i>	LESIC
copepods	Arthropoda	Harpacticoida	Laophontidae	<i>Onychocamptus mohammed</i>	ONMO
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Ceriodaphnia</i> sp.	CESP
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Ceriodaphnia dubia</i>	CEDU
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia ambigua</i> sp. 2	DAAM
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia mendotae</i>	DAME
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia pulex</i> gr.	DAPU
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia retrocurva</i>	DARE
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Sididae	<i>Diaphanosoma</i> cf. <i>Heberti</i>	DIAPH
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Bosminiidae	<i>Bosmina longirostris</i> complex	BOLO
cladocerans	Arthropoda	Cladocera	Leptodoridae	<i>Leptodora kindti</i>	LEKI
rotifers	Rotifera	Plioma	Brachionidae	<i>Brachonus caudatus</i>	BRCA
rotifers	Rotifera	Plioma	Brachionidae	<i>Keratella hiemalis</i>	KEHI
rotifers	Rotifera	Plioma	Brachionidae	<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>	KECO

We then estimated that there were between 19 and 20 zooplankton taxa in the study area based on rarefaction analysis, first-order jackknife, second-order jackknife, and Chao estimators given our

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sampling effort (Figure 3). These analyses demonstrated that we had very good coverage of zooplankton sampling in the study area.

Figure 29 Rarefaction curve of number of zooplankton taxa predicted in our study area based on sample effort.

Rank abundance (individuals L⁻¹) of zooplankton taxa uniformly decreased suggesting a relatively balanced assemblage (Figure 30 and Table 2).

Figure 30 Rank abundances of zooplankton encountered in our mesocosm study, 2023. Rank abundance metrics are in Table 14

Table 14 Zooplankton taxa rank abundance, mean density, rank frequency, and number of occurrences.

Taxon	Rank Abundance	Mean Density	Rank Frequency	Frequency (number of occurrences)
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ACAM	1	710.623	1	97
LESI	2	418.815	2	95
DARE	3	355.687	4	79
DAPU	4	214.297	7	52
DIAPH	5	172.643	3	93
DAME	6	93.792	5	67
CEDU	7	49.035	8	46
LESIC	8	34.386	6	56
NAUP1	9	28.451	10	38
NAUP2	10	18.497	11	32
KECO	11	14.56	12	25
LEKI	12	6.637	9	42
KEHI	13	4.7	14	8
BRCA	14	1.543	13	11
DAAM	15	0.806	15	5
ONMO	16	0.615	16	3
BOLO	17	0.201	17	3
CESP	18	0.175	18	2
DIAP	19	0.075	19	1

SEASONAL CHANGES IN ZOOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

We found strong evidence of seasonal zooplankton assemblage patterns using NMS and MRPP. We developed an excellent fit NMS model for the zooplankton assemblages showing seasonal changes. The NMS model had a 3-dimensional solution, with final stress = 8.26, final instability < 0.0001 at 87 iterations using a Relative Sorenson distance matrix. The NMS model explained 0.95 seasonal variability in assemblages with Axis 1= 0.47, Axis 2 = 0.29, and Axis 3 = 0.19 (Figure 6 and Figure 7).

The NMS model showed that zooplankton assemblages varied seasonally (Figure 6 and Figure 7) as we have reported elsewhere in Utah Lake and as occurs throughout temperate regions, although individual taxa densities in Utah Lake can differ annually (Richards et al. years). Some of the less common taxa varied more so than did the common taxa annually. 2023 was a very high-water year compared to recent years and likely affected assemblages and taxa relative abundances.

Figure 31 NMS Axis 1 and Axis 2 showing seasonal trend in zooplankton assemblages starting in June progressing through summer and into early autumn when assemblages once again started to resemble early summer assemblages.

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Figure 32 NMS Axis 1 vs. Axis 3 and Axis 2 vs. Axis 3 showing differences and similarities of zooplankton assemblages among and between sampling events.

NMS axes were determined by densities of individual taxa. Table 4 provides Pearson (parametric r , and R^2) and Kendall (τ) correlations of taxa with each of the three NMS axes.

Table 15 Pearson and Kendall correlations with NMS ordination axes. Positive values are to the right and top of axes, negative values are to the left and bottom of axes.

Taxon	Axis 1			Axis 2			Axis 3		
	r	R^2	τ	r	R^2	τ	r	R^2	τ
NAUP1	-0.461	0.212	-0.251	0.321	0.103	0.248	-0.188	0.035	-0.251
NAUP2	-0.294	0.086	-0.139	0.29	0.084	0.293	-0.032	0.001	-0.074
ACAM	0.46	0.212	0.333	-0.033	0.001	-0.078	0.159	0.025	0.141
DIAP	-0.015	0	-0.03	-0.055	0.003	-0.069	0.101	0.01	0.087
LESI	-0.379	0.144	-0.38	0.425	0.181	0.401	0.468	0.219	0.271
LESIC	-0.077	0.006	0.016	-0.182	0.033	-0.09	0.042	0.002	-0.005
ONMO	0.004	0	-0.001	0.051	0.003	-0.011	0.095	0.009	-0.015
CESP	-0.02	0	-0.022	0.029	0.001	-0.001	-0.028	0.001	-0.022
CEDU	-0.421	0.177	-0.407	-0.161	0.026	-0.026	-0.201	0.041	-0.073
DAAM	-0.003	0	-0.078	-0.205	0.042	-0.204	-0.003	0	0.016
DAME	-0.199	0.04	0.006	-0.55	0.303	-0.408	-0.156	0.024	-0.173
DAPU	-0.654	0.428	-0.506	-0.062	0.004	-0.251	-0.411	0.169	-0.204
DARE	0.479	0.23	0.543	0.305	0.093	0.236	-0.496	0.246	-0.173
DIAPH	-0.457	0.209	-0.28	0.426	0.182	0.394	0.094	0.009	0.062
BOLO	-0.179	0.032	-0.157	-0.301	0.09	-0.221	-0.037	0.001	-0.077
LEKI	0.086	0.007	0.072	-0.396	0.156	-0.265	-0.071	0.005	-0.041
BRCA	0.094	0.009	0.086	-0.211	0.045	-0.245	0.012	0	0.013
KEHI	-0.373	0.139	-0.342	0.134	0.018	0.151	-0.077	0.006	-0.092
KECO	0.249	0.062	0.178	-0.138	0.019	-0.145	0.121	0.015	0.043

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Multi-response Permutation Procedures (MRPP) results confirmed our NMS results that showed seasonal changes in zooplankton assemblages. MRPP provided very strong evidence that zooplankton assemblages differed seasonally ($T = -42.41$, $A = 0.40$, $p < 0.001$) and that assemblages differed between all sampling events (Table 5).

Table 16 MRPP results provided strong evidence ($p < 0.01$) that zooplankton assemblages differed between and among sample events.

Sample Events	T	A	p
17-Aug vs.31-Aug	-20.21	0.28	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 12-Sep	-20.84	0.44	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 27-Sep	-20.93	0.35	< 0.01
17-Aug vs. 16-Jun	-22.19	0.39	< 0.01
31-Aug vs. 12-Sep	-19.00	0.25	< 0.01
31-Aug vs. 27-Sep	-21.49	0.27	< 0.01
31-Aug vs.16-Jun	-22.23	0.28	< 0.01
12-Sep vs. 27-Sep	-8.77	0.11	< 0.01
12-Sep vs.16-Jun	-22.76	0.35	< 0.01
27-Sep vs.16-Jun	-20.18	0.28	< 0.01

SEASONAL ZOOPLANKTON INDICATOR TAXA

In the previous section we showed that zooplankton assemblages differed seasonally (i.e., by sample events). In this section we show that several individual zooplankton taxa were strong seasonal indicators based on Indicator Species Analysis (Table 6) and were mostly responsible for the overall seasonal differences found in assemblages.

Table 17 Seasonal zooplankton Indicator taxa. See Table 2 for taxa names.

Sample Event	Taxon	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	IV from Randomized groups		p *
			Mean	Std. Dev	
JUNE16	NAUP1	60.7	15.4	4.05	< 0.01
	CEDU	70.6	19.9	5.55	< 0.01
	DAPU	67.5	18.6	4.06	< 0.01
	DIAPH	44.1	25.2	2.71	< 0.01
	KEHI	50	7.2	3.56	< 0.01
	NAUP2	34.8	14.2	4.19	< 0.01
AUG17	DAME	67.5	24	5.02	< 0.01
	LEKI	48.8	15.6	3.54	< 0.01
	LESIC	39.5	20.7	4.54	< 0.01
	BRCA	19.7	8	3.39	< 0.01
	DAAM	15.6	6.2	3.42	< 0.01
	BOLO	14.3	5.1	3.02	< 0.01
AUG31	ACAM	33.9	24.6	2.06	< 0.01

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	DARE	45.3	24.7	4.05	< 0.01
SEPT27	LESI	46.1	26	2.86	< 0.01

* Proportion of randomized trials with indicator value equal to or exceeding the observed indicator value. $p = (1 + \text{number of runs } \geq \text{observed}) / (1 + \text{number of randomized runs})$.

MESOCOSM EFFECTS ON ZOOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES

We found strong evidence that the mesocosms, ignoring individual mesocosm treatment effects, by simply blocking wave action, affected zooplankton assemblages in late August through September. However, we found no evidence for mesocosm effects in June or early August sampling events (Table 7).

Table 18 Multi-Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP) results of mesocosm effects (inside vs. outside of mesocosms) on zooplankton assemblages by sample event. A = chance corrected within group agreement statistic.

Sample Event	T	A	p
June16	-0.59	0.019	0.22
Aug17	-0.69	0.013	0.20
Aug31	-2.59	0.07	0.02
Sept12	-3.98	0.10	0.01
Sept27	-4.21	0.11	< 0.01

Although zooplankton taxa richness and effective number of zooplankton varied seasonally, we found no evidence of mesocosm effects on these two metrics (Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Figure 33 Zooplankton Taxa Richness, S inside and outside of mesocosm by sampling event.

The mean effective number of zooplankton taxa (ENT) was about half the number of encountered taxa and ranged from about 3 to 5 or 6 (Figure 9). ENT was about four of five times less than the

total number of taxa found during the study, $N = 19$ (Table 1). Low ENT signifies impairment to the lake.

Figure 34. Effective number of zooplankton taxa inside and outside of mesocosms by month.

Zooplankton evenness appeared to be greater inside mesocosms in the August 31 sample event, but we did not find any evidence for difference in any of the other sample events (Figure 10).

Figure 35 Taxa Evenness, E inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event.

There was also no evidence of mesocosm effects on the two zooplankton diversity indices, Shannon's, and Simpsons (Figure 11 and Figure 12).

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Figure 36 Zooplankton Shannon Diversity, H for zooplankton inside and outside mesocosms by month.

Figure 37 Simpson Diversity, D for zooplankton inside and outside mesocosms by month.

Zooplankton density appeared to be greater inside mesocosms in the June16 and Aug17 sampling events, but this was not supported statistically. There was however statistical evidence that zooplankton density was greater outside of mesocosms than inside on the Aug31 sample and it appeared this also occurred in the Sept27 sample event (Figure 13).

Figure 38 Zooplankton density inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event. Negative binomial regression: Aug31 IRR = 2.17, $z = 2.25$, $p = 0.03$.

TREATMENT EFFECTS ON ZOOPLANKTON ASSEMBLAGES AND INDIVIDUAL ZOOPLANKTON TAXA

In the previous section we showed that the mesocosms affected zooplankton assemblages but had little effect on diversity metrics. In this section we show how mesocosm treatments may have affected zooplankton assemblages and individual zooplankton taxa.

Cluster analysis showed that zooplankton assemblages differed in several of the treatments Figure 16). Specifically,

- Mesocosms 2, 5, 6, 7, 10, and 12 on August 17 compared to the other treatments on August 17 that clustered together,
- Mesocosms 2, 3, 4, 5 and 12 on September 12 compared to other treatments on September 12 that clustered together, and
- Mesocosms 2, 3, 9, and 10 on August 31 compared to other treatments on August 31 that tended to cluster together.

Reasons for these differences are unknown, whether there were actual treatment effects, the poor condition of mesocosms, or because there was only one sample collected from a mesocosm on each sample event. There did not appear to be any other treatment effects on zooplankton assemblages, likely because of chronic disrepair of mesocosms allowing relatively rapid flushing, thus preventing observable effects.

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Figure 39 Potential effects of treatments on zooplankton assemblages using cluster analysis and dendrograms. Coded by month. Distance measure = relative Sorenson, group linkage = nearest neighbor, clustering of codes relativized by maximum.

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Cluster analysis showed some treatment effects therefore, we examined in more detail whether there were treatment effects on individual zooplankton taxa.

Figure 18 shows individual zooplankton taxa densities inside and outside of mesocosms by sampling event. Some taxa seemed unaffected, while others were either more abundant inside mesocosms or outside mesocosms in the lake and this varied by sample event (Figure 18).

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Figure 40 Zooplankton density (individuals L⁻¹) inside and outside mesocosms by month.

POTENTIAL TREATMENT EFFECTS ON ZOOPLANKTON DENSITY

We used joint skewness and kurtosis tests for normality (StataCorp 2019) to determine an appropriate transformation for parametric statistical analyses. The test used χ^2 with a larger p-value indicating a better transformation towards Gaussian normality. The commonly used and easily interpretable square root transformation provided the best redistribution of densities.

Figure 41 Raw zooplankton density distribution (left) and best transformation (square root) for normal (Gaussian) parametric analyses (right).

Zooplankton densities (sqrt individuals m⁻²) varied widely between treatments on the August 31 and September 12 sample events but were more consistent between treatments on the August 17 and September 27 sample events (Figure 42). We didn't find any evidence that zooplankton densities (sqrt transformed) differed between any of the treatments and the control mesocosms on the August 17, August 31, and September 27 sample events, even with the wide variability on August 31 and September 12 sample events. However, there was strong evidence that densities differed between several treatments and controls on the September 12 sample event.

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Figure 42 Zooplankton densities m^{-2} (sqrt transformed) for each treatment compared to controls for each sample event. Dashed black line is mean.

The following table, Table 19 provides one sample t-tests for treatment effects on zooplankton densities vs. controls on the September 12 sample event. We found evidence that all treatment densities differed from controls except the juvenile carp and adult carp treatments on September 12.

Table 19 One sample t-test results for September 12 sample event. Negative t statistic indicates zooplankton density m^{-2} (sqrt transformed) greater than control densities.

Treatment	t	p-value
Carp eggs	-3.84	0.03
GR Control	-6.79	0.01
GRP1	-11.68	0.01
GRP2	6.34	0.01
Juvenile carp	1.16	0.18
Clams 1	3.25	0.04
Clams 2	-6.33	0.01
GRP 3	-4.18	0.03
Adult carp	0.58	0.30

DIURNAL PATTERNS

It is well known that zooplankton assemblage diurnal patterns exist throughout the world and have been reported in Utah Lake (Richards and Miller personal observations) as they track phytoplankton diurnal patterns. We cursorily examined diurnal patterns of zooplankton taxa in this study. Some taxa appeared to have diurnal patterns either occurring at greater biovolumes late morning or early afternoon and varied by sampling event (month). Wave induced turbidity may have clouded these results. These results support other's observations that diurnal patterns exist in the lake and that sample timing may influence results and confound interpretation.

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Figure 43 Diurnal patterns of zooplankton taxa densities by sample event.

DISCUSSION

As with all temperate lakes, Utah Lake's zooplankton assemblage transitioned seasonally in a generally predictable manner. This natural transition was somewhat delayed by an abnormally high-water year that diluted nutrients in spring and kept water temperatures lower than in previous low water years that have consistently occurred during the last decade or so.

The effects of mesocosms on the zooplankton assemblage and as we have shown in Chapter 1, phytoplankton assemblages, clearly implicates wave induced turbidity and sediment resuspension as a leading impairment to Utah Lake's health. Zooplankton assemblages closely tracked phytoplankton assemblages. See Richards et al. 2022 mesocosm report for more details of zooplankton assemblage ecology as it relates to our mesocosm studies and restoration of Utah Lake.

Utah Lake suffers from high turbidity due to several factors including,

- its shallow nature,
- strong winds and waves,
- easily suspended fine sediments,
- bioturbator fishes (primarily carp but also other non-indigenous species),
- transition from benthic and macrophyte primary producers that stabilized sediments to zooplankton dominated primary production,
- loss of mollusks that also stabilized sediments, and
- regulation as a reservoir that resulted in unnatural lake level fluctuations, etc. (Richards reports)

Even though these factors contribute to turbidity in Utah Lake; turbidity is now primarily caused by wind and wave driven sediment resuspension that directly affects light penetration and nutrient levels in the water column. Bioturbators (e.g., carp, catfish) also contribute to sediment resuspension but likely to a lesser extent. Light and nutrient levels can have many anticipated and unanticipated indirect effects on Utah Lake's foodweb including the transfer of nutrients and energy from the base of the foodweb (primary producers), to grazer consumers (zooplankton), to higher level trophic organisms including fishes and birds.

Figure 44 Response of primary, secondary, and tertiary production to turbulence (e.g., sediment resuspension, turbidity). From Jin et al. (2021).

In large shallow lake ecosystems such as Utah Lake, zooplankton productivity generally increases with phytoplankton biomass but then is somewhat limited by wave induced turbidity (Quinlan et al. 2021, Edwards et al. 2016, Scheffer 1998, Scheffer et al. 2001, Richards 2022b). Resuspension enhances release of sediment bound particles into the water column making them available to phytoplankton and then zooplankton grazers (Tammeorg et al. 2013, Tang et al. 2020, Zhang et al. 2020). However, large amounts of suspended solids entering the water column from resuspension interferes with zooplankton feeding and production (Schallenberg and Burns 2004). Please see our 2022 mesocosm report for more detailed discussion (Richards et al. 2022).

Trophic transfer of energy and matter from primary producers to higher trophic levels is a fundamental aspect of food web functioning (Jin et al. 2021, Richards 2022a). A reduction in trophic transfer due to wind induced turbulence can potentially lead to declines of higher trophic levels in aquatic food webs including zooplankton, fish and waterbirds, but is generally understudied (Jin et al. 2021, Richards 2022a). A proof- of -concept Utah Lake foodweb model created by Richards (2022b) suggested that trophic transfer efficiency in the lake was out of balance with Lindeman's (1942) 10% 'rule'. Richards (2022b) also found that zooplankton grazers in the lake did not appear to be able to utilize a large portion of the zooplankton biomass mostly during summer months (i.e., low ecotrophic efficiency) and that much of the zooplankton biomass was unconsumed and fell as detrital 'rain'. These findings suggest that the effects of sediment resuspension, turbulence, and turbidity on light and nutrient levels in Utah Lake likely play a significant role in retaining Utah Lake in an unbalanced poorly functioning state, but we suggest the lake is redeemable.

CONCLUSION

Results from our 2023 mesocosm study showed the effects of mesocosms on zooplankton assemblages. This clearly demonstrated that sediment resuspension from wind induced wave turbulence is now the ultimate factor limiting restoration of Utah Lake.

APPENDICES

Appendix 7 Indicator Species Method

Dufrene and Legendre's Method

The method assumes that two or more a priori groups of sample units exist, and that species abundances have been recorded in each of the sample units.

For each species, the following steps are made in the implementation in PC-ORD:

1. Calculate the proportional abundance of a particular species in a particular group relative to the abundance of that species in all groups. Also express as a percentage and display the intermediate result.

Let

- A = sample unit x species matrix
- a_{ijk} = abundance of species j in sample unit (SU) i of group k
- n_k = number of sample units in group k
- g = total number of groups

First calculate the mean abundance x_{kj} of species j in group k :

$$x_{kj} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} a_{ijk}}{n_k}$$

Then calculate the relative abundance RA_{jk} of species j in group k

$$RA_{jk} = \frac{x_{kj}}{\sum_{k=1}^g x_{kj}}$$

2. Calculate the proportional frequency of the species in each group, i.e. the percentage of sample units in each group that contain that species. Also express as a percentage and display the intermediate result.

First transform A to a matrix of presence-absence, B:

$$b_{ij} = a_{ij}^0$$

Then calculate relative frequency RF_{kj} of species j in group k :

$$RF_{kj} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} b_{ijk}}{n_k}$$

3. Combine the two proportions calculated in steps 1 and 2 by multiplying them. Express the result as a percentage, yielding an indicator value IV_{kj} for each species j in each group k .

$$IV_{kj} = RA_{jk} \cdot RF_{kj} \cdot 100$$

4. The highest indicator value (IV_{max}) for a given species across groups is saved as a summary of the overall indicator value of that species.

5. Evaluate statistical significance of IV_{max} by a randomization method. Randomly reassign SU's to groups a large number of times (default=1000). Each time, calculate IV_{max} . The probability of type I error is based on the proportion of times that the IV_{max} from the randomized data set equals or exceeds the IV_{max} from the actual data set. The null hypothesis is that IV_{max} is no larger than would be expected by chance (i.e. that the species has no indicator value).

ADDENDUM

Daphnia mendotae = *Daphnia galeata mendotae*

Daphnia mendotae was described from Lake Mendota, Wisconsin—the birthplace of American Limnology. However, genetic similarity with the old-world species *D. galeata*, which has seniority over North American *D. mendotae*, eventually placed *D. mendotae* as one of the two subspecies of *D. galeata*. Thus, the current scientific name for this species is *Daphnia galeata mendotae*, or *D. g. mendotae*. The traditional *D. mendotae* name was retained in these reports because it has a long history of use by other researchers on Utah Lake (e.g., Richards 2019) and because the taxon is treated simply as *D. mendotae* in the currently most commonly used taxonomic keys (Balcer et al. 1984, Haney et al. 2013, Thorpe and Rogers 2016)—Other Utah Lake investigators are likely to use the same nomenclature. Long term zooplankton studies on eutrophic Lake Mendota (e.g., Lathrop et al. 1999) found that *D. g. mendotae* populations contributed to water clarity in summer if they were established early, but in years where larger, less heat-tolerant *Daphnia* species became established earlier, water clarity was greater in the spring than in the summer because competitive exclusion slowed the growth of *D. g. mendotae* populations.

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CHAPTER 4: BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE ASSEMBLAGES

By
David C. Richards, Ph.D.

OreoHelix Ecological, Vineyard UT 84059
Phone: 406.580.7816
Email: oreohelix@icloud.com

and

Brett Marshall
River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT

SUMMARY

Utah Lake's ecosystem has experienced major degradation shifts with marked increases in entropy in little over a century, a literal blink of a geologic eye. A key factor in Utah Lake's ecosystem downfall was degradation of the vast majority of its littoral zone habitat into profundal zone habitat. This is reflected in its now non-analog benthic invertebrate assemblage that endeavors to fill the roles of the tragic loss of the lake's keystone mollusk assemblage, among other factors.

A total of 53 benthic invertebrate samples were collected, processed, and taxonomically identified in the 2023 mesocosm study. There was strong evidence for seasonal shifts in the benthic assemblage. Chironomid larvae were more abundant inside mesocosms, and segmented and unsegmented worms were more abundant outside mesocosms demonstrating the positive effects of the mesocosms. Overall, mesocosms tended to improve evenness, diversity, and effective number of taxa, particularly in the August 31 sample event. The overall effective number of taxa was roughly between 2 and 4 taxa, which signifies extreme impairment.

Chironomid larvae were the most abundant benthic taxa at 56% relative abundance, segmented and unsegmented worms comprised 44% abundance, and other benthic taxa were < 1% abundance. This poorly developed benthic invertebrate assemblage reflects the poor condition of Utah Lake's benthos. The HBI index, an index of tolerance to pollution was 8.93 indicating very poor water quality and severe degree of organic pollution.

Even though, the benthic invertebrate assemblage was a pittance of past assemblages, the importance and ecosystem function of remaining benthic taxa should not be underestimated, particularly chironomid larvae. These larvae now appear to govern benthic ecosystem function, including to help regulate cyanobacteria blooms. Their role is discussed in detail.

Results from this and past mesocosm studies presented in our progress reports can be used to help guide holistic restoration efforts.

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INTRODUCTION

After the inevitable demise of the keystone ecosystem engineering mollusks and associated ecological shift to a lower trophic state in Utah Lake over the past century, remaining benthic invertebrate species endeavored to fill vacant functional roles. Since the late 1800s benthic substrate conditions shifted from a substrate stabilized by mussels and clams, macrophytes, and benthic algae to a mostly unconsolidated mud-clay-silt unstable substrate that occupies most of the top layers of the lake substrate today. This chapter evaluates mesocosm effects on benthic invertebrate assemblages that live in this zone, the profundal zone.

METHODS

STUDY SITE

Benthic invertebrate samples were collected inside limnocorrals (mesocosms) and outside of corrals, in-lake (Figure 1).

Figure 45 Schematic of limnocorrals (LC) (mesocosms) and outside in-lake sample locations. Orange triangles are buoys. Schematic generated by River Continuum Concepts.

BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE SAMPLING, PROCESSING, AND TAXONOMIC IDENTIFICATION

A total of 53 benthic invertebrate samples were collected, processed, and taxonomically identified. See Table 1 for a listing of sample dates, and samples collected inside and outside of limnocorrals (mesocosms).

Table 20 List of sample events (dates), samples collected inside limnocorrals (LC), and outside of limnocorrals (Out). See Figure 1 for limnocorral locations and numbering.

Sample Event	Inside Mesocosms (LC)	Outside Mesocosms (Out)
--------------	-----------------------	-------------------------

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June 16/17	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7
August 31	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8
September 27	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12	1, 2, 3, 5

Samples were collected using a petite Ponar grab (Figure 46) with area = 0.023 m² deployed from TSSD boat.

Figure 46 Petite Ponar grab similar to the one used in our study, 2023.

When sampling from within a corral, we suspended the sampler above the water, laterally as far from the edge of corral as possible (about 1m). After the sampler reached the bottom, we pulled vertically on the rope/chain until the jaws set closed. If the sampler did not completely seal, it was rinsed with filtered field water and redeployed elsewhere until we attained a good seal/sample. Once a properly sealed sample was attained, it was rinsed in a 500-micron sieve bucket until the silt and clays were purged from the sample. Samples were then preserved in new labeled jars with 99% isopropanol.

The shoreline area where mesocosms were installed in 2023 was typical of Utah Lake's degraded habitat where once was abundant macrophytes, stable sediments, and a functioning littoral zone and is now what we consider part of the profundal zone.

PROCESSING AND TAXONOMY

In the laboratory, benthic samples were washed gently with tap water and nested sieve system of 350-microns over a 1000-micron sieve; the larger sieve contents were used for taxonomy, and the smaller-mesh sieve's contents were preserved and retained for posterity in case they are needed later. This followed the trend using larger mesh-sizes for processing muddy samples from wetlands (e.g., Barba 2010), where silt and clay balls hinder sorting under microscopy by perpetually fouling/clouding the preservative—greatly reducing visibility. The larger mesh size greatly reduces sorting time, the contribution of smaller animals, and the number of immature, ambiguously identified animals—to order or family-level—but may result in slightly lower richness estimates (e.g., Harwell and Fukiyama 2015).

Using the larger sieve portion also prevented our methods from obfuscating important trends in the larger invertebrates responsible for bioturbation (which may play an important role in ameliorating

toxic cyanobacteria blooms). Using fixed-count subsampling protocols (e.g., Plafkin et al. 1989, Barbour et al. 1999), which are primarily influenced from high-abundance tiny invertebrates (e.g., nematodes, rotifers etc.), excludes less-ephemeral taxa from the data set (e.g., Marshall 2014, Marshall in prep), numerically excluding the larger invertebrates. This method resulted in zero subsampling for most samples and those that were subsampled (4/54) used a large portion of the sample required most of the sample to be processed. Thus, this method greatly increased the similarity of unit-effort for density determinations among different corrals and treatments. Zooplankton were removed from benthos and included in the data sets, (mostly *Daphnia*), but were not used toward the subsample target of >200-animals per sample. Additionally, zooplankton collected with benthos were not included in the broader analyses because they were addressed in their own section as plankton.

Taxonomy followed the guides of Merritt et al. (2019), Thorpe and Rogers (2016), Anderson et al. (2013) and Epler (2001)—except zooplankton, which followed the consensus taxonomy described earlier.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES

Statistical analyses were similar to those in our phytoplankton and zooplankton chapters. In addition, we developed Hilsenhoff Biotic Tolerance Index (HBI) values that are commonly used by water quality agencies.

The Hilsenhoff Biotic Tolerance Index (HBI) was created by William Hilsenhoff in 1977 to measure the effects of oxygen depletion (BOD) in Wisconsin streams resulting from organic or nutrient pollution. HBI is a quantitative diagnostic metric used to identify samples with a high degree of pollution tolerant organisms. based on the predetermined pollution tolerances of the observed taxon. This index is on a scale from 0 to 10 with higher values indicating more tolerant organism and more polluted conditions, and lower values indicating sensitive taxa and less polluted conditions. HBI estimates the overall tolerance of the community in a sampled area, weighted by the relative abundance of each taxonomic group (family, genus, etc.).

The formula is $\sum (n_i * t_i) / N$, where,

n_i is the number of individuals of the "i"th taxon,

t_i is the tolerance index value of that taxon,

N is the total number of individuals in the sample assigned a Hilsenhoff Biotic Tolerance value.

EPA and other water quality agencies use Tolerance Values derived from HBI values that vary slightly from region to region for each taxon. (Barbour et al. 1999). Tolerance Values are error prone when combining species to genus or family level taxonomy or when values are unknown and estimated using best professional judgement.

RESULTS

The total number of taxa we found in our benthic samples was 17 (Table 21) with estimates of total number species in the study area = 18. Many of the invertebrates collected were zooplankton Cladocera and Copepoda (Table 21) that were in good condition and were either still alive during collection or recently dead. Of the non-zooplankters, nine taxa were Chironomidae (midges), three segmented and unsegmented worm taxa, one mollusk, and one amphipod and one ostracod taxon (Table 21). Chironomids were the only insect taxon collected.

Chapter 4 Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages

Table 21 Invertebrates collected in benthic samples 2023 and codes used in this report.

Phylum	Class	Group	Taxon	Taxon Code
Annelida	Clitellata	Lumbricidae	<i>Eiseniella</i> sp.	EISP
Annelida	Clitellata	Oligochaeta	Oligochaeta	OLIG
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Daphnia gaelata mendotae</i>	DAGA
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Daphnia pulex</i> gr.	DAPU
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Daphnia retrocurva</i>	DARE
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Daphnia</i> sp.	DASP
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Diaphanosoma</i> sp.	DISP
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Ehippia	EPHI
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	<i>Leptodora kindtii</i>	LEKI
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Copepoda	<i>Acanthocyclops americanus</i>	ACAM
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Copepoda	<i>Leptodiptomus sicilis</i>	LESI
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus crassicaudatus</i>	CHCR
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus decorus</i> grp. spp.	CHDE
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Cladotanytarsus</i> sp.	CLAD
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Cryptochironomus</i> sp.	CRPY
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Glyptotendipes</i> sp.	GLYP
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Parachironomus</i> sp.	PASP
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	Partial Chironomidae	PACH
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Polypedilum halterale</i> grp.	POHA
Arthropoda	Insecta	Chironomidae	<i>Procladius</i> sp.	PRSP
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	<i>Hyalella</i> sp	HYSP
Arthropoda	Ostracoda	Ostracoda	Ostracoda	OSTR
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	<i>Corbicula</i> sp.	CORB
Nematoda			Nematoda/Nemata	NEMA

Taxa rank abundance, total abundance, rank frequency, and frequency are in Table 22.

Table 22 Taxa rank abundance, total abundance, rank frequency, and frequency in mesocosms study 2023.

Taxa Code	Rank Abundance	Total	Rank Frequency	Frequency
OLIG	1	3489	1	53
CLAD	2	1319	3	42
CHCR	3	1035	2	52
CHDE	4	395	4	39
NEMA	5	214	5	28
LEKI	6	176	5	28
PACH	7	92	6	33
PRSP	8	80	7	27
GLYP	9	23	9	9

Chapter 4 Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages

EISP	10	20	8	11
EPHI	11	14	10	7
CRPY	12	13	9	9
CORB	13	11	9	9
POHA	14	6	11	5
OSTR	15	3	12	3
PASP	16	3	13	2
HYSP	17	1	14	1

Rank abundances of phytoplankton encountered in our mesocosm study, 2023 are in Figure 47. This figure shows the dominance of a few taxa, particularly oligochaetes (OLIG), *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD), and *Chironomus crassicaudatus* (CHCR), and decreasing abundances of other taxa.

Figure 47 Rank abundances of phytoplankton encountered in our mesocosm study, 2023.

Of the non-zooplankters, nine taxa were Chironomidae (midges), three were worms (segmented and unsegmented), and three were other taxa, bivalves, ostracods, and amphipods.

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Figure 48 Percent abundances of benthic invertebrate groups, worms, midges, and other collected and identified in our mesocosm study 2023. See Table 21 for a complete list of all invertebrate taxa.

A list of all invertebrate taxa and their abundances for each sample event is in Appendix 8.

HBI TOLERANCE VALUES

The following table, Table 23 **Error! Reference source not found.** summarizes HBI/Tolerance values for our mesocosm benthic invertebrate sample results. The HBI/Tolerance Value for all benthic samples combined, excluding zooplankton, was 8.93. This value should actually be somewhat higher because of the arbitrary assignment of HBI = 5 to Nematoda/Nemata¹⁰.

Table 23 Invertebrate taxa counts and HBI/Tolerance Values.

Taxon	Count	HBI/Tolerance Values
OLIG	3489	9.5
CLAD	1319	7
CHCR	1035	10
CHDE	395	10
NEMA	214	5
PACH	92	10
PRSP	80	7
GLYP	23	7
EISP	20	9.5
CRPY	13	8
CORB	11	6.3
POHA	6	7.2

HBI/Tolerance values ranked water quality in the mesocosm 2023 study as ‘very poor’ and its degree of organic pollution ‘severe’ (Table 24).

Table 24. HBI Water Quality Ranks

HBI	Water Quality	Degree of Organic Pollution
0.00-3.50	Excellent	No apparent
3.5-4.50	Very Good	Possible slight
4.51-5.50	Good	Some
5.51-6.50	Pair	Fairly significant
6.51-7.50	Fairly Poor	Significant
7.5-8.50	Poor	Very significant
8.5-10.0	Very Poor	Severe

SEASONAL CHANGES IN BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE ASSEMBLAGE

We removed zooplankton taxa other than *Leptodora kindtii* for multivariate assemblage analyses. Zooplankton taxa assemblages were analyzed in our previous chapter. We kept *L. kindtii* in the benthic invertebrate assemblage analyses because we found very few during our zooplankton sample events and they were underrepresented in those analyses. These highly effective

¹⁰ HBI/Tolerance Values for Nematoda/Nemata were assigned 5 based on extremely limited studies, large number of taxa within that group that vary in organic pollution tolerances, and subsequently an arbitrarily assigned mean value (River Continuum Concepts personal communication)

predacious cladocerans are fairly strong swimmers and likely spend time in the benthos diurnally, subsequently, their relatively large abundance in the benthos was considered important.

SAMPLE EVENT

We found strong evidence that assemblages differed by sample event (MRPP $T = -8.83$, $A = 0.11$, $p < 0.01$). There was strong evidence that the June assemblage was different from the August and September assemblages, but no evidence that August and September assemblages were different from each other (Table 25).

Table 25 MRPP results for benthic invertebrate assemblage comparisons by sample events.

Sample Event	T	A	p
June16 vs, August 31	-10.56	0.13	0.00
June 16 vs. September 27	-8.91	0.13	0.00
August 31 vs September 27	-0.32	0.00	0.26

JUNE 16 SAMPLE EVENT

MRPP results showed no difference in assemblages inside vs outside of mesocosms ($T = 0.77$, $A = -0.02$, $p = 0.77$). However, *Eiseniella* sp. (oligochaete worms) and nematodes were more likely to occur outside of mesocosms using Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) ($p = 0.04$, 0.06 respectively). We did not find any evidence that other taxa were likely to occur either inside or outside mesocosms at the time of the June 16 sample event.

Our best NMS model was a superior three-dimensional model with final stress = 3.47, final instability < 0.001, at 73 iterations using a Sorensen’s distant measure. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.68$, Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.17$, and Axis 3 $R^2 = 0.12$.

Figure 49 NMS axis 1 and 2 of benthic invertebrate taxa inside and outside of mesocosms on June 16 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

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Figure 50 NMS axis 1 and 3 of benthic invertebrate taxa inside and outside of mesocosms on June 16 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Table 26 Taxa parametric and non-parametric relations to NMS Axes 1, 2, and 3 on June 16 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Taxa Code	Axis 1			Axis 2			Axis 3		
	r	R ²	τ	r	R ²	τ	r	R ²	τ
CHCR	-0.61	0.38	-0.60	-0.32	0.10	-0.21	-0.40	0.16	-0.04
CHDE	-0.32	0.11	-0.34	-0.20	0.04	-0.37	0.77	0.60	0.45
CLAD	-0.71	0.50	-0.48	-0.52	0.27	-0.45	0.11	0.01	0.25
CORB	-0.15	0.02	-0.24	-0.22	0.05	-0.21	0.06	0.00	0.14
EISP	-0.04	0.00	-0.13	0.43	0.19	0.31	0.30	0.09	0.19
GLYP	0.41	0.17	0.38	-0.08	0.01	-0.14	-0.08	0.01	-0.10
HYSP	-0.36	0.13	-0.26	-0.10	0.01	-0.17	-0.46	0.22	-0.35
LEKI	0.20	0.04	-0.04	-0.24	0.06	-0.21	-0.25	0.06	-0.16
NEMA	-0.07	0.01	-0.14	0.17	0.03	0.09	0.62	0.39	0.00
OLIG	-0.89	0.79	-0.78	0.25	0.06	0.19	-0.03	0.00	0.08
OSTR	0.05	0.00	0.12	0.11	0.01	0.07	0.77	0.59	0.35
PACH	-0.51	0.26	-0.32	-0.17	0.03	-0.23	-0.03	0.00	0.01
POHA	-0.04	0.00	-0.12	-0.33	0.11	-0.26	0.13	0.02	0.21
PRSP	-0.01	0.00	-0.02	-0.60	0.35	-0.39	0.67	0.45	0.54

AUGUST 31 SAMPLE EVENT

We found strong evidence that the benthic invertebrate assemblage differed inside and outside of mesocosms on the August 31 sample event (MRPP $T = -6.07$, $A = 0.18$, $p < 0.01$).

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We developed an excellent NMS two-dimensional model of benthic invertebrate assemblage on the August 31 sample event using a Relative Sorenson distance measure. Final Stress = 6.74, final instability < 0.001, at 63 iterations indicating there is little chance of misinterpreting the model. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.87$, Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.10$ explaining a cumulative 97% of the variability in the assemblage.

Figure 51 NMS axis 1 and 2 of benthic invertebrate taxa inside and outside of mesocosms on August 31 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Table 27 Taxa parametric and non-parametric relations to NMS Axis1 and Axis 2 on August 31 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Taxon	Axis 1			Axis 2		
	r	R ²	τ	r	R ²	τ
CHCR	0.22	0.05	0.08	0.11	0.01	0.23
CHDE	0.10	0.01	0.02	0.20	0.04	0.05
CLAD	0.69	0.47	0.62	0.18	0.03	0.02
CORB	0.08	0.01	0.13	-0.45	0.20	-0.38
CRPY	0.27	0.07	0.18	0.26	0.07	0.32
EISP	-0.22	0.05	-0.06	0.10	0.01	0.06
EPHI	-0.34	0.11	-0.37	0.36	0.13	0.06
GLYP	0.34	0.11	0.26	0.06	0.00	0.10
LEKI	0.06	0.00	0.00	-0.67	0.45	-0.33
NEMA	-0.29	0.09	-0.25	0.57	0.33	0.49
OLIG	-0.45	0.20	-0.32	0.17	0.03	0.04

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OSTR	0.16	0.03	0.17	-0.24	0.06	-0.07
PASP	0.21	0.05	0.18	-0.10	0.01	-0.06
PACH	0.18	0.03	0.14	-0.10	0.01	-0.01
POHA	0.18	0.03	-0.08	0.13	0.02	-0.01
PRSP	0.27	0.07	-0.05	0.37	0.14	0.37

A closer examination of the relations among taxa using NMS revealed that all three worm taxa, were negatively related to four midge taxa particularly the most abundant midge *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD) on the August 31 sample event based on Axis 1 ($R^2 = 0.87$) (Table 27 and Figure 52). Reasons for these negative relationships are speculative at this time such as predation by midges on worms, interspecific competition, etc. and beyond the scope of this project.

Figure 52 NMS Axis 1 showing all three worm taxa (EISP, NEMA, AND OLIG) and several midge taxa (CLAD, PASP, GLYP, AND CRPY) were negatively correlated with each other at the August 31 sample event. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.87$. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Several taxa were indicators on conditions inside and outside of mesocosms using ISA. *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD) ($p < 0.01$), *Corbicula* sp. (CORB) ($p = 0.04$), and *Glyptotendipes* sp. (GLYP) ($p = 0.08$) were more likely to occur inside mesocosms, whereas nematode worms (NEMA) ($p = 0.02$) were more likely to occur outside of mesocosms.

SEPTEMBER 27 SAMPLE EVENT

We found no evidence that benthic invertebrate assemblages differed inside and outside of mesocosms on September 27 sample event (MRPP $T = -1.14$, $A = 0.04$, $p = 0.12$). However, we were able to develop a superior NMS 2-dimensional model with final stress = 4.06, instability < 0.001 , at 68 iterations. Axis1 $R^2 = 0.80$, Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.01$.

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Figure 53 NMS axis 1 and 2 of benthic invertebrate taxa inside and outside of mesocosms on September 27 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

A closer examination of the relations among taxa using NMS revealed that all three worm taxa, EISP, OLIG, and NEMA were negatively related to four midge taxa particularly the most abundant midge *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD) and several others on the September 27 sample event based on Axis 1 ($R^2 = 0.80$) (Table 27 and Figure 52). Reasons for these negative relationships are speculative at this time such as predation by midges on worms, interspecific competition, etc. and beyond the scope of this project.

Figure 54 NMS Axis 1 showing that all three worm taxa (EISP, NEMA, AND OLIG) and several midge taxa (CLAD, PACH, AND CRPY) were negatively correlated with each other at the September 27 sample event. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.80$. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Table 28 Taxa parametric and non-parametric relations to NMS Axis1 and Axis 2 on the September 27 sample event. Taxa names are in Table 21.

Taxon	Axis 1			Axis 2		
	r	R ²	τ	r	R ²	τ

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CHCR	0.23	0.053	0.222	0.452	0.204	0.356
CHDE	0.004	0	-0.008	0.45	0.203	0.431
CLAD	0.705	0.497	0.537	-0.286	0.082	-0.313
CORB	0.12	0.014	0.086	-0.024	0.001	0.043
CRPY	0.33	0.109	0.239	-0.104	0.011	-0.179
EISP	-0.206	0.042	-0.129	-0.105	0.011	-0.086
EPHI	-0.328	0.107	-0.262	-0.064	0.004	0.077
GLYP	0.056	0.003	0.063	-0.25	0.062	-0.219
LEKI	-0.289	0.084	-0.188	-0.278	0.077	-0.426
NEMA	-0.291	0.085	-0.205	0.404	0.163	0.205
OLIG	-0.653	0.426	-0.397	-0.076	0.006	0.015
PACH	0.453	0.205	0.369	-0.023	0.001	0.097
PRSP	0.067	0.005	0.108	0.609	0.371	0.416

The only taxon more likely to occur inside mesocosms on Sept 27 sample event was *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD) based on ISA ($p = 0.01$).

ABUNDANCE, RICHNESS, EVENNESS, AND DIVERSITY

Mesocosms tended to improve evenness, diversity, and effective number of taxa overall and particularly in the August 31 sample event (Figure 55). Mean abundance¹¹ was higher outside mesocosms on June 16 and September 27 sample events and higher inside mesocosms on August 31 sample event. Mean taxa richness was greater inside mesocosms for all three sample events. Mean evenness was greater on June 16 and September 27 sample events and higher inside mesocosms on August 31 sample event. Mean Shannon Diversity was greater inside mesocosms for all three sample events and mean Simpson Diversity was lower June 16, higher August 31, and about the same Sept 27 inside mesocosms than outside mesocosms. Mean effective number of taxa (ENT) was greater inside mesocosms for all three sample events. Overall, ENT was roughly between 2 and 4 taxa, which signifies extreme impairment.

¹¹ To convert abundance results to density m^2 simply divide by 0.023.

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Figure 55 Abundance, richness, diversity, and effective number of taxa inside vs outside mesocosms for all three sample events. Mean and 95% CIs. There was good evidence ($p < 0.08$) that E, H, and D were greater inside mesocosms than outside on August 31 sample event.

Individual taxa abundances varied inside and outside of mesocosms and between sample events (Figure 56). The June 16 sample event was when mesocosms were just getting settled and is less informative than the August 31 and September 27 events, other than showing how similar benthic invertebrate densities were inside mesocosms with the lake. *Cladotanytarsus* sp., (CLAD), *Corbicula* sp. (CORB), *Glyptotendipes* sp. (GLYP), *Leptodora kindtii* (LEKI), and partial unidentified Chironomidae (PACH) tended to be more abundant inside mesocosms while nematode (NEMA), *Eiseniella* sp. (EISP) lumbricid worms, and oligochaete worms (OLIG) tended to be more abundant outside of mesocosms (Figure 56, and assemblage ISA results [June 16](#)).

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Figure 56 Abundances of individual invertebrate taxa found in mesocosm study 2023 inside and outside of mesocosms for all three sample events.

Leptodora kindtii (LEKI), and partial unidentified Chironomidae (PACH) tended to be more abundant inside mesocosms while nematode (NEMA) and oligochaete worms (OLIG) tended to be more abundant outside of mesocosms.

DISCUSSION

Our mesocosm 2023 benthic invertebrate collection and results, combined with our other research continues to be some of the most comprehensive analysis of benthic invertebrates conducted on Utah Lake, particularly from profundal habitats. Subsequently, results presented here are invaluable for improving our understanding Utah Lake's ecosystem function. Researchers at Utah State University routinely collect macroinvertebrates from littoral zones in Utah Lake (Landom et al., 2023) and their findings will be useful for predicting what taxa are likely to colonize profundal shoreline habitats if aquatic plants and mollusks are restored.

The benthic invertebrate assemblage in our study site was taxa depauperate consisting of mostly pollution and poor habitat tolerant midges (Chironomidae) and worms (Oligochaeta, Nematoda).

Consequently, we did not anticipate finding meaningful mesocosm effects. A shallow lake littoral zone, if healthy, should have dozens of macroinvertebrate taxa. More taxa with differing niches would have given a better effect signal. However, we were able to document positive effects of mesocosms on the assemblage despite encountering only this handful of taxa. Several taxa were more likely to occur (indicators) in improved conditions inside mesocosms, for example the midge, *Cladotanytarsus* sp. The three worm taxa occurred more frequently outside the mesocosms in the lake. Reasons for these effects requires further investigation and are likely to be complex.

Two important chironomid taxa collected in our study included *Cladotanytarsus* sp. (CLAD) and *Glyptotendipes* sp. (GLYP).

There are 28 known (described) species of the genus *Cladotanytarsus* known from the northern hemisphere, but the larvae of most species remain undescribed. The larvae are found in many kinds of aquatic habitats: streams, rivers, lakes, ponds, brackish estuaries, and hot springs. They build silty sessile cases of silk and fine detritus. Hilsenhoff gave the genus a tolerance value of 7.0, indicating that he found them tolerant of adverse organically enriched habitats, but that they were more facultative. In Western Rivers, they can be found in a wide range of habitats, often among deposits of sand mixed silt, at locations that do not support large populations of *Chironomus* or *Glyptotendipes*. The specimens found in Utah Lake have smaller Lauterborne organs than most specimens we have collected in western rivers. Most of the 11 *Cladotanytarsus* species observed by Epler (2001) from the southeastern USA have not been formally named and have temporary letter designations.

Glyptotendipes larvae live among the silt and other fine organic sediments of still or slow-moving eutrophic waters. Larvae often incorrectly field identified as “*Chironomus* sp.” because of their size and red color. Hilsenhoff (1987) gave this genus an HBI tolerance value of 10.0, the maximum (the same as *Chironomus*), because of their occurrence in very eutrophic environments. However, many species are most often associated with benthic algae in these environments, although some may burrow between the bark and cambium of submerged wood. There are about 25 species known as adults, but the larval taxonomy remains “confused since its establishment” (Anderson et al. 2013).

Mesocosm effects were mostly observed on the mid-summer August 31 sample event. Mid-summer is when Utah Lake’s ecosystem is most vulnerable to stress due to dominance by cyanobacteria, large abundance of zooplanktivorous juvenile invasive fishes, and other environmental stressors (Richards et al. 2023, Richards 2022). The fact that we found positive effects demonstrates that reduction of wave induced turbulence will go a long way in helping restore Utah Lake’s ecosystem function.

The widely used HBI value of 8.93 from this mesocosms study was similar to but slightly lower than the HBI value Richards (2022) calculated from our 2022 mesocosm study of 9.12. This slight improvement could be due to the 2023 mesocosms being deployed in better substrate, e.g., less muddy conditions and/or the now unusually high-water level in 2023 compared to an extreme low water year in 2022. However, our 2023 mesocosm HBI = 8.93 was substantially less than an atrocious HBI = 9.85 derived from 93 samples collected by Richards and Miller (2017) collected from various locations around Utah Lake (Richards 2022). The 93 samples analyzed by Richards (2022) included samples collected from deeper sections of the lake that have unconsolidated, fine, thick, ‘ooze’ substrates inhospitable to even some of the more tolerant taxa that likely caused the

high HBI value reported by Richards (2022). This suggests that near shore habitats in Utah Lake are at least in somewhat better condition than mid-lake habitats.

Although extremely useful, HBI is but one of many metrics that should be used in an assessment of restoration effects in Utah Lake. Most county, state, federal and tribal water quality agencies understand the limitations of using only a single metric to measure biological/ecological integrity and incorporate HBI into a suite of metrics for assessing water quality (e.g., Multimetric Index of Biological Integrity). Richards and Miller (2019) are developing a Multimetric Index of Ecological Integrity for Utah Lake that includes HBI/Tolerance Index as one of many informative metrics.

MIDGES DOMINATE THE BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE ASSEMBLAGE

As we have shown, the dominant benthic invertebrates in the lake presently consist of just a handful of taxa. As a result, much of the lake exists as profundal and can be considered chronically impaired, early successional (Richards 2022). However, some areas of the lake including areas in Provo Bay and the limited macrophyte habitats outside of the bay have a greater diversity of benthic invertebrates including corixids (bugs) and coleoptera (beetles) as well as odonates (dragonflies) and isopods and amphipods, etc. (Landom and Walsworth 2021). Out of approximately twenty macroinvertebrate taxa found by Richards et al. (2016) that included 93 benthic samples, only three taxa dominated the invertebrate biomass, *Chironomus* sp. (midge), *Tanytus* sp. (midge larvae), and oligochaete worms. These three pollution tolerant indicators comprised 99% of the biomass (Richards and Miller 2019) and continue to do so, although it appears that midge larvae densities in the lake fluctuate greatly from year to year and may be decreasing (Richards and Miller 2019, and unpublished data).

The extreme low effective number of benthic invertebrate taxa is of great concern because it reflects the degraded condition of Utah Lake's benthic environment. Dominance by only three pollution tolerant taxa is a red flag in all biological assessments of water quality throughout the world. However, these remaining three dominant taxa are now the default keystone ecosystem engineers that struggle to maintain the lake's present ecological state and are a crucial component of the lake's food web and help maintain a functioning ecosystem (Richards and Miller 2019). Their presence and role in Utah Lake's ecosystem should not be underestimated nor undervalued. Midge larvae are responsible for much of the lake's benthic/sediment function and interaction with the water column given their sheer volume, biomass, secondary production, and ecology (Richards and Miller 2019c, Holker et al. 2015); and as reported by Randal et al. (2017) and Hogsett et al. (2019), the sediment water interface appears to be a major controlling factor of phosphorus recycling and subsequent algal blooms. Although midge larvae densities can exceed $10,000 \text{ m}^{-2}$ in the lake, primary production estimates suggest that their numbers should be substantially greater (Richards 2022). For example, in Lake Myvatn (Midge Lake), Iceland, midge larval density often exceeds $500,000 \text{ m}^{-2}$. The reason for the relatively low density of midge larvae in Utah Lake can be attributed to heavy predation from fishes and to a lesser extent unsuitable conditions. Midge larvae are the most common prey item of all fish species in the lake, including those fishes that typically should focus their diets on other smaller fishes (Richard 2022). This conundrum of low biomass and preferred food item of large numbers of fish suggest that midge larvae secondary production is very high (i.e., the production to biomass ratio could be near 100 or more) and that Utah Lake's foodweb is severely out of balance. Science based restoration that incorporates our research findings is needed.

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Adult midges also transfer energy and nutrients out of Utah Lake into surrounding wetlands after larval pupation and adults become airborne. Midge swarms along the shoreline of Utah Lake are often intense with tens of thousands of adults participating in their mating rituals. The following two videos show such swarms along the lake's shores:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vVSgmNQS9YI>

and

<https://youtu.be/aE4nThbiY6s>

Although midge densities are extremely high in Utah Lake, they are often much higher in Farmington Bay of Great Salt Lake (Figure 57) and are nothing compared to densities and swarms that can occur in Lake Myvatn, Iceland¹².

Figure 57. Adult midge swarm at Farmington Bay, Great Salt Lake wetland ponds. Swarms appear to be dark funnel clouds along the wetland horizon and are not controlled burning.

The following video shows a typical midge swarm in Lake Myvatn:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E0BhQm27RA4>.

It has become clear that several dominant benthic taxa, primarily chironomids (midges), can alter benthic ecosystem function and play a key role in the timing and intensity of cyanoHABs in lake ecosystems. However, this relationship has received very little attention, particularly in Utah Lake. For refresher, the section on the relation between midge larvae and cyanoHABs that Richards and Miller reported in their 2016 Progress Report has been added to this report. In the following section, we discuss our latest literature findings on just how important midge larvae can be to benthic ecosystem functions, including cyanoHABs in Utah Lake.

¹² Lake Myvatn literally translates to Midge Lake.

SUBSTRATE STABILIZATION AND STRUCTURE, NET ECOSYSTEM PRODUCTION, AND CYANOHABS

Larval midge tubes are constructed from silk similar to the kind of silk produced by spiders, which has very strong tensile strength and ductility. Midge larvae also produce connecting networks of silk that stabilizes the substrate and provides three-dimensional structure to the sediment (Ólafsson and Paterson 2004, Høolker et al. 2015). Midge larvae can reach high densities in Utah Lake, which certainly helps stabilize the substrate and increases structure (Figure 58).

Figure 58. Hundreds of midge larval tubes in Provo Bay, Utah Lake. These larvae help stabilize the easily disturbed substrate, provide three-dimensional structure, and the larvae actively oxygenate the sediments including Fe near the sediment water boundary layer. Tubes are likely either *Chironomus* sp. or *Tanyptus* sp. or both. This photo was taken during a low water year when water levels were shallow enough that large insectivorous fish were excluded, and predation was reduced allowing midge populations to maintain high densities and to continue to provide valuable ecosystem services other than just as fish food.

Midge larval tubes increase sediment shear strength subsequently reducing resuspension and turbidity. Ólafsson and Paterson (2004) documented that *Tanytarsus gracilentus* (midge) larvae in Lake Myvatn, Iceland modified the surface sediment by tube building and showed that shear strength of the sediment surface, and hence resistance to erosion, increased significantly with increased densities of *T. gracilentus* larvae (Phillips et al. 2019).

Sediment stabilization is critical for Utah Lake because among other things, sediments and nutrients are easily suspended and affect turbidity and nutrient availability, which often favors cyanoHABs. Midge larval tubes provide three-dimensional structure that also increases habitat for small microorganisms and algae. By providing stable substrate for algae, larval midge tubes indirectly increase gross primary production (GPP) in the sediment, although by consuming algae, midges may inhibit GPP. Midge larvae can also stimulate microbial respiration (RESP) by oxygenating the sediment. (Phillips et al. 2019, Holker et al. 2015). Therefore, the overall effect of midge larvae on net ecosystem production (NEP) depends on the balance between their effects on GPP and RESP, which is also affected by light conditions (Phillips et al. 2019) (Figure 59).

Figure 59, Midge larvae alter benthic ecosystem function. This figure and caption were taken from Philipps et al. 2019. “Midges can alter benthic ecosystem function. Larval midges build silk tubes that provide a substrate for algal growth and increase gross primary production (GPP) in the sediment. However, midges may inhibit GPP through consumption of algae. Furthermore, midges can stimulate microbial respiration (RESP) by oxygenating the sediment. Gross primary production and RESP have opposite effects on net ecosystem production (NEP), so the effect of midges on NEP depends on the balance between their effects on GPP and RESP. We hypothesized that light mediates this balance, because the positive effects of midges on GPP would decline as photosynthesis became more limited by light. Episodic cyanobacterial blooms have a negative effect on benthic light levels, which could result in spatiotemporal variation in the net effects of midges on benthic production.”

MIDGE LARVAE AND CYANOHABS

Richards and Miller (2017) briefly reported how midge larvae could affect cyanoHABS in Utah Lake in their Utah Lake 2016 Progress Report, including how circumstantially, cyanoHABS appeared to cycle out of sync with larval abundance. Philips et al. (2019) further elaborated on these effects more recently (Figure 59). Einarsson and Örnólfssdóttir (2004) also reported that intense cyanoHABS blooms (*Aphanizomenon flos-aquae*) always occurred in years of low chironomid populations but sometimes developed in other years in Lake Myvatn and similar to our current findings; cyclic patterns of dominant midges varied several orders of magnitude. Einarsson and Örnólfssdóttir (2004) also suggested that cyclic patterns of midges were not likely due to climate. *Tanytarsus gracilentus* in Lake Myvatn showed cyclic population fluctuation with three peaks occurring during a 20-year period. Body size of *T. gracilentus* fluctuated with population size but in an opposite fashion and with a time lag in Lake Myvatn again, similar to findings in Utah Lake (Richards and

Miller 2019). *T. gracilentus* body size and abundance and predator abundance in Lake Myvatn suggested that the population fluctuations were driven by interaction with resources and not by predator-prey interactions (Einarsson et al. 2002). However, there are only two major predacious fish in Lake Myvatn, three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) and Arctic charr (*Salvelinus alpinus*) (Einarsson et al. 2004), whereas there are several invasive fish species in Utah Lake that are avid midge larvae hunters; common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), white bass (*Morone chrysops*), channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*), and black bullhead (*Ameiurus melas*), to name a few. Common carp biomass is measured in the tens to hundreds of tons in Utah Lake and this species alone can regulate or decimate midge populations within the lake.

We agree with the midge researchers on Lake Myvatn that the underlying mechanisms for midge cycles are not fully understood and that further investigation is required and that by sheer abundance, midges may be one of the major regulating factors in the long-term dynamics of Lake Myvatn and Utah Lake ecosystems. We also agree with our Icelandic colleagues that “for effective conservation, the only sound strategy seems to be to avoid interfering with the basic components of the ecosystem” (Phillips et al. 2019). Although interfering in ecosystem components in Utah Lake has been the mainstay of citizens and managers over the last century, further interference other than restoration based on sound science should be avoided.

The effects of midge larval on ecosystem respiration (RESP) and GPP vary seasonally with greater effects in summer during increased temperatures. Baranov et al. (2016) showed that RESP in sediments with and without chironomids did not differ at 5°C, but at 30°C sediment respiration in microcosms with 2000 chironomid larvae per m² was 4.9 times higher than in uninhabited sediments. This is a somewhat lower density of larvae than what we typically find in Utah Lake and compared to their results suggest that midge larval effects on RESP may be higher in Utah Lake.

Warm summer water temperatures result in faster midge larval development, shorter life cycles, additional generations per year and higher reproduction rates—all resulting in higher larval densities and intensified ecosystem effects (Hamburger et al. 1995; Eggermont and Heiri 2012). With large densities, especially in eutrophic water bodies with warm water, midge larvae burrowing, and ventilation activities can dramatically impact freshwater biogeochemistry (Morad et al. 2010). For example, in shallow Lake Muggelsee in Germany (mean depth 5 m, relatively similar to Utah Lake mean depth) a volume equivalent to the total water column of the lake is pumped by chironomids through their burrows, once a week (Morad et al. 2010). This rate is likely similar to Utah Lake. That is, during certain times of year when midge larvae are at relatively high densities and are active, they can pump the entire water column of Utah Lake through the sediments, perhaps weekly or less. Baranov et al. (2016) concluded that high densities of chironomids in shallow lakes can significantly intensify sediment respiration, especially in warm and well-oxygenated systems. This effect is most pronounced in shallow, non-stratified lakes such as Utah Lake and is consistent with sediment chemistry findings by Hogsett et al. (2019).

Very few studies have been conducted on the benthic invertebrate assemblages in Utah Lake (Barnes and Toole 1981, Spencer and Denton 2003, Shiozawa and Barnes 1977) and none were conducted at the level and intensity that is presently being accomplished by members of this group. No study has ever examined the role of benthic invertebrates on HABs in Utah Lake, although this is the first to document reduction in cyanobacteria by filter feeding bivalves (see Chapter 1). Our research is also an important element of sediment chemistry, nutrients, and food web models that are presently being conducted by us and others on Utah Lake. Results of our

research are leading to valuable insights on the role of benthic macroinvertebrates in the ecology and ecosystem functioning.

BENTHIC MACROINVERTEBRATES AND HABS

The relationship between benthic macroinvertebrates, particularly worms and midges, and harmful algal blooms has received very little attention. In this section, we discuss the latest science on just how important these interactions are to Utah Lake HABS.

For several decades it has been recognized that anoxia is a pre-condition for cyanobacteria blooms in eutrophic waters (Trimbee and Prepas 1988) and that warm temperatures and stable water columns promote anoxia (Paerl, 1988; Zhang & Prepas, 1996). However, the role of Fe in cyanobacteria blooms has been severely underappreciated and the role of midge (Chironomidae) larvae in regulating Fe availability has been even less so.

ANOXIA AND FE

Molot et al. (2014) proposed that the role of anoxia and ferrous iron was critical for cyanobacteria bloom formation. Their model can be summarized as follows:

“The model has several critical concepts: (i) P regulates biomass and productivity in fresh waters until excessive loading renders a system N-limited or light-limited, but it is the availability of ferrous ions (Fe^{2+}) that regulates the ability of cyanobacteria to compete with its eukaryotic competitors; (ii) Fe^{2+} diffusing from anoxic sediments is a major Fe source for cyanobacteria, which acquire it by migrating downwards into Fe^{2+} -rich anoxic waters from oxygenated waters; and (iii) subsequent cyanobacterial siderophore production provides a supply of Fe^{3+} for reduction at cyanobacteria cell membranes that leads to very low Fe^{3+} concentrations in the mixing zone.

When light and temperature are physiologically suitable for cyanobacteria growth, bloom onset is regulated by the onset of internal Fe^{2+} loading which in turn is controlled by anoxia, reducible Fe content of surface sediments and sulphate reduction rate.”

MIDGE LARVAE

Midge larvae can actively oxygenate the sediments near the sediment/water boundary, including converting Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} (Holker et al. 2015) (Figure 60). Midge larvae are extremely abundant in Utah Lake sediments and can thus have a tremendous effect on Fe conversion. However, midge larvae pupate and then leave the lake as adults and are therefore not always present actively aerating the sediment. Subsequently, when larvae pupate and leave sediments as adults, larval tubes collapse and Fe^{3+} reduces to Fe^{2+} (Figure 60).

Figure 60. From: Holker et al. 2015. Tube-dwelling invertebrates: tiny ecosystem engineers have large effects in lake ecosystems.

BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE ASSEMBLAGES IN UTAH LAKE

Benthic invertebrate assemblages differ in taxonomic composition spatially and temporally in Utah Lake. For example, Richards and Miller (2017) conducted one of the most intensive benthic invertebrate surveys on Utah Lake to date. They estimated that there was between 1.89 and 7.66 g m⁻² wet weight in the lake and at any one time during the 2016 sampling season there were between 790 and 3210 tons (U.S. short tons) of wet weight benthic invertebrate standing crop biomass in the lake. During peak growth in late summer there could easily have been 6000 tons (90th centile). Richards and Miller (2017) reported that there was a major difference between percentage biomass of benthic invertebrates in Provo Bay and the rest of Utah Lake. Provo Bay was dominated by both *Chironomus* sp. and *Tanytus* sp. with *Tanytus* sp. being the most dominant, about 55% (Figure 61), whereas the rest of the lake was dominated by *Chironomus* sp. with almost 80% of the total biomass (Figure 62).

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Figure 61. Percent benthic macroinvertebrate biomass in Provo Bay (center site).

Figure 62. Percent benthic macroinvertebrate biomass in Utah Lake not including Provo Bay (center). From Richards and Miller (2017).

In addition, Richards and Miller (2017) demonstrated difference in assemblage biomasses at their twelve sample sites (Figure 63).

Figure 63. Benthic invertebrate biomass (mg/m²) in Utah Lake at twelve sampling sites.

USU researchers routinely collect invertebrate samples on Utah Lake, however they focus on limited remaining littoral zone macrophyte habitats which are not directly comparable to our habitat sampling in shoreline profundal. Comparisons need to be made.

CHIRONOMID SECONDARY PRODUCTION AND PRODUCTION-BIOMASS RATIOS.

We did not measure secondary production or production/biomass ratios in this study, even though these measures are extremely important for modeling Utah Lakes current ecosystem function and any effects of restoration. Secondary production is the quantitative base of energy flow and trophic interactions between autotrophs and heterotrophs and is a key parameter of ecosystem functioning. The amount of secondary production and its distribution between populations are measures of trophic position and of linkage in aquatic food webs (Benke 2011, Brey 2012) and can be used as a measure of ecosystem and population health (Buffagni and Comin 2000; Dolbeth et al. 2005). In shallow water ecosystems including the area we conducted mesocosm experiments, benthic secondary production at the sediment-water interface is extremely important as it has the potential to be the focus of intense energy and matter turnover. It is relevant for both nutrient recycling and channeling of matter to higher trophic levels in Utah Lake's fisheries. Accurate estimates of benthic secondary production are crucial if we are to prudently manage Utah Lake based on scientific evidence.

Temperature is the most important environmental factor governing macroinvertebrate secondary production, somatic growth rates (production), development rates, feeding rates, and production to biomass ratios (P/B) (Vijverberg 1980, Peters 1984, Plante and Downing 1989, Reynolds and Benke 2005, Stites and Benke 1989, others). Benthic invertebrate growth rates and P/B ratios have been estimated for a wetland in Farmington Bay, downstream of Utah Lake (Richards 2023) but not

for Utah Lake. Utah Lake undergoes large seasonal shifts in temperature due to its shallow nature and latitude and large fluctuation along its shoreline.

The results of our mesocosm study 2023 and past research showed that diverse substrate habitat is lacking and severely restricts invertebrate assemblage efficiency and functioning. Measuring changes in benthic invertebrate production and P/B ratios as restoration improves benthic habitat is critical.

RESTORATION EFFECTS ON INVERTEBRATE ASSEMBLAGE

As discussed, our research has shown that only a few invertebrate taxa reside in the degraded near shore habitat of Utah Lake and their contribution to its ecosystem function. We predict that restoration aimed at improving littoral zone habitat along the lake's shoreline by increasing macrophytes (aquatic plants), reintroducing bivalves, reducing invasive benthivorous fishes, and redirecting primary production towards the benthos will substantially improve invertebrate assemblage diversity, increase secondary production, and greatly improve ecosystem function.

By increasing substrate habitat from its present homogenous sand/silt condition to a diverse 3-dimensional canopy of macrophytes and bivalves (native *Anodonta* sp.) periphytic and benthic algae will proliferate. Many more taxa will colonize these habitats including, additional midge taxa (e.g., additional *Polypedilum* sp.), corixids, trichopterans, coleopterans, and amphipods, etc. This diversity will be able to utilize primary production more efficiently thus increasing secondary production and will diversify invertebrate food resources for upper trophic levels, e.g., fishes. Presently non piscivorous fishes have mostly only midge larvae and worms as food resources. Consequently, these habitats are now dominated by mostly invasive benthivorous species, mostly carp and catfish. A diverse invertebrate assemblage will also provide consistent food resources for upper trophic levels via non synchronized seasonal abundances unlike current midge larvae populations.

STATE, STRUCTURE, AND FUNCTION OF UTAH LAKE'S ECOSYSTEM

Understanding the trophic state, structure, and function of Utah Lake's ecosystem is of paramount importance if we are to manage and restore it based on a scientific ecological perspective. Several metrics that are used to measure ecosystem health, integrity, maturity, robustness, resistance, resilience, state, structure, and function include: Trophic transfer efficiency (TTE), ecoexergy, ascendancy, overhead, and redundancy, to name a few (Christensen et al 2005, Nielson et al. 2020, Richards 2022b, Jørgensen 2005, 2007). These measures are used by ecosystem ecologists as more informative quantitative metrics than the latent buzz words used primarily by managers, health and integrity. These will be discussed briefly in relation to our mesocosm 2023 findings.

TROPHIC TRANSFER EFFICIENCY

Results from our mesocosm 2023 study indirectly demonstrate improvement of trophic transfer efficiency (TTE), how efficiently energy is transferred up to higher trophic levels (i.e., the foodweb). TTE is a direct measure of an ecosystem's health and is widely used in aquatic foodweb models. Richards (2022b) foodweb-ecosystem function model showed that Utah Lake has major trophic level transfer problems. Our results will assist in continued development of ecosystem function models that use these metrics and in turn will guide restoration.

ECOLOGICAL SUCCESSION AND ECOEXERGY

Richards (2022b) foodweb based ecosystem function model indicated that Utah Lake is now stalled at an ‘immature’ early ecological successional stage. Richards (2022b) suggested that this was primarily because of chronic wave action and unnatural water level fluctuations that consistently disturb unconsolidated sediments and reset the food web, thus preventing maturation and stability of the system. Our midge results support this finding. Restoration will reduce this problem.

Exergy has been proposed as a useful indicator of the state, structure, and function of an ecosystem (Nielsen et al. 2020). Ecoexergy is the term used for ecosystem exergy. Ecoexergy is the amount of inherent workable energy of an ecosystem when it maintains equilibrium within its living environment. The concept has been suggested by Jørgensen (2005, 2007) and reviewed by Nielsen et al. (2020). When ecosystem is at maximum distance from thermodynamic equilibrium, it possesses the highest value of ecoexergy (Jørgensen 2007). Therefore, ecoexergy measures the distance from thermodynamic equilibrium (Jørgensen 2005)¹³. Higher group organisms possess more exergy value than the simpler organisms, and in a complex system, the ecoexergy level is high. Living systems have a particular high ecoexergy mostly due to their high information content (Jørgensen 2005). The theory is that biological systems including ecosystem should evolve in a way that they optimize their thermodynamic efficiency (Nielsen et al. 2020). Ecoexergy can be considered one of the major functional parameters of the ecosystem, as it reflects the components’ energy level to maintain the normal functioning of the ecosystem (Zhang et al., 2010). Lake Mendota, Wisconsin one of the most studied lakes in the world, was shown to have an increase in entropy (decrease ecoexergy) due to eutrophication (Aoki 1989, Nielsen et al. 2020). Margues et al. (2003) found exergy and species richness decreased as a function of increased eutrophication. Flindt et al. (1997) showed that ecoexergy differed with different degrees of organic pollution. Reversing entropy in Utah Lake will require energy input equal to or greater than the useful energy (ecoexergy) that was lost as the lake became more degraded.

Ascendancy is the measure of the average mutual information in a system. It is a product of total throughput (TST) and average mutual information (AMI) of a system (Ulanowicz and Puccia, 1990). A system with high ascendancy is more developed and diversified and contains efficient pathways of energy flow in an unperturbed condition (Ulanowicz, 1986). Ecosystem information is a concept primarily based on functional DNA; the amount of DNA responsible for the part of the genome which is believed to be expressed during the life history of the organism (Nielsen et al. 2020). More complex organism (e.g., fish vs. algae) have more DNA information, and more complex ecosystems have more information than less complex ecosystems. Subsequently, the amount of DNA information an ecosystem stores is a measure of ecoexergy and reverse entropy.

Overhead, *O* also known as the “system reserve” to counter the external perturbation (Ulanowicz, 1986), is complementary to ascendancy. It describes the parallel (unrecognized) path of energy in a system (Feng et al., 2018). Unlike ascendancy, overhead is asymmetrical, i.e., the values from input and output are different (Christensen et al., 2008). Among the four components of overhead

¹³ Ecoexergy is often explained as a translation of Darwinian survival of the fittest. The fittest ecosystem is the one able to use and store fluxes of energy and materials in the most efficient manner i.e., it has the highest ecoexergy. Ecoexergy can also be considered reverse entropy or ‘negentropy’ (Nielsen et al. 2020). Exergy may then constitute not only a suitable system-oriented characteristic to express natural tendencies of ecosystems evolution, but also a good ecological indicator of ecosystems health Marques et al. (1997).

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(i.e., export, import, internal flow and respiration), overhead in internal flow or redundancy is a sensible attribute to measure the system stability by indicating the number of parallel ways for energy flow between two components (Christensen et al., 2005; Heymans et al., 2007). Ecological stability in terms of resilience and resistance is one of the most important properties in ecosystem health assessments (Chang and Wen 2017). Overhead and the redundancy are measures of the resilient capacity of any system; a high overhead bearing system is more resilient and has more reserve strength (Odum, 2014). Functional redundancy is the major aspect of the resilient capacity and is considered the integral part to maintain robustness so that a system can overcome any stress factor to maintain its function (Mumby et al., 2014).

Although not measured in our mesocosm 2023 study but based on our findings, measurable TTE, ecoexergy, ascendancy, overhead, and redundancy metrics should improve in Utah Lake if diverse benthic habitats and associated invertebrates are restored. Continued monitoring of Utah Lake's ecosystem is highly recommended.

Chapter 4 Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages

APPENDICES

Appendix 8 Abundances of invertebrate taxa collected in mesocosm study 2023. Taxa names are in Table 21

Sample Code	Month	In Out	CHDE	CLAD	CORB	CRPY	EISP	EPHI	GLYP	HYSP	LEKI	NEMA	OLIG	OSTR	PASP	PACH	POHA	PRSP
IN1JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	13	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	55	0	0	0	0	1
IN2JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	15	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0
IN3JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	15	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	61	0	0	1	0	0
IN4JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	16	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	17	0	0	1	0	4
IN5JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	25	12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	76	0	0	0	0	4
IN6JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	19	7	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	3
IN7JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	23	22	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	2	1	4
IN8JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	14	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	55	0	0	2	0	1
IN12JUNE3	JUNE16	Inside	2	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	168	0	0	3	0	1
OU1JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	51	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	5	39	1	0	0	0	6
OU2JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	21	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	2	74	0	0	0	0	1
OU3JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	9	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1
OU4JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	0	0	0	0	1
OU5JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	18	18	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	12	0	0	1	0	0
OU6JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	23	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	5
OU7JUNE3	JUNE16	Outside	37	42	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	112	0	0	3	0	4
IN1AUG31	AUG31	Inside	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	25	1	1	0	0	0
IN2AUG31	AUG31	Inside	0	24	1	0	0	1	2	0	7	1	144	0	0	9	0	0
IN3AUG31	AUG31	Inside	3	35	2	2	0	0	3	0	13	3	232	0	0	6	0	3
IN4AUG31	AUG31	Inside	0	32	1	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	42	0	0	2	0	0
IN5AUG31	AUG31	Inside	0	11	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	26	0	0	3	0	0
IN6AUG31	AUG31	Inside	2	26	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	19	0	0	1	0	1
IN7AUG31	AUG31	Inside	1	39	1	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	71	0	0	4	0	1
IN8AUG31	AUG31	Inside	2	61	0	0	0	0	1	0	5	0	43	1	2	2	0	1
IN9AUG31	AUG31	Inside	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	49	0	0	4	1	0
IN10AUG31	AUG31	Inside	4	134	2	0	0	0	8	0	12	2	152	0	0	16	0	8
IN11AUG31	AUG31	Inside	1	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	17	0	0	1	0	0

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IN12AUG31	AUG31	Inside	5	315	0	0	0	0	5	0	12	20	81	0	0	5	2	12
OU1AUG31	AUG31	Outside	2	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	4	48	13	0	0	1	0	5
OU2AUG31	AUG31	Outside	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	2	6	127	0	0	2	0	3
OU3AUG31	AUG31	Outside	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	8	4	53	0	0	1	1	0
OU4AUG31	AUG31	Outside	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	7	16	0	0	2	0	2
OU5AUG31	AUG31	Outside	1	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	11	98	0	0	1	1	1
OU6AUG31	AUG31	Outside	3	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	24	27	0	0	0	0	1
OU7AUG31	AUG31	Outside	0	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	13	13	0	0	3	0	2
OU8AUG31	AUG31	Outside	0	9	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	59	0	0	2	0	0
IN1SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	1	39	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	6	57	0	0	3	0	0
IN2SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	45	0	0	0	0	0
IN3SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	2	19	0	0	1	2	0	0	6	1	133	0	0	2	0	0
IN4SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	1	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	36	0	0	0	0	0
IN5SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	3	91	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	4	0	0
IN6SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	4	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	23	0	0	1	0	1
IN7SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	0	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	14	0	0	0	0	0
IN8SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	3	29	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	1	0	0
IN9SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	29	0	0	0	0	0
IN10SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	115	0	0	0	0	0
IN11SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	13	0	0	0	0	0
IN12SEPT27	SEPT27	Inside	0	12	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	3	26	0	0	0	0	0
OU1SEPT27	SEPT27	Outside	6	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	9	119	0	0	0	0	0
OU2SEPT27	SEPT27	Outside	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0
OU3SEPT27	SEPT27	Outside	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	18	61	0	0	1	0	2
OU4SEPT27	SEPT27	Outside	0	12	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	16	0	0	0	0	0
OU5SEPT27	SEPT27	Outside	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	135	0	0	0	0	0

CHAPTER 5: PHYTOPLANKTON AND ZOOPLANKTON RELATIONS

By
David C. Richards, Ph.D.

Oreohelix Ecological, Vineyard UT 84059
Phone: 406.580.7816
Email: oreohelix@icloud.com

And

Sam Rushforth, Ph.D., and Sarah Rushforth
Rushforth Phycology, Provo, UT

Brett Marshall
River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT

Cover Image: “*Daphnia* playing with Volvox”. From <https://www.aquaticlivefood.com.au/zooplankton-daphnia/>.

Summary

Zooplankton grazers are the principal water column top-down biotic regulator of phytoplankton, including cyanobacteria in Utah Lake. Phytoplankton can also bottom-up regulate zooplankton abundances.

In this chapter, we statistically analyzed relationships between phytoplankton and zooplankton including potential mesocom/treatment effects from our mesocoms study 2023.

We found strong evidence that phytoplankton biovolumes were inversely related to zooplankton densities likely from grazing by zooplankton. A major finding was that zooplankton densities had a negative effect on cyanophyte biovolumes on the August 17 sample event when cyanophyte biovolumes were greatest. Zooplankton helped regulate these blooms. In particular, *Daphnia mendotae* had more grazing effect on cyanophytes than any other zooplankton taxon on the August 17 sample event that was then followed by the other *Daphnia* spp. on August 31. These results strongly support findings by other ecologists that zooplankton and daphnia in particular, graze cyanophytes. There was less than a two-week lag between phytoplankton biovolumes and zooplankton densities as the zooplankton tracked their food source.

Mesocom treatments had mixed effects on zooplankton-phytoplankton division relationships and there was no overall effect of mesocoms on our pseudo zooplankton/phytoplankton ratio, Z/P. We found strong evidence that the Z/P ratio was highest on the June 16 sample event and lowest on the August 17 sample event indicating that zooplankton typically control phytoplankton except during a bloom.

Our results show that it is imperative to identify biota such as phytoplankton and zooplankton to the highest taxonomic level, genus and/or species. Results also confirm that restoration efforts directed towards turbulence reduction and a more balanced fisheries will allow zooplankton assemblages to help adjust and steer the lake toward a more functioning ecosystem via phytoplankton grazing resulting in increased energy transfer efficiency.

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INTRODUCTION

Zooplankton grazers are the principal water column biotic regulator of phytoplankton, including cyanobacteria in lakes worldwide (Iglesias et al. 2007, Scheffer 1998, Karlson et al. 2015, Cole and Weihe 2016; Wetzel 2001, Schwarzenberger 2022), including Utah Lake (Richards et al. 2019). Zooplankton have top-down effects on phytoplankton assemblages via size selective grazing and in turn are affected by phytoplankton assemblages (e.g., bottom-up effects) (Iglesias et al. 2007). Zooplankton nutrient excretion and respiration into the water column is immediately available for assimilation by phytoplankton, often within minutes, thus accelerating primary productivity via a positive feedback loop and improving ecosystem efficiency (i.e., increased ecoexergy).

Phytoplankton assemblages can have bottom-up control on zooplankton assemblages via several mechanisms, including relative abundance, digestibility, nutrient content, toxin production, etc. However, and contrary to past assumptions, it is becoming apparent that many zooplankton taxa routinely and selectively rely on cyanobacteria as an important part of their diets (Motwani et al. 2017, Kemal et al. 2016, Woodland et al. 2013, Koski et al. 2002, Vehmaa et al. 2013, Gorokhova and Engstrom-Ost 2009, Hogfors et al. 2014, and Jiang et al. 2013), although a diet consisting mainly of lower quality cyanobacteria can alter trophic level energy transfer efficiency and food web function (Ruiz et al. 2022).

Zooplankton are the dominant energy transfer link from primary producers to higher trophic levels, primarily planktivorous fishes, and can in turn be top-down regulated by this higher trophic level. Consequently, zooplankton can govern a large segment of a water body's ecosystem function, particularly in lakes such as Utah Lake that have limited littoral zone and benthic primary production (Richards et al. 2019, previous chapters in this report). We posit that restoring a robust and healthy zooplankton assemblage in conjunction with other restoration actions (i.e., carp reduction, macrophyte establishment, reestablishment of native mollusks, and a balanced fishery, etc.) will help transition Utah Lake towards increased ecoexergy and improved ecosystem function in the desired direction of a clearer water state.

Despite their keystone importance and precarious existence in highly regulated and abused Utah Lake, very little research has been conducted on the ecological role of zooplankton. In this chapter we analyzed relationships between phytoplankton and zooplankton including potential mesocom/treatment effects from our mesocom study 2023.

METHODS

We conducted statistical analyses comparing phytoplankton and zooplankton assemblages and other factors measured by us in the study using several methods. These included several types of regression: linear, linear-quadratic, fractional, and negative binomial. Best fit models were selected based on the nature of data distribution and lowest AIC, BIC, and log likelihood criteria. Phytoplankton biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) were typically log transformed and zooplankton densities (individuals L^{-1}) were typically square root or log transformed, except on a few instances when raw

biovolumes and densities were considered more informative. We then created graphical representations of phyto-zooplankton, and treatment interactions. All statistical analyses and graphs were conducted using Stata 16.1 for Mac.

RESULTS

We found strong evidence that phytoplankton biovolumes were inversely related to zooplankton densities. We attribute this response mostly to grazing by zooplankton (Figure 64 and Appendix 9). When zooplankton and month were regressed as predictors of phytoplankton biomass, $R^2 = 0.82$ and zooplankton remained an important predictor ($p = 0.03$) (Appendix 10).

Figure 64 Linear relation of phytoplankton biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) as a function of zooplankton density (L^{-1}). Sample events are coded for additional interpretation. Shade area is 95% CIs.

A major finding was that zooplankton densities m^{-2} (square root transformed) had a negative effect on Cyanophyta biovolumes (log transformed) on the August 17 sample event (Figure 65). We did not find any relations between phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities on the other four sample events (Figure 65).

Figure 65 Linear relationships between phytoplankton biovolume and zooplankton density for each sample event.

Cyanophyta biovolumes were greatest on the August 17 sample event indicating a large bloom around that time (see chapter on phytoplankton and following results). Zooplankton appeared to have grazed cyanophytes and reduced their biovolume when needed most to help control the bloom (Figure 66). Mesocosms also reduced cyanophyte biovolumes on August 17 (see previous chapter) and combined with zooplankton grazing had more of an effect than either factor alone (Figure 66 and Appendix 11).

Figure 66. Best fit quadratic regression of the effects of zooplankton density m^{-2} (sqrt transformed) and mesocosms on Cyanophyta biovolume $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$ (log transformed) on the August 17 sample event. Samples were combined from inside and outside of mesocosms for analyses. Shaded area is 95% CIs.

ALONG CAME DAME

Negative binomial regression provided strong evidence that DAME, *Daphnia mendotae* density was highest on the August 17 sample event compared with the other events (mean = 297, median = 186 individuals L^{-1}) (Figure 67 and Appendix 12). DAME and DAAM *Daphnia ambigua* were the only zooplankton taxa that had their highest densities on the August 17 sample event (see Figure 13 in zooplankton chapter).

Figure 67 *Daphnia mendotae* densities (individuals L⁻¹) on the five sample events. Mean and 95% CIs based on best fit regression in Appendix 10.

As mentioned, *Daphnia ambigua* (DAAM) also had its highest density on August 17 sample event but its densities were very low (mean = 3.1 individual L⁻¹, median = 0.0 individuals L⁻¹) and this species likely had limited or no impact on cyanophyte or other phytoplankton division biovolumes throughout the duration of the study.

We also found strong evidence that combined densities of all four *Daphnia* spp., *D. ambigua*, *D. mendotae*, *D. pulex*, *D. retrocurva* were greater on the June 15, August 31, and September 12 sample events than the August 17 sample event (Figure 68), indicating that only *D. mendotae* was the key *Daphnia* spp. responsible for the initial decline in cyanophyte biovolume during the bloom August 17. However, *Daphnia* spp. reached their highest densities on Aug 31 suggesting an approximate two-week lag between cyanophyte bloom and daphnia density (Figure 68).

Figure 68 *Daphnia spp.* densities (individuals L⁻¹) on the five sample events. Mean and 95% CIs based on best fit regression Error! Reference source not found.. Red line points to August 17 sample event.

ZOOPLANKTON TRACK PHYTOPLANKTON

Estimated mean zooplankton densities were lowest on June16 as was the estimated phytoplankton biovolume (Figure 69). Zooplankton densities then increased on Aug17 and peaked Aug31 tracking phytoplankton biovolume that peaked Aug17 and then declined to the end of the study period (Figure 69). Phytoplankton biovolume then decreased starting on Aug31 coinciding with the peak of zooplankton densities on Aug31. Thus, there was a \leq two-week lag of zooplankton tracking and grazing on phytoplankton.

Figure 69 Estimated zooplankton densities and phytoplankton biovolumes for each sample event. Mean and 95% CIs based on regression analyses.

Relations for zooplankton densities vs. each phytoplankton division biovolumes for each sample event are in the following figures.

Figure 70 Estimated zooplankton densities and Bacillariophyta biovolumes for each sample event. Mean and 95% CIs based on regression analyses.

Figure 71 Estimated zooplankton densities and Chlorophyta biovolumes for each sample event. Mean and 95% CIs based on regression analyses.

Figure 72 Estimated zooplankton densities and Cyanophyta biovolumes for each sample event. Mean and 95% CIs based on regression analyses.

Figure 73 Estimated zooplankton densities and Dinophyta biovolumes for each sample event. Mean and 95% CIs based on regression analyses.

Chapter 5 Phytoplankton and zooplankton relations

The following figures, Figure 74 - Figure 77 illustrate relations between phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities within and between mesocosm treatments (Table 29) on the sample events where we found evidence for important relationships. Effects varied by phytoplankton divisions, treatments, and sample events. Other mesocosm effects occurred due to condition of mesocosms (e.g., high flushing rates) or can be mostly explained from results reported and discussed in previous chapters.

Table 29 Mesocosm and experimental treatments

Mesocosm	Experimental Treatment
1	Eggs/Juvenile carp
2	Geochem Control
3	Geochem, rhodamine, and phosphorus
4	Geochem, rhodamine, and phosphorus
5	Juvenile carp
6	Bivalves
7	Control
8	Control
9	Bivalves
10	Adult carp
11	Adult carp
12	Control

Figure 74 Phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities in relation to mesocosms treatments and outside mesocosms on August 17.

Figure 75 Phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities in relation to mesocosms treatments and outside mesocosms on August 31.

Chapter 5 Phytoplankton and zooplankton relations

Figure 76 Phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities in relation to mesocosms treatments and outside mesocosms on September 12.

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Figure 77 Phytoplankton division biovolumes and zooplankton densities in relation to mesocosms treatments and outside mesocosms on September 27.

PSEUDO ZOOPLANKTON TO PHYTOPLANKTON RATIO, PSEUDO-Z/P

The zooplankton to phytoplankton, Z/P ratio is a commonly used metric to evaluate the condition of a lake ecosystem. Z/P is based on biomasses of each. Phytoplankton biovolume has close to a one-to-one relation with biomass, however, we did not estimate biomass of zooplankton only densities. Instead, we developed a pseudo-Z/P ratio based on log transformations of zooplankton densities (as opposed to biomass) and phytoplankton biovolumes to compare treatments for the sample event presented in Table 30. Results are similar to Figure 74 but likely easier to interpret and considers all phytoplankton divisions combined.

We found strong evidence that Z/P was highest on June 16 sample event when phytoplankton biovolume was very low and that Z/P was lowest on August 17 sample event when phytoplankton biomass was greatest (Figure 78). We did not find any evidence that Z/P differed inside or outside of mesocosms (Figure 78).

Figure 78 Estimated mean and 95% CIs for pseudo-Z/P based on sample events and inside vs. outside of mesocosms. Values estimated from best fit fractional regression in Appendix 13.

Table 30 Zooplankton (log density) to phytoplankton (log biovolume) ratio, pseudo-Z/P for all sample events inside and outside mesocosms.

Mesocosm	16-Jun	17-Aug	31-Aug	12-Sep	27-Sep
LC1	0.64	0.41	0.45	0.44	0.53
LC2	NA	0.43	0.48	0.49	0.54
LC3	0.70	0.47	0.51	0.57	0.52
LC4	0.67	NA	0.43	0.36	0.64

LC5	0.54	0.35	0.42	0.44	0.56
LC6	0.63	0.36	0.38	0.41	0.60
LC7	0.59	0.31	0.41	0.43	0.58
LC8	0.60	0.37	0.45	0.45	0.53
LC9	NA	0.31	na	0.55	0.58
LC10	NA	0.57	0.52	0.47	0.54
LC11	NA	0.35	0.46	0.44	0.50
LC12	0.63	0.49	0.48	0.45	0.61
Mesocosm Mean	0.63	0.40	0.45	0.46	0.56
Out	0.60	0.39	0.46	0.43	0.59
Out	0.61	0.41	0.49	0.53	0.66
Out	0.57	0.40	0.45	0.51	0.63
Out	0.57	0.36	0.55	0.51	0.56
Out	0.47	0.37	0.49	0.47	0.54
Out	0.62	0.36	0.45	0.43	0.55
Out	0.63	0.38	0.48	0.41	0.52
Out	0.58	0.41	0.45		0.56
Out		0.41			
Lake Mean	0.58	0.39	0.48	0.47	0.58
Grand Mean	0.60	0.40	0.46	0.46	0.57

DISCUSSION

We showed that zooplankton reduced phytoplankton biovolumes, particularly when their biovolumes were greatest on the August 17 sample event. We also provided additional evidence that larger sized zooplankton such as *Daphnia* spp. likely graze cyanophytes in Utah Lake. We even found evidence that daphnia can aid in reducing cyanophyte blooms, *D. mendotae* in particular. We have reported this well-known interaction based on scientific literature in our previous reports, however some management agencies continue to opine that zooplankton likely don't graze cyanophytes in Utah Lake.

Most researchers rarely identify Utah Lake's zooplankton past group level such as cladocera, copepods, and rotifers. Consequently, important food web and ecosystem functions are overlooked and could lead to mismanagement of the lake. Findings presented in this chapter solidify our assertion that it is extremely important to identify taxa to the best possible extent, in this case species level¹⁴. We never would have documented the grazing effects of *Daphnia* spp., starting with *D. mendotae* on cyanophytes without this level of taxonomic resolution. Our mesocosm studies continue to add to this knowledge and have generated valuable data. These

¹⁴ Taxonomy of Utah Lake's zooplankton has never been fully documented or verified. Subsequently, zooplankton taxonomy is under revision by Oreohelix Ecological and River Continuum Concepts, Manhattan, MT.

data can now be used to explore additional phytoplankton/zooplankton relations in more detail but are beyond the scope of this project.

Richards and Miller (2017) reported that Utah Lake supports a zooplankton assemblage that varied spatially and temporally. They reported that there were approximately 20 zooplankton taxa occurring in Utah Lake including cladocerans, copepods, and rotifer taxa identified to species or genus from several functional groups, each with different life history and feeding strategies. Their research group reported that only a very few (3 or 4) zooplankton taxa were ecologically relevant at any given time suggesting chronic lake impairment. (Richards and Miller 2017, Richards 2019, Marshall 2019, and unpublished data).

Unfortunately, zooplankton assemblages in Utah Lake have also undergone bottlenecks and assemblage shifts, including those stressors discussed in the previous sections. This has resulted in Utah Lake's zooplankton assemblages becoming analogs of past natural assemblages and they are unable to completely regulate cyanobacteria blooms in its current state.

One of the most important factors not discussed so far has been and continues to be predation on zooplankton by planktivorous invasive fish and how this indirectly affects cyanoHABs in Utah Lake. Richards and Miller (2019) found that overall zooplankton body size was lower than expected suggesting selective pressure from planktivorous fishes in the lake. All fish species in Utah Lake are zooplanktivorous, at least during juvenile stages. USU researchers have suggested that zooplankton body lengths have increased after the carp removal project was initiated but time will tell if this trend continues due to increasing carp densities post 2013 (Walsworth et al. 2020, Walsworth and Landom 2021, Landom and Walsworth 2021) and curtailment of the carp removal program, hopefully only temporary. Our mesocosm findings showed that larger sized zooplankton (e.g., *Daphnia* spp.) still exist in the lake, track phytoplankton biovolumes, and can increase in abundance under restorative conditions (e.g., mesocosm reduction in wave induced turbulence and turbidity).

Zooplankton now appear to have limited ability to completely control phytoplankton densities/biovolumes in Utah Lake, other than within our artificially protective mesocosms. However, they obviously continue to have some regulatory authority, potentially limiting cyanobacteria bloom frequency and intensity.

The zooplankton to phytoplankton biomass ratio, Z/P is often used as a metric evaluating trophic status of a water body and ecosystem functioning, and as a component of food web models. Z/P typically decreases with increased eutrophication (Gulati, 1983; Andronikova, 1996; Jeppesen et al., 1999, 2000, 2005; Haberman & Laugaste, 2003, Blank et al. 2010). Our pseudo-Z/P ratio supported this tendency as well as seasonal trends in Z/P that reflected summer phytoplankton growth and blooms. Our pseudo-Z/P ratio was based on zooplankton densities and should not be used for comparison of standard Z/P ratios that use biomass. Richards (2022) calculated that Utah Lake Z/P also varied seasonally with higher values in winter vs. summer. The highest Z/P was in

March = 0.18, lowest in September and order of magnitude lower at 0.018 (annual mean = 0.07). Z/P showed that zooplankton grazing was very inefficient from June through November when harder to digest phytoplankton were dominant and infers that much of the unconsumed phytoplankton (and dead zooplankton) falls as detrital 'snow' to the sediments. Large amounts of detrital snow alter the benthic portion of the food web from past benthic algae autotrophic to heterotrophic and signify a food web much out of balance. It also emphasizes that the microbial loop in Utah Lake likely contributes disproportionately more to the food web than typical naturally functioning shallow lakes, although there have been no studies on this important component in the lake's function. Results from this mesocosm study suggest that restoration efforts directed towards turbulence reduction and a more balanced fisheries can allow zooplankton assemblages to adjust and steer the lake toward a more functioning ecosystem via phytoplankton grazing and increased energy transfer efficiency.

Zooplankton frequently move between habitats including daily horizontal migration tracking phytoplankton as demonstrated in previous chapters of this report. As we have shown in our 2022 study and to a lesser extent in our 2023 study (e.g., *Leptodora kindtii*), zooplankton can occur in very high abundances in benthic filamentous algae, at least during daylight hours when we sampled. Subsequently, zooplankton are also a vital linkage between the pelagic, benthic, and littoral zones (Vander Zanden and Vadeboncoeur 2002, Jones and Waldron, 2003). Zooplankton are the main consumers of phytoplankton and are in turn consumed by small fish, including all juvenile fishes and all juvenile and adult June Suckers in Utah Lake (Richards et al. 2019). They are the chief intermediaries between primary production and higher trophic levels, and thus play a critical role in Utah Lake food web dynamics (Richards et al. 2019).

Zooplankton are not only grazers, some taxa prey upon other zooplankton (e.g., *Leptodora kindtii* discussed in previous chapter). Most zooplankton, however, are selective feeders, given the opportunity. All of these complex foodweb interactions directly and indirectly influence nutrient cycling in the water column. This phytoplankton-zooplankton component of water column nutrient cycling has been well documented and known by limnologists and ecologists for several decades and is likely an important driver of cyanobacteria blooms in Utah Lake (Iglesias et al. 2007, Scheffer 1998). Medium- and large-sized cladocerans, typically *Daphnia* spp. can markedly reduce phytoplankton biomass (Jeppesen et al. 1990, Scheffer 1998), even in communities dominated by cyanobacteria (Jeppesen et al. 2003, Lampert et al. 1986, Brooks and Dodson 1965, Gorokhova and Engstrom-Ost 2009, and Hogfors et al. 2014) and as we have illustrated in this chapter. *Daphnia* spp. are known as one of the most important zooplankton taxa able to control cyanobacteria blooms (Schwarzenberger 2022). *Daphnia* spp. can feed on bacteria, protozoa, phytoplankton and even some small zooplankton, highlighting their important role in freshwater food webs (Yin et al. 2010). It has been demonstrated that intensive zooplankton grazing can promote a clear-water state (Scheffer 1998). For example, grazing by *Daphnia* sp. has been reported to be responsible for spring clearing in temperate lakes (Meijer et al. 1999). Zooplankton assemblages can shift phytoplankton assemblages toward better adapted cyanobacteria consumer species (Motwani et al. 2017, Woodland et al. 2013, Koski et al. 2002, Gorokhova and

Engstrom-Ost 2009, Hogfors et al. 2014, Ger et al. 2016, Ruiz 2022), however there can be an energetic cost to *Daphnia* spp. consuming toxin producing cyanobacteria that may affect trophic level energy transfer and ecosystem function (Brown et al. 2004, Kooijman 2009, Ruiz 2022). Our past and present 2023 results strongly support these conclusions that *Daphnia* spp. and other taxa often consume cyanophytes even though cyanophytes are a lower quality food resource than other types of phytoplankton (Schwarzenberger 2022). We recommend that managers initiate actions to balance Utah Lake's food web so that zooplankton assemblages will continue to help regulate cyanophyte blooms and return the lake to a clearer water stable state (high ecoexergy, low entropy).

Jin (2021) reported that zooplankton are often hindered by filtering sediment laden water and do not have the ability to prevent ingesting sediment. This can limit their intake of phytoplankton and sediment excretion is energetically costly (Koenings et al. 1990, Kirk and Gilbert 1990, Penning et al. 2013). Turbulence may also inhibit growth of large-sized zooplankton species with body sizes that exceed Kolmogorov length scale because they are more affected by eddy motion (Peters and Marrasé 2000, Jin 2021). This can impair food detection or capture, or directly lead to body damage (Visser et al. 2009, G. -Tóth et al. 2011, Zhou et al. 2016, Jin 2021). Sediment resuspension may also cause physical damage to zooplankton by abrasion and turbulent shear forces which may lead to decreases in zooplankton biomass (Peters and Marrasé 2000). We suggest from our 2023 and past mesocosm results that reducing wave induced turbulence can alleviate these effects and stimulate higher trophic production and ecosystem efficiency (i.e., increased ecoexergy, decreased entropy) and move Utah Lake from a chronic early successional state to a more mature state.

APPENDICES

Appendix 9 Linear regression model for phytoplankton biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) (log transformed) as a function of zooplankton density (individuals L^{-1}) (sqrt transformed).

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	93
Model	12.5670954	1	12.5670954	F(1, 91)	=	18.18
Residual	62.9100159	91	.691318856	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.1665
				Adj R-squared	=	0.1573
Total	75.4771114	92	.820403385	Root MSE	=	.83146

log10Phyto~l	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
sqrtzoototal	-.0302139	.0070864	-4.26	0.000	-.0442902	-.0161375
_cons	8.050408	.3225413	24.96	0.000	7.40972	8.691097

Appendix 10 Best fit linear regression model for phytoplankton biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) (log transformed) as a function of zooplankton density (individuals L^{-1}) (sqrt transformed) and sample event (monthcode). Aug17 sample event was used as baseline for comparisons.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	94
Model	61.7556381	5	12.3511276	F(5, 88)	=	78.45
Residual	13.8538456	88	.157430063	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.8168
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8064
Total	75.6094837	93	.813005201	Root MSE	=	.39677

logdivisio~l	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
sqrtzoototal	-.0080816	.0035383	-2.28	0.025	-.0151132	-.0010499
monthcode						
1	-2.108139	.1404958	-15.00	0.000	-2.387345	-1.828933
AUG31	-.5015188	.1342735	-3.74	0.000	-.7683591	-.2346785
SEPT12	-.9619607	.1275511	-7.54	0.000	-1.215442	-.7084797
SEPT27	-1.771468	.1333339	-13.29	0.000	-2.036441	-1.506495
_cons	8.117237	.1562399	51.95	0.000	7.806743	8.427731

Appendix 11 Best fit quadratic regression model of the effects of zooplankton density m^{-2} (sqrt transformed) and mesocosms on Cyanophyta biovolume $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$ (log transformed) on the August 17 sample event. Samples were combined from inside and outside of mesocosms for analyses.

Chapter 5 Phytoplankton and zooplankton relations

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	20
Model	3.31200388	2	1.65600194	F(2, 17)	=	13.89
Residual	2.02721772	17	.119248101	Prob > F	=	0.0003
				R-squared	=	0.6203
				Adj R-squared	=	0.5756
Total	5.3392216	19	.281011663	Root MSE	=	.34532

logcyanophyta	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
inoutcode Outside	.4430949	.2180958	2.03	0.058	-.0170471	.9032369
c.sqrtzoototal#c.sqrtzoototal	-.0003095	.0000679	-4.56	0.000	-.0004528	-.0001663
_cons	7.858448	.2355572	33.36	0.000	7.361465	8.35543

Appendix 12 Best fit negative binomial regression of *D. mendotae* (DAME) in relation to sample event (MonthCode) and inside vs. outside of mesocosms. August 17 sample event (2) was used as baseline comparison.

Negative binomial regression	Number of obs	=	97
	LR chi2(5)	=	62.20
Dispersion = mean	Prob > chi2	=	0.0000
Log likelihood = -413.08598	Pseudo R2	=	0.0700

dame	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
MonthCode						
1	-4.145507	.531138	-7.80	0.000	-5.186518	-3.104495
3	-1.032061	.4919844	-2.10	0.036	-1.996333	-.0677895
4	-2.740008	.4942908	-5.54	0.000	-3.708801	-1.771216
5	-4.07817	.4970742	-8.20	0.000	-5.052417	-3.103922
2.inoutcode	-.3461373	.3384847	-1.02	0.306	-1.009555	.3172806
_cons	5.844951	.3760874	15.54	0.000	5.107834	6.582069
/lnalpha	.8850649	.1597013			.5720561	1.198074
alpha	2.423142	.3869789			1.771906	3.313727

LR test of alpha=0: $\text{chibar2}(01) = 9461.76$ Prob >= $\text{chibar2} = 0.000$

Appendix 13 Best fit fractional probit module for pseudo-Z/P inside vs outside of mesocosms and by sample event. August 17 was baseline for comparing with other sample events.

CHAPTER 6: CHEMISTRY AND NUTRIENT RELATIONS

https://www.greenbiz.com/sites/default/files/2022-07/chemistry_Yurchanka%20Siarhei_shutterstock.jpg

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Cover illustration: Relationships between cyanophytes and zooplankton (primarily *Daphnia* sp.), iron (Fe) and magnesium (Mg) within mesocosms based on regression for four sample events. In general, cyanophytes were 1) preyed upon by zooplankton, primarily by *Daphnia* sp., 2) had greater biovolumes when Fe was less available in the water column (i.e., cyanophytes utilized Fe), 3) had slightly higher biovolumes with Mg in the water column, and 4) had lower biovolumes within mesocosms than in the lake. However, these relations changed slightly over the season.

SUMMARY

Chemistry and nutrients are the building blocks of Utah Lake's ecosystem. Underutilized nutrients due to Utah Lake's degraded ecosystem are the primary cause of algal blooms in the lake.

Mesocosms had structural integrity problems throughout this study 2023 and subsequently they did not always eliminate water from the lake flowing through. Consequently, mesocosms effects were more difficult to discern than originally anticipated. However, increased movement of lake water through the damaged mesocosms was more similar to what will occur after restoration of native aquatic plant assemblages that will only restrict water movement, not eliminate it.

The effects of individual mesocosm treatments varied by treatment and sample event somewhat unpredictably. Therefore, we were not able to conclusively show effects but were only speculative based on graphical interpretations.

Phytoplankton biovolume tended to be greater with higher levels of TP and grazing likely reduced biovolume. We found no evidence of mesocosm effects on phytoplankton biovolume. However, we found that cyanophyte biovolume was negative related to Fe concentrations in the water column. Cyanophytes are strongly dependent on Fe uptake for metabolic functions.

We discuss at length the relation between cyanophytes, Fe, anoxia, and potential competition for Fe between cyanophytes and chlorophytes where controlling Fe can allow chlorophytes competitive advantage.

Our finding that cyanobacteria biovolumes were limited by Fe availability has important management implications for Utah Lake restoration, and for reducing cyanobacteria blooms. Holistic restoration can provide chlorophytes with competitive advantage; an important but often overlooked restoration strategy for Utah Lake.

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INTRODUCTION

Chemistry and nutrients are the building blocks of Utah Lake's ecosystem. Phytoplankton directly utilize nutrients and zooplankton excrete nutrients that are quickly utilized by phytoplankton. Benthic invertebrates help regulate sediment nutrients entering the water column. Planktivorous fish such as juvenile carp alter nutrients and chemistry in the water column and benthivorous fishes such as adult carp alter nutrients from the sediments. Bivalve mollusks were the penultimate regulators of sediment-water column nutrient chemistry but no longer provide this service. In this chapter we examine the interactions of nutrients and other chemistry variables inside and outside of mesocosms primarily on phytoplankton biovolume but also the relations of Fe and Mg, particularly in relation to cyanophyte biovolume dynamics.

METHODS

Table 31 shows mesocosm experimental treatments.

Table 31 Mesocosm and experimental treatment, 2023

Mesocosm	Experimental Treatment ¹
1	Juvenile carp
2	Geochem Control
3	Geochem, rhodamine, and phosphorus
4	Geochem, rhodamine, and phosphorus
5	Juvenile carp
6	Bivalves
7	Control
8	Control
9	Bivalves
10	Adult carp
11	Adult carp
12	Control

¹In 2023, mesocosms were unable to prevent fish movement in and out. Consequently, we were unable to monitor the number or species of fishes in the mesocosms at any one time. Therefore, we do not consider mesocosms 1, 5, 10, and 11 as full fish treatments and were designated simply as mesocosm wave reduction treatments for many analyses. Fish entering and leaving the other mesocosms including controls may have also clouded results as we discussed in other sections of this report.

Important chemistry and nutrients analyzed in this chapter include:

- Nitrite, NO₂
- Nitrate, NO₃
- Ammonia, NH₄
- Soluble reactive phosphorus, SRP
- Total phosphorus, TP
- Total suspended solids, TSS
- Volatile suspended solids, VSS
- Total dissolved solids, TDS
- Dissolved oxygen, DO
- Chlorophyll A, Chl A
- Fe
- Mg

- Temperature

Several nutrients were strongly correlated (Figure 79, Table 32) and covaried. Unfiltered SRP was dropped from further analysis because of its strong correlation with TP and filtered SRP was considered more important ecologically.

Figure 79 Correlations between nutrients.

Table 32 Correlations, *r* and *p*-values for nutrients.

	NO ₃	NO ₄	NH ₄	Unfiltered SRP	SRP
NO ₄	0.91				
	< 0.01				
NH ₄	0.79	0.65			
	< 0.01	< 0.01			
UnSRP	0.20	0.17	0.05		
	0.09	0.16	0.71		
SRP	0.56	0.40	0.39	0.19	
	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.11	
TP	0.09	0.12	-0.22	0.75	0.24
	0.45	0.33	0.07	< 0.01	0.05

We used several chemistry and nutrient variables as well as other factors including inside vs. outside of mesocosms, sample event, and zooplankton density, as predictors for phytoplankton and Cyanophyta biovolumes. Biovolumes were log transformed. Lasso regression was used to help select the most useful factors for linear regression models. Multilevel mixed effects models were also created and examined. Best fit models were determined by comparing and selecting AIC and BIC criteria with lowest values. We also generated dozens of graphs depicting changes in chemistry and nutrients in relation to mesocosm treatments over the duration of the study.

RESULTS

PHYTOPLANKTON BIOVOLUME

Our best fit regression model for total phytoplankton biovolume (log transformed) explained 78% variability and corroborated our findings that phytoplankton biovolume increased throughout the summer and decreased in autumn. The model also provided good evidence that phytoplankton biovolume was greater with higher levels of TP and that grazing zooplankton likely reduced biovolume. Mg was also important for explaining phytoplankton biovolume in the final model although its relation had a high p-value¹⁵. We found no evidence that mesocosms affected total phytoplankton biovolumes.

CYANOPHYTA BIOVOLUME

Lasso model selection along with examination of additional combinations not suggested by Lasso but considered to be potentially meaningful confirmed that phosphorus was not limiting to cyanophytes in our study area and likely throughout the lake (Appendix 14). Our best fit cyanophyte biovolume (log transformed) linear regression model for all sample events (excluding June sample event because no chemistry data was available) again confirmed that cyanophytes increased in mid-August and decreased by mid-autumn (Appendix 14). Throughout the study, chlorophytes were positively correlated with cyanophytes (Appendix 14).

An important finding was the Fe and cyanophytes were negatively correlated with each other (Figure 80, Appendix 15). Cyanophytes are strongly dependent on Fe uptake for metabolic functions and will be discussed in more detail in the discussion section.

Figure 80 Negative relation between Cyanophyta biovolume (log transformed) and Fe throughout the study.

Because cyanophyte biovolumes changed over the season, we modeled sample events separately. Our best fit regression for August 17 cyanophyte biovolumes had only one predictor, zooplankton.

¹⁵ Best fit models sometimes include predictor variables with large p-values. These predictors improve the predictive power of the model when included.

Zooplankton grazing predicted about 51% of cyanophyte biovolume on August 17 sample event (Appendix 16, Chapter 5).

Our best fit regression model for August 31 sample event showed that cyanophyte biovolumes were lower inside mesocosms than in the lake, presumably due in part to reduced amounts Fe laden sediment resuspension, and that zooplankton grazing continued to have a strong negative effect on cyanophytes. Fe was negatively associated with cyanophytes, as was the case for most of the season, and Mg was again positively associated with cyanophytes (Appendix 17). The model explained about 75% variability in cyanophyte biovolumes on August 31 sample event.

We did not find suitable regression models for predicting cyanophyte biovolumes on the September sample events.

BACILLARIOPHYTA

Bacillariophyta biovolume was best predicted by whether they were inside or outside of mesocosms although SRP, zooplankton densities, and sampling events improved the prediction strength of the model ($R^2 = 0.44$) (Appendix 18). There was strong evidence that bacillariophytes were more abundant inside mesocosms (Appendix 18). Again, this was likely due to the effects of reduced wave action.

CHLOROPHYTA

Our chlorophyte biovolume regression model had many useful predictors including, inside vs outside of mesocosms, sample event showing seasonal effects, zooplankton grazing, negative relations with Fe and Mg. The strongest predictor of chlorophyte biovolume was TP (Appendix 19). Zooplankton grazing was the single best predictor of cyanophyte biovolume on the August 17 sample event with $R^2 = 0.55$ (Appendix 20). We were unable to develop a useful model for chlorophytes on the August 31 sample event. SRP, dinophytes, Fe, and Mg were the most useful predictors of chlorophytes on September 12 sample event (Appendix 21).

CHEMISTRY AND NUTRIENT VARIABILITY

The following figures illustrate the sometimes, large variability of chemistry and nutrients inside mesocosms including controls over the course of the study (Figure 81).

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Figure 81 Chemistry and nutrients inside mesocosms throughout the study period.

TREATMENTS VS CHEMISTRY AND NUTRIENTS

GEOCHEMICAL

Geochemical treatments included rhodamine and phosphorus. The following table, Table 33 lists treatments, mesocosms, and dates started. Rhodamine and phosphorus treatments were added during the peak of the cyanophyte bloom observed August 17 to September 12, 2023.

Table 33 Geochemical treatments, mesocosms, and dates started.

Treatment	Mesocosm	Date Started
Geochem Control	2	August 24, 2023
Rhodamine + phosphorus	3	August 24, 2023
Rhodamine + phosphorus	4	August 24, 2023
Rhodamine + phosphorus	10	August 29, 2023
Controls	7, 8, 12	
Outside		

The following figure shows the relationships between chemistry and nutrient values and geochemical treatments.

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Figure 82 Geochemical treatments in relation to chemistry/ nutrients during study.

JUVENILE CARP

The following table lists juvenile carp treatments, mesocosms, and dates started.

Table 34 Juvenile carp (JC) treatments, mesocosms, and dates started.

Treatment	Mesocosm	Date Started
Juvenile carp	1	August 8, 2023
Juvenile carp	5	August 9, 2023
Controls	7, 8, 12	
Outside	NA	

The following figure, Figure 83 shows the relationships between chemistry and nutrient values and juvenile carp treatments. As discussed in previous chapters, mesocosms were not completely able to restrict fish passage in and out, therefore caution should be used in interpretations of effects. Ammonia (NH₄) was often higher in juvenile carp treatments than the mesocosm controls or in the lake starting in mid-summer.

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Figure 83 Potential effects of juvenile carp on chemistry and nutrients

ADULT CARP

The following table shows carp treatments and controls.

Table 35 Adult Carp treatments, mesocosms, and dates started.

Treatment	Mesocosm	Date Started
Adult Carp	10	August 4, 2023
Adult Carp	11	August 4, 2023
Controls	7, 8, 12	
Outside		

The following figure, Figure 84 shows the relationships between chemistry and nutrient values and juvenile carp treatments. As discussed in previous chapters, mesocosms were not completely able to restrict fish passage in and out, therefore caution should be used in interpretations of effects.

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Figure 84 Potential effects of adult carp on nutrients and chemical measures.

BIVALVES

The interactions between nutrients and chemistry variables and bivalve treatments showed mixed results. Several variables including NH_4 , NO_3 , NO_4 , and TDS tended to be higher in bivalve treatment mesocosms compared to control mesocosms, while TSS tended to be lower inside bivalve treatments (Figure 85). However, strong evidence to support these observations is lacking other than bivalves can increase NO_x and decrease TSS through metabolism and feeding.

Figure 85 Potential effects of bivalves on nutrients and chemistry.

MESOCOSM EFFECTS

Mean Chl A and TDS were always higher inside mesocosms, whereas mean TSS and VSS were lower. Mean SRP was similar inside and out (Figure 86). These results support the vast literature and our findings that as wave induced turbulence and sediment resuspension are reduced (TSS), primary production and associated metrics (Chl A, TDS, VSS) increases. Also, available phosphorus (SRP) was constantly utilized by primary producers, predominantly phytoplankton.

These transformations, although sometimes considered problematic are a necessary first step towards restoring Utah Lake to a more energy efficient state.

Figure 86 mesocosm effects on several nutrients and chemical measures. Mean and 95% CI.

DISCUSSION

Mesocosms had structural integrity problems throughout this study 2023 and subsequently they did not always eliminate water from the lake flowing through. Consequently, mesocosm effects were more difficult to discern than originally anticipated. However, increased movement of lake water through the damaged mesocosms was more similar to what will occur after restoration of native aquatic plant assemblages that will only restrict water movement, not eliminate it.

Our finding that cyanobacteria biovolumes were limited by Fe availability has important management implications for Utah Lake restoration aimed at reducing cyanobacteria blooms. Mean Fe concentrations in the water column varied throughout the study (Figure 87). Fe decreased during maximum growth of cyanophytes in early August but then increased shortly thereafter to remain higher in late summer and autumn than in early to mid-summer (Figure 87). Other reasons for Fe concentration variability and its relation to cyanophytes needs substantially more research beyond this study.

Figure 87 Fe concentrations (log (mg L⁻¹)) during the study period. Includes samples from inside and outside of mesocosms.

Following the evidence of the relationship between Fe and cyanophytes documented in this study and the large amount of literature on Fe importance to cyanophytes, we discuss the following.

It is well known, that cyanophytes require substantial amounts of Fe for metabolic function. For example, Kranzler et al. (2013) reported that cyanobacterial Fe requirements exceed non-photosynthetic prokaryotes by ~10-fold and are exceptionally high even among other photosynthetic organisms. Ferrous and ferric Fe ions are strongly related to oxygen concentrations and cyanobacterial siderophores play a crucial role in Fe ion balance.

ANOXIA AND FE

Molot et al. (2014) proposed that the role of anoxia and ferrous iron was critical for cyanobacteria bloom formation. Their highly cited model can be summarized as follows:

“The model has several critical concepts: (i) P regulates biomass and productivity in fresh waters until excessive loading renders a system N-limited or light-limited, but it is the availability of ferrous ions (Fe²⁺) that regulates the ability of cyanobacteria to compete with its

eukaryotic competitors; (ii) Fe^{2+} diffusing from anoxic sediments is a major Fe source for cyanobacteria, which acquire it by migrating downwards into Fe^{2+} -rich anoxic waters from oxygenated waters; and (iii) subsequent cyanobacterial siderophore production provides a supply of Fe^{3+} for reduction at cyanobacteria cell membranes that leads to very low Fe^{3+} concentrations in the mixing zone.

When light and temperature are physiologically suitable for cyanobacteria growth, bloom onset is regulated by the onset of internal Fe^{2+} loading which in turn is controlled by anoxia, reducible Fe content of surface sediments and sulphate reduction rate.”

Figure 88 (taken directly from Molot et al. 2014) illustrates the processes that promote Fe delivery to cyanobacteria and thereby promote cyanobacteria dominance in lakes.

Figure 88. Anoxia: systems with anoxic sediments will experience Fe^{2+} flux into anoxic waters. Migrating cyanobacteria can acquire Fe^{2+} for direct transport into cells. (2) photoreduction: DOM-Fe^{3+} can be photo-reduced, giving rise to Fe^{2+} that is available for direct Fe^{2+} transport into phytoplankton cells, but the transport rate is pH dependent. Acidity affects rates of abiotic oxidation by dissolved O_2 and at $\text{pH} < 6$ Fe^{2+} re-oxidation may be low enough to give rise to a pool of transportable Fe^{2+} . At higher pH, much of it is probably re-oxidised before transport. (3) and (4) Fe^{3+} -scavenging (or acquisition) system: siderophores are produced by cyanobacteria that can (3) bind free soluble Fe^{3+} and (4) cleave Fe^{3+} from DOM complexes. Scavenged Fe^{3+} is then delivered to the cell membrane, creating a pool of Fe^{2+} only accessible by cyanobacteria. Fe^{3+} is reduced by the FeR reducing system before transport across the inner membrane. The Fe^{2+} pool is shown as two separate pools – in anoxic waters (internal loading) and in the mixing layer (photo-reduction).

Thus, Molot et al. (2014) hypothesized that “large cyanobacteria populations that turn surface waters green (i.e., large blooms) must be supported by high external supply rates of Fe^{2+} , and the most likely source of this would be internal Fe^{2+} loading from anoxic sediments. Buoyancy-controlling cyanobacteria can migrate to at least 10–12 m below the surface to acquire nutrients (Camacho et al. 1996, 2000; Head et al. 1999; Gervais et al. 2003), suggesting that in eutrophic systems they may migrate into or adjacent to anoxic bottom waters to acquire Fe^{2+} . Thus, diffusion of Fe^{2+} from anoxic sediments into overlying waters may play a role in the success of these taxa.”

Verschuur et al. (2017) demonstrated that two preconditions, warm temperatures, and sediment anoxia with internal Fe^{2+} loading, were necessary preconditions for cyanobacteria dominance in

areas of the Great Lakes. Vershoor et al. (2017) also concluded that “The collective evidence from contrasting oligotrophic and meso -eutrophic freshwater systems suggests that warm temperatures, anoxia, and internal Fe²⁺ loading are critical preconditions for cyanobacteria dominance, and these preconditions along with high P are needed for relatively large, visible blooms to form.”

COMPETITION FOR FE

The requirement of cyanophytes for large amounts Fe can also make them vulnerable to interspecific competition with other phytoplankton taxa that require less Fe if Fe becomes limited. As our data suggests, Fe may limit cyanophyte blooms via intraspecific competition (e.g., chlorophyte biovolumes trended with cyanophyte biovolumes).

Simple Lotka- Volterra two-taxa interspecific competition models (Lotka 1932) show that reducing Fe in the water column and near surface sediments will favor other phytoplankton taxa that are less dependent on Fe (Figure 89).

Figure 89 Lotka-Volterra two taxa competition MODEL. x-axis = cyanophyte biovolume, y-axis = chlorophyte biovolume. (<https://d2vlcm61l7u1fs.cloudfront.net/media/8a2/8a2dd203-baf0-4bb4-bc72-ec8e4ae9a962/php1BJcX0.png>).

The two taxa L-V competition model is as follows:

Cyanophytes: $dN_1/dt = r_1 N_1 ((K_1 - N_1) / K_1)$

Chlorophytes: $dN_2/dt = r_2 N_2 ((K_2 - N_2) / K_2)$

Where N_1 = cyanophytes, N_2 = chlorophytes, r = intrinsic growth rate, K = carrying capacity, α = effect of cyanophytes on chlorophytes, and β = effect of chlorophytes on cyanophytes.

When Fe becomes less available to cyanophytes through 1) stabilization of sediments (e.g., benthic algae, macrophytes, carp removal, bivalves, etc.), 2) improved oxic conditions in sediments from increased numbers of chironomid larvae aeration (see Chapter 4), and 3) direct competition for Fe with benthic algae, then cyanophyte r , intrinsic growth rate and K , carrying capacity will decrease. Chlorophytes will have the competitive advantage; an important but often overlooked restoration strategy for Utah Lake.

CONCLUSION

Utah Lake has been impaired with low ecoexergy and high entropy for likely well over a century as we have discussed in previous chapters and progress reports. The findings presented in this chapter along with findings from the other chapters in this report help solidify our recommendation for initiation of a holistic restoration program for Utah Lake. The lake cannot simply heal itself.

APPENDICES

Appendix 14 Phytoplankton biovolumes best fit linear regression.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	66
Model	32.6747858	6	5.44579764	F(6, 59)	=	36.36
Residual	8.83636532	59	.149768904	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.7871
				Adj R-squared	=	0.7655
Total	41.5111512	65	.638633095	Root MSE	=	.387

logdivisiontotal	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
zpdatacode						
Aug17	.8941126	.1443315	6.19	0.000	.605306	1.182919
Aug31	.3251593	.1585515	2.05	0.045	.0078984	.6424202
Sept27	-.7093092	.1407921	-5.04	0.000	-.9910335	-.4275849
totalphosphorusunfiltered	1.767747	.8258504	2.14	0.036	.1152241	3.42027
sqrtzoototal	-.0086093	.0037358	-2.30	0.025	-.0160845	-.0011341
mg2852_u	-.0085769	.0084555	-1.01	0.315	-.0254964	.0083425
_cons	7.36147	.4195549	17.55	0.000	6.521943	8.200997

Appendix 15 Cyanophyte best fit regression model.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	66
Model	161.42527	4	40.3563175	F(4, 61)	=	28.37
Residual	86.7747109	61	1.42253624	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.6504
				Adj R-squared	=	0.6275
Total	248.199981	65	3.81846125	Root MSE	=	1.1927

logcyanophyta	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
zpdatacode						
Aug17	.4411774	.4334538	1.02	0.313	-.4255671	1.307922
Sept27	-3.091902	.3573717	-8.65	0.000	-3.806511	-2.377293
logchlorophyta	.3622075	.2103511	1.72	0.090	-.0584155	.7828305
fe2382_u	-1.5655	1.651483	-0.95	0.347	-4.867844	1.736843
_cons	5.248918	1.189463	4.41	0.000	2.87044	7.627396

Appendix 16 Cyanophyte regression module for August 17 sample event.

Chapter 6 Chemistry and Nutrient Relations

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	20
Model	2.71101608	1	2.71101608	F(1, 18)	=	18.57
Residual	2.62820552	18	.146011418	Prob > F	=	0.0004
				R-squared	=	0.5078
				Adj R-squared	=	0.4804
Total	5.3392216	19	.281011663	Root MSE	=	.38211

logcyanoph~a	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
sqrtzoototal	-.0280968	.0065206	-4.31	0.000	-.041796	-.0143976
_cons	8.794221	.2519309	34.91	0.000	8.264933	9.323508

Appendix 17 Best fit regression for August 31 cyanophytes

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	16
Model	3.85652875	4	.964132188	F(4, 11)	=	8.27
Residual	1.28236682	11	.116578802	Prob > F	=	0.0025
				R-squared	=	0.7505
				Adj R-squared	=	0.6597
Total	5.13889557	15	.342593038	Root MSE	=	.34144

logcyanoph~a	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
inoutcode						
Inside	-.3664997	.1911834	-1.92	0.082	-.7872915	.0542922
sqrtzoototal	-.0311123	.0061574	-5.05	0.000	-.0446646	-.01756
fe2382_u	-5.84871	2.947788	-1.98	0.073	-12.33675	.639327
mg2852_u	.0376116	.0185123	2.03	0.067	-.0031337	.078357
_cons	8.206417	.8705981	9.43	0.000	6.290244	10.12259

Appendix 18 Best fit regression model for Bacillariophyta biovolumes (log transformed).

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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	66
Model	7.11559269	6	1.18593211	F(6, 59)	=	7.85
Residual	8.90950603	59	.151008577	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.4440
				Adj R-squared	=	0.3875
Total	16.0250987	65	.24653998	Root MSE	=	.3886

logbacillariophyta	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
sqrtzoototal	.0001141	.0038562	0.03	0.976	-.0076022	.0078304
zpdatacode						
Aug31	.1325516	.1665132	0.80	0.429	-.2006405	.4657436
Sept12	-.1604792	.1881033	-0.85	0.397	-.5368731	.2159148
Sept27	-.1257502	.1975617	-0.64	0.527	-.5210703	.2695698
inoutcode						
Outside	-.6624656	.1064108	-6.23	0.000	-.8753931	-.4495381
filteredreactivephosphorus	.4425158	1.054084	0.42	0.676	-1.6667	2.551732
_cons	5.245547	.2247321	23.34	0.000	4.795859	5.695235

Appendix 19 Chlorophyta models selected by lasso all sample events excluding June.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	66
Model	29.6409226	9	3.29343584	F(9, 56)	=	20.03
Residual	9.20759463	56	.164421333	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.7630
				Adj R-squared	=	0.7249
Total	38.8485172	65	.597669495	Root MSE	=	.40549

logchlorophyta	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
inoutcode						
Inside	.0593129	.1165472	0.51	0.613	-.1741592	.2927851
zpdatacode						
Aug17	.3032139	.2061786	1.47	0.147	-.1098115	.7162393
Aug31	.258785	.2175333	1.19	0.239	-.1769866	.6945566
Sept12	-.922174	.1587282	-5.81	0.000	-1.240145	-.6042033
totalphosphorusunfiltered	2.438404	.9086184	2.68	0.010	.6182229	4.258586
sqrtzoototal	-.0036044	.0041346	-0.87	0.387	-.011887	.0046782
logdinophyta	.0549668	.0253254	2.17	0.034	.004234	.1056997
fe2382_u	-.4978737	.6001933	-0.83	0.410	-1.700205	.7044581
mg2852_u	-.0090011	.0092063	-0.98	0.332	-.0274436	.0094414
_cons	5.82669	.5045718	11.55	0.000	4.815912	6.837469

Appendix 20 Chlorophyta model selected by lasso Aug 17.

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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	20
Model	4.87419094	2	2.43709547	F(2, 17)	=	10.48
Residual	3.95370329	17	.232570782	Prob > F	=	0.0011
				R-squared	=	0.5521
				Adj R-squared	=	0.4994
Total	8.82789424	19	.464626012	Root MSE	=	.48226

logchlorop~a	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
sqrtzoototal	-.0166622	.0082609	-2.02	0.060	-.0340912	.0007667
inoutcode						
Inside	.9290756	.2175867	4.27	0.001	.4700079	1.388143
_cons	6.030123	.3314154	18.20	0.000	5.330897	6.729348

Appendix 21 Chlorophyta model selected by lasso Sept 12 sample event.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	66
Model	13.3154563	4	3.32886406	F(4, 61)	=	7.95
Residual	25.5330609	61	.41857477	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.3428
				Adj R-squared	=	0.2997
Total	38.8485172	65	.597669495	Root MSE	=	.64697

logchlorophyta	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
filteredreactivephosphorus	3.350886	1.257298	2.67	0.010	.8367628	5.865009
logdinophyta	.1078325	.0291393	3.70	0.000	.049565	.1661001
fe2382_u	-.1033719	.8459145	-0.12	0.903	-1.794883	1.588139
mg2852_u	-.0124062	.0144497	-0.86	0.394	-.0413001	.0164877
_cons	5.628961	.7053325	7.98	0.000	4.218561	7.039361

EPILOGUE

Image: Last remnants of old growth native cottonwoods along shore of Utah Lake

UTAH LAKE AGING PROCESS

Lakes are temporary pools in a watershed. They are born, age, and eventually die, some more quickly than others depending on many physical, ecological, and human induced factors. As lake's age, they fill with sediment deposited from their tributaries that constantly erode rocks in their watershed. The life expectancy of a lake is partially determined by how much sediment is deposited by its tributaries, how much nutrients the sediments contain, and how fast the lake flushes its nutrient laden sediments downstream via its outlet. As a lake fills with sediment and nutrients it becomes shallower and more eutrophic. Consequently, the aging process accelerates. A large proportion of lakes worldwide eventually become wetlands.

Utah Lake evolved from Lake Bonneville, a deep, clear, oligo-mesotrophic lake. Utah Lake is now a shallow nutrient laden, poorly flushing, eutrophic lake eyeing its potential destiny as a future

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wetland. The lake's retirement plan was postponed for a brief moment on the geologic time scale due to it lying on several seismic faults that deepened the lake by about 3 meters over the centuries during its existence (Dinter 2014). Since the late 1800s, humans resumed and accelerated the lake's ageing process as discussed in this and our previous mesocosm reports and by others cited in the literature cited section of this report.

ALTERNATIVE RESTORATION OPTION

Note: The following restoration option is suggested by the senior author and does not reflect the opinion of the co-authors.

The senior author of this progress report, D.C. Richards suggested for several years that one viable option was for society to consider allowing Utah Lake to peacefully age into wetlands, fens, native cottonwood dominated forest with clear cold, spring fed tributaries meandering within. Richards called this the "80/40 option", reducing the surface area of Utah Lake by 80% and deepening the remaining lake to 40 ft or so. This option would create approximately 80,000 acres of critical wetland, fen, and native cottonwood/pine habitat for many species of wildlife including migratory shorebirds and waterfowl that are rapidly losing wetland habitat throughout the Western Flyway (Richards 2023). Many types of wildlife would flourish in the native Cottonwood dominated 'park' habitat including mule deer, turkey, and potentially elk. Springs, streams, and river corridors that are now partially inundated by lake water would increase in length and sinuosity and would be shaded by ample native canopy cover, kept cool enough to restore a viable native Bonneville Cutthroat Trout (BCT) metapopulation. Nutrients in the tributaries would be usurped by the wetlands. Tributaries would flow clear and cold, and any nutrient concern would be moot. The approximately 20,000-acre remaining Utah Lake would have a heterogenous shoreline dendrologically determined by its tributaries and would be deep enough for native fishes, including BCT, to reestablish and allow ample opportunity for water recreationalists¹⁶. Forestry Fire and State Lands would then inherit a roughly 100,000-acre state park that would rival any state park in the nation and the restoration project would be the envy of the nation, a world travel destination. Tens of miles of hiking and biking trails as well as campground could be established. Utah County's economy would transition towards a circular economy¹⁷ as opposed to its present traditional, unsustainable, linear economy. Richards discussed this option at several meetings and forums. Richards (2024) recently estimated that the ecosystem services provided by Utah Lake, presently

¹⁶ A limnological evaluation of desired depth and topography would need to be conducted to optimize its ecosystem function and prevent hypoxic conditions.

¹⁷ The circular economy is a economic system where materials never become waste and nature is regenerated. In a circular economy, products and materials are kept in circulation through processes like maintenance, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, recycling, and composting. The circular economy tackles climate change and other global challenges, like biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution, by decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources (<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy-introduction/overview>).

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could be worth \$625 million/year based on Li and Tsigaris (2024) valuation of lakes worldwide. The '80/40' option would substantially increase this value.

Results from our mesocosms studies support the option of transitioning Utah Lake to a large wetlands with a smaller deep lake as discussed in this and our previous reports. As it stands now, Utah Lake is trapped in an early successional state (low ecoexergy, high entropy) and is likely incapable of maturation to a high ecoexergy, fully functioning condition that it once was or towards a fully functioning wetland without ecologically enlightened restoration efforts (Richards 2022).

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